

“Anisotropy-Driven Ground State Properties in Frustrated Triangular and Trillium Lattice Antiferromagnets”

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work reported in this thesis is original and has been carried out by me during my tenure as a Integrated PhD student at the **School of Physics, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Thiruvananthapuram** under the supervision of Prof. Ramesh Chandra Nath. This work has not been submitted earlier as a whole or in part for a degree/diploma at this or any other Institution/University. Materials obtained from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the thesis.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the work contained in this project report entitled “**Anisotropy-Driven Ground State Properties in Frustrated Triangular and Trillium Lattice Antiferromagnets**” submitted by **Sebin Joseph Sebastian** (Roll No: **IPHD18017**) to Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Thiruvananthapuram towards the requirement of **Doctor of Philosophy** in Physics has been carried out by him under my supervision and that it has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any degree.

Place: Thiruvananthapuram

Prof. Ramesh Chandra Nath

Date:

Doctoral Advisor

This thesis is dedicated to

Almighty God, *the source of strength, purpose, and grace,*
who carried me through both clarity and uncertainty,
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whose love asked for nothing yet gave me everything,
and whose quiet resilience became the unseen force behind every step I have
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List of Publications

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3. *"Short-range spin freezing in the double trillium lattice spin-liquid candidate $\text{KSrFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ revealed via ^{31}P NMR"* **Sebin J. Sebastian**, Q.-P. Ding, A. A. Tsirlin, R. Nath, Y. Furukawa, [Phys. Rev. B 112, L22040 \(2025\)](#) [Editors' suggestion]
4. *"Static and dynamic properties of a frustrated spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ depleted-kagome antiferromagnet $\text{Cu}_7(\text{TeO}_3)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH}_6)$ "* K.U. Akshay, **Sebin J. Sebastian**, Q.-P. Ding, Y. Furukawa, R. Nath, [Phys. Rev. B 112, 224429 \(2025\)](#)
5. *"Spin fluctuations, absence of magnetic order, and crystal electric field studies in the Yb^{3+} -based triangular lattice antiferromagnet $\text{Rb}_3\text{Yb}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ "* **Sebin J. Sebastian**, R. Kolay, Abhidev. B, Q.-P. Ding, Y. Furukawa, R. Nath, [Phys. Rev. B 112, 104428 \(2025\)](#)
6. *"Disordered ground state in a spin-orbit coupled pseudospin- $\frac{1}{2}$ cobalt-based metal-organic framework magnet with orthogonal spin dimers"* **Sebin J. Sebastian**, S. Mohanty, A. Nath, M. P. Saravanan, S. Mandal, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, [Phys. Rev. Materials 8, 034403 \(2024\)](#)
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8. *“Static and dynamic magnetic properties of the spin- $\frac{5}{2}$ triangle lattice antiferromagnet $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ studied by ^{31}P NMR”*
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Abstract

In this thesis, we have carried out a detailed investigation of the structural and magnetic properties of four geometrically frustrated antiferromagnets (AFMs): (1) $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, (2) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, (3) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, and (4) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The investigation combines structural, thermodynamic, and local-probe techniques such as powder x-ray diffraction, DC magnetization, AC magnetization, pulsed-field magnetization, heat capacity (C_p), neutron powder diffraction, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), and muon spin resonance (μSR). The experimental results are further analyzed with appropriate theoretical models and supported by the band-structure calculations.

$\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ is established as a spin-5/2 triangular-lattice antiferromagnet (TLAF) that undergoes magnetic long-range order (LRO) at $T_N \simeq 10.4$ K. Based on the neutron powder diffraction, we obtained the ground state spin structure to be a collinear AFM with propagation vector $\mathbf{k} = (1, 0, 0)$, where the Fe^{3+} moments align within the ab -plane. The thermodynamic measurements yield a moderate frustration index ($f \simeq 3.6$) and an exchange coupling of $J/k_B \simeq 1.8$ K. Furthermore, the field-dependent magnetization identifies a spin-flop transition near $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T and full saturation at $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T, reflecting an easy plane XY-type anisotropy in the system.

The isostructural TLAFs, $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ with Co^{2+} ($3d^7$) ions, host an effective $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ moment at low temperatures due to strong spin-orbit coupling. Both the compounds exhibit two successive magnetic phase transitions driven by weak easy-axis anisotropy, with $T_{N1} \simeq 1.47$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 1.22$ K for Nb compound, and $T_{N1} \simeq 0.88$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 0.67$ K in the Ta analogue. $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ displays a clear 1/3 magnetization plateau, while $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ exhibits an unusual field-induced disordered phase characterized by gapless excitations with $C_p \propto T^2$, indicating strong quantum fluctuations.

The double trillium lattice compound $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, despite a large AFM Curie-Weiss temperature ($\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -70$ K), does not show any signature of magnetic LRO down to 30 mK. The heat capacity data exhibit a field-independent behavior with a broad maximum near 7 K

and a quadratic low-temperature dependence ($C_{\text{mag}} \propto T^2$). Moreover, the local probe measurements, ^{31}P NMR and μSR , reveal field-independent line broadening below $T^* \simeq 3.5$ K, persistent low-energy spin dynamics, and multiple dynamic relaxations without detecting any static internal field. The longitudinal-field μSR data confirm these dynamics to be sporadic spin fluctuations, observed for the first time in a trillium lattice AFM. Additionally, the band structure calculation confirms all interactions in the trillium network to be AFM, which generate strong frustration in the system, consequently hindering the onset of magnetic LRO and driving the system close to the spin-liquid regime.

Contents

List of Figures	xvii
List of Tables	xxvii
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Motivation	1
1.2 Spin Hamiltonians and Dimensionality	3
1.2.1 Spin-Spin Correlation	5
1.3 Magnetic Frustration	6
1.3.1 Geometric Frustration	8
1.3.2 Frustration due to competing interactions	20
1.3.3 Exchange frustration	21
1.4 Physics of Co^{2+} -based systems	23
1.5 Overview of the thesis	26
2 Experimental Techniques	29
2.1 Powder X-ray Diffraction	29
2.2 Neutron Powder Diffraction	31
2.2.1 Rietveld Refinement	35
2.3 Magnetometry	36
2.3.1 Vibrating Sample Magnetometer	36

2.3.2	SQUID (DC) Magnetometer	38
2.3.3	AC Magnetometry	41
2.4	Heat Capacity	43
2.4.1	Sample Preparation and Measurement	44
2.4.2	Thermal Relaxation Technique	45
2.5	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)	52
2.5.1	Basic Principles of NMR	53
2.5.2	Electron-nucleus interactions	58
2.5.3	NMR Shift	62
2.5.4	Relaxation	66
2.5.5	NMR Data Acquisition and Analysis	74
2.5.6	NMR Experimental Details	80
2.6	Muon-Spin Resonance (μ SR)	82
3	Na₃Fe(PO₄)₂	87
3.1	Experimental details	89
3.2	Results	90
3.2.1	X-ray Diffraction	90
3.2.2	Magnetization	93
3.2.3	Heat Capacity	99
3.2.4	Neutron diffraction	102
3.3	Discussion and Summary	107
4	Sr₃Co(Nb,Ta)₂O₉	111
4.1	Experimental details	113
4.2	Results	114
4.2.1	X-ray Diffraction	114
4.2.2	Magnetization	117

4.2.3	Heat Capacity	122
4.3	Discussion	127
4.4	Conclusion	131
5	KBaFe₂(PO₄)₃	133
5.1	Experimental Details	134
5.2	Results	137
5.2.1	X-ray Diffraction	137
5.2.2	DC and AC magnetization	140
5.2.3	DFT	142
5.2.4	Heat Capacity	143
5.2.5	Electron spin resonance	145
5.2.6	³¹ P NMR	146
5.2.7	μSR	154
5.3	Conclusion	160
6	Summary and Future Directions	161
	Bibliography	165

List of Figures

1.1	Schematic representation of (a) Ising, (b) XY, and (c) Heisenberg models.	4
1.2	A plot of inverse magnetic susceptibility (χ^{-1}) showing the difference between (a) a non-frustrated and (b) a frustrated AFM spin system	7
1.3	Geometric frustration in a triangular lattice antiferromagnet.	8
1.4	Crystal lattice showing (a) kagome, (b) hyper-kagome, (c) pyrochlore, and (d) trillium geometries.	9
1.5	A section of triangular lattice showing $J_1 - J_2$ model with J_1 and $J_2 > 0$	11
1.6	(a, b) Schematic representation of phase diagrams for a $J_1 - J_2$ model on TLAF.	12
1.7	The phase diagram for $J_1 - J_2$ XXZ model on a $S = 1/2$ TLAF.	13
1.8	(a) Schematic of an anisotropic Heisenberg TLAF with J (chain) and J' (inter-chain) couplings. (b) Corresponding phase diagram showing the distinct ground states across different J'/J regimes.	14
1.9	The field evolution of magnetic spins in Heisenberg TLAF	17
1.10	Trillium lattices: (a) single trillium lattice, (b) double trillium lattice, and (c) complex exchange pathways ($J_1 \rightarrow J_5$) in a double trillium lattice.	18
1.11	Schematic illustration of frustration due to competing interactions in (a) 1D spin chain and (b) square lattice.	21
1.12	The schematic illustration of exchange frustration in a honeycomb lattice based on the Kitaev model.	22

1.13	The high-spin state of Co^{2+} [$3d^7$ ($t_{2g}^5 e_g^2$)] configuration in an octahedral crystal field.	23
1.14	The tentative energy diagram that depicts the splitting of 4F state of Co^{2+} under an octahedral crystal field and of the $^4T_{1g}$ state under SOC	24
2.1	Schematic illustration of Bragg diffraction from lattice planes.	30
2.2	Schematic representation of a neutron scattering process.	32
2.3	Schematic diagram of a DC SQUID loop.	38
2.4	Configuration of a SQUID magnetometer in a MPMS setup.	40
2.5	Schematic representation of the coil arrangement in an AC magnetometer. . .	42
2.6	Schematic diagram of the heat capacity puck used in the PPMS, showing its thermal and electrical connections (adapted from the Quantum Design user manual).	45
2.7	Schematic of a conventional thermal relaxation calorimeter.	46
2.8	Temporal profiles of heater power and platform temperature in (a) the <i>single-tau</i> model and (b) the <i>two-tau</i> model.	52
2.9	(a) Visualization of the \vec{H}_{eff} in the rotating frame. The static field component ($H_z - \omega/\gamma_N$) \hat{z} (magenta) and the transverse <i>rf</i> field $H_1\hat{x}$ (blue) combine to form the effective field \vec{H}_{eff} (red). The magnetic moment vector $\vec{\mu}$ (green) precesses about \vec{H}_{eff} in a conical trajectory, as shown by the dotted circular path. (b) Response of magnetic moment towards a 90° pulse, and its relaxation back to equilibrium. (c) Schematic representation of FID: variation of transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) with delay time (t).	56
2.10	Diagram showing the Zeeman energy level splitting for $I = 1/2$ nucleus.	58
2.11	Schematic representation of all possible hyperfine interactions in an Fe^{3+} -based system.	59
2.12	Effect of effective field in the NMR spectra.	63

2.13 NMR signal detection setup: A rf coil wound around the sample which can experience an oscillating rf field H_1 along the x -direction. The coil is placed inside the magnet with static field H_0 along the z -direction.	74
2.14 Schematic representation of FID as mentioned in the text.	75
2.15 Spin-echo process by employing a $\pi/2 - \pi$ pulse sequence.	78
2.16 (a) Pulse sequence for T_1 measurement. (b) Variation of longitudinal magnetization as a function of τ_1	78
2.17 (a) Pulse sequence for T_2 measurement. (b) Variation of transverse magnetization as a function of τ	79
2.18 Schematic representation of a NMR resonant circuit in (a) parallel-tuned series-matched (b) series-tuned parallel-matched configurations. C_T and C_M are the capacitors used for tuning and impedance matching, respectively, while L denotes the coil inductance.	80
2.19 (a) The probability of positron emission in the direction of each blue arrow is indicated by its length. Positrons are preferentially emitted along the muon spin direction (shown in a red arrow). Experimental geometries for (b) zero-field (ZF- μ SR), (c) longitudinal-field (LF- μ SR), and (d) transverse field (TF- μ SR).	83
2.20 Pelletized powder sample of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ loaded on to the sample holder of FLAME spectrometer in $S\mu S$ for dilution measurements.	85
3.1 (a) Crystal structure of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ showing triangular layers sculpted by the corner-shared FeO_6 octahedra and PO_4 tetrahedra. Location of Na^+ ions is also shown. (b) A section of the layer showing Fe^{3+} ions linked via PO_4 tetrahedra on an anisotropic triangular lattice.	88

- 3.2 Powder XRD pattern of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ measured at (a) $T = 300$ K and (b) $T = 12.5$ K. The open circles are the experimental data and the solid black line is the Rietveld refined fit. The Bragg positions are indicated by green vertical bars and the bottom solid blue line indicates the difference between the experimental and calculated intensities. 91
- 3.3 The lattice constants (a , b , and c), and unit cell volume (V_{cell}) are plotted as a function of temperature from 12.5 to 300 K. The solid line in (b) represents the fit using Eq. (3.1). 92
- 3.4 (a) χ as a function of temperature in an applied field $\mu_0 H = 0.5$ T. The downward arrow points to the transition temperature (T_N). The solid line represents the fit using isotropic triangular lattice model [Eq. (3.4)]. Inset: comparison of experimental data with spin-5/2 uniform chain model and isotropic triangular lattice simulated using QMC and full diagonalization (FD), respectively. (b) Inverse susceptibility $1/\chi$ vs T and the solid line represents the CW fit, as discussed in the text. Upper inset: $\chi(T)$ measured in different fields, below T_N . Lower inset: $\chi(T)$ measured under ZFC and FC conditions in $\mu_0 H = 0.01$ T. 94
- 3.5 (a) Magnetization (M) vs H measured at various temperatures from 1.8 K to 50 K. The encircled portion depicts the field induced transition regime. (b) The derivative dM/dH vs H is plotted at various temperatures from 1.8 K to 9 K in-order to highlight the field induced transition. 95
- 3.6 Magnetization (M) and its field derivative dM/dH vs H measured at $T = 1.4$ K using pulsed magnetic field in the left and right y -axes, respectively. The pulse field data are scaled with respect to the SQUID data measured up to 7 T. The dash-dotted line represents the saturation magnetization $M_{\text{sat}} \sim 5.2 \mu_B$ per Fe^{3+} ion. The sharp peaks in dM/dH vs H plot depict the spin-flop and saturation fields $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T and $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T, respectively. 98

- 3.7 (a) Heat capacity (C_p) as a function of temperature in zero applied field. The solid line represents the phonon contribution (C_{ph}) [Eq. (3.6)] while the dashed line indicates the magnetic contribution (C_{mag}). Inset: Field dependence of $C_p(T)$ around T_N . (b) C_{mag}/T and S_{mag} vs T in the left and right y -axes, respectively. Inset: C_{mag}/T vs T^2 and the solid line is the linear fit. 100
- 3.8 (a) Temperature evolution of the neutron powder diffraction (NPD) patterns of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the low- Q regime and for temperatures below 15 K. The emergence of magnetic reflections with $k = (1, 0, 0)$ is evident below T_N 103
- 3.9 Rietveld refinement of the neutron powder diffraction data at (a) $T = 15$ K and (b) $T = 1.6$ K, considering only nuclear reflections and nuclear + magnetic reflections, respectively. The experimental data are depicted as open black circles. The red solid line represents the calculated pattern. The difference in intensities of experimental and calculated data is shown as blue solid line at the bottom. The allowed Bragg peaks corresponding to the nuclear (green) and magnetic (pink) reflections are shown as vertical bars. Inset of (a) presents the temperature variation of ordered magnetic moment, below T_N . Inset of (b) presents the variation of flipping ratio (R) in the T -range $5 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$. . . 105
- 3.10 (a) Spin structure of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ derived from the neutron powder diffraction at $T = 1.6$ K. (b) A section of the triangular layer (ab -plane) showing the spin orientation and exchange interactions. 106
- 3.11 $H - T$ phase diagram of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ drawn from the magnetic isotherm, $\chi(T)$, and $C_p(T)$ measurements. H_{SF} represents the critical field at which the SF transition takes place. The point (T_{Bc}, H_{Bc}) denotes the bi-critical point, where the SF transition ends. 109

- 4.1 (a) A 3D view of the crystal structure of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$. The dashed lines guide the triangular layers composed of corner shared CoO_6 and NbO_6 octahedra. The $\text{Co}(1)\text{O}_6$ and $\text{Co}(2)\text{O}_6$ octahedra are shown in different colours. (b) A section of the triangular layer that depicts nearly parallel edge-shared arrangement of CoO_6 octahedra and presents the honeycomb lattice, after removing NbO_6 octahedra. 112
- 4.2 Room temperature powder XRD patterns of (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The black circles show the XRD data and the red line represents the calculated pattern. The blue small vertical lines represent the Bragg positions. The green line at the bottom represents the difference between observed and calculated intensities. 115
- 4.3 χ vs T measured in $\mu_0 H = 1$ T for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. $1/\chi$ after subtracting χ_{VV} is plotted as a function of T in the right y -axis to emphasize the low- T linear portion. Solid line represents the Curie-Weiss fit in the low temperature linear regime, as discussed in the text. 118
- 4.4 Magnetization (M) vs H measured at $T = 1.4$ K using pulsed magnetic field for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The dash-dotted line represents the linear fit to the data in high fields which is extrapolated down to zero field to obtain the Van-Vleck magnetization. The corrected magnetization M_{corr} after the subtraction of Van-Vleck contribution is also plotted vs H . The dashed lines mark the critical fields. dM_{corr}/dH vs H is plotted in the right y -axis to highlight the features at the critical fields. 120
- 4.5 M vs H measured at different temperatures for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. dM/dH vs H is plotted on the right y -axis. 122

- 4.6 Temperature dependent heat capacity [$C_p(T)$] measured in different magnetic fields for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The red dash-dotted line represents the lattice heat capacity using Eq. (4.1). The black solid lines are the power law and power law + nuclear Schottky fits to the low- T data of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. The dashed line in (b) marks the power law with $\alpha = 2$. Lower insets: Variation of α and γ with H in the left and right y -axes, respectively, obtained from the low temperature data fit. Upper inset in (b) is the plot of A vs H^2 with solid line being a linear fit. 123
- 4.7 Difference in heat capacity ΔC ($= C_p - C_{\text{ph}} - C_n$) vs T in different magnetic fields for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The solid lines are the fits using Eq. (4.2). Inset of (b) shows the plot of Δ/k_B and n as a function of H for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ in the left and right y -axes, respectively. The change in magnetic entropy ΔS vs T in different magnetic fields for (c) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (d) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ 125
- 4.8 T vs H phase diagram for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ constructed using the heat capacity and magnetization data. The exotic field induced regime (III) between H_{S1} and H_{S2} for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ is highlighted in a different color. 128
- 5.1 A coupled trillium unit of Fe^{3+} ions, connected via PO_4 tetrahedra. 133
- 5.2 Powder XRD pattern of (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, and (c) $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ measured at $T = 300$ K. The circles are experimental data points and the solid line is the Rietveld refinement fit. The Bragg peak positions are indicated by vertical lines, whereas the bottom solid line indicates the difference between the experimental and calculated intensities. 138
- 5.3 Rietveld refinement of the 80 K high-resolution XRD data for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ 139

- 5.4 (a), (b) Temperature dependence of χ_{dc} , measured under different applied fields for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, respectively. Insets: $1/\chi$ vs T at $\mu_0 H = 0.5$ T and the solid line represents the CW fit. The solid line in (a) represents the classical Monte-Carlo simulation using the optimized exchange parameters from Table. 5.3 for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (c), (d) $\chi_{dc}(T)$ measured under ZFC and FC protocols in $\mu_0 H = 0.01$ T. The characteristic temperature T^* marks the onset of bifurcation between the ZFC and FC curves. (e) M vs H for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ measured at $T = 1.5$ K using pulsed magnetic fields upto 60 T. The pulsed field data are scaled with respect to the $M(H)$ data measured using PPMS at $T = 2$ K. (f) M vs H for $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at $T = 2$ K. Insets of (e) and (f): low-field M vs H data (-0.5 to 0.5 T) at $T = 2$ K showing no hysteresis. 140
- 5.5 Temperature dependence of the real component of ac susceptibility (χ'_{ac}) measured at various frequencies for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The curves are vertically offset for clarity. The vertical dashed line serves as a guide to show no shift in peak position with frequency. 142
- 5.6 C_p vs T in different applied fields along with the power law fit ($C_p = \gamma T^\alpha$) in the low-temperature regime for (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The solid line represents the phonon contribution to the heat capacity (C_{ph}) using the non-magnetic analog, $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. C_{mag}/T vs T in the left y -axis and magnetic entropy ΔS_{mag} vs T in the right y -axis for (c) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (d) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ 143
- 5.7 C_{mag} vs T^2 plot fitted with a straight line at low- T s for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ 144
- 5.8 ESR spectra of (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at some selected temperatures and with magnifications as indicated. The black solid line depicts the fit using a Lorentzian line shape. Temperature dependence of (c) ΔB and (d) B_{res} for both $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Inset of (d): $1/\chi_{ESR}$ vs T with solid lines indicating the CW fits in the range $10 \leq T \leq 150$ K. 145

- 5.9 Temperature dependent field-sweep ^{31}P NMR spectra measured at 126.6 MHz for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The vertical dashed line marks the Larmor field. Inset: temperature-dependent signal intensity multiplied by temperature with the T_2 corrections. 147
- 5.10 Temperature-dependent ^{31}P NMR spectra measured at 56.4 MHz. Inset: Temperature dependence of ^{31}P NMR shift (\mathcal{K}) at 56.4 MHz and 126.6 MHz overlaid with dc magnetic susceptibility (χ_{dc}) data measured at 2 T. 148
- 5.11 Clogston-Jaccarino plot of \mathcal{K} vs χ with T as an implicit parameter. Inset: $1/(\mathcal{K} - \mathcal{K}_0)$ vs T and the solid line is the CW fit as per Eq. (5.3). 149
- 5.12 Full width at half maximum (ΔB) of the ^{31}P NMR line as a function of temperature, measured at three different frequencies. The solid line represents the magnetization (M) vs T plot for $\mu_0 H = 7$ T. Inset: ΔB as a function of the NMR frequency. 149
- 5.13 Longitudinal magnetization recovery curves at three different temperatures for 56.4 MHz and the solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.4). 150
- 5.14 Temperature dependence of $1/T_1$ at different frequencies, together with the temperature dependence of $\chi_{\text{dc}}T$ measured at 2 T. 151
- 5.15 $1/T_1 T \chi$ vs T using the $1/T_1$ data at 56.4 MHz and χ_{dc} data at 2 T for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The horizontal dashed line marks the T -independent behaviour from the high- T regime. 151
- 5.16 (a) Recovery curves of the transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) plotted against time (t) for temperatures below and above T^* . (b) M_{xy} measured at different temperatures below T^* . The solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.7). 153
- 5.17 $1/T_2$ as a function of temperature measured at various frequencies. The red solid line represents the fit discussed in the text, with $T^* = 3.5$ K. 154

- 5.18 (a) ZF muon spin asymmetry [$A_{ZF}(t)$] at different temperatures for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Left panel: magnified short-time behavior ($t \leq 0.6 \mu\text{s}$) and right panel: long-time tail ($t \geq 0.6 \mu\text{s}$). Solid lines are fits using Eq. (5.8). (b) Muon-spin asymmetry $A_{LF}(t)$ measured under different LFs at $T \simeq 0.1 \text{ K}$. Left panel: enlarged short-time scale; right panel: long-time tail. The dashed lines represent simulated depolarization curves using Eq. (5.9). Solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.10). (c) Temperature dependence of the ZF muon-spin relaxation rates (λ_1 and λ_2). Inset: temperature dependence of the stretching exponent β . (d) Temperature dependence of the fractional weight α . Inset: LF dependence of the contribution ϕ from *sporadic field fluctuations*. 155
- 5.19 Zero-field muon spin asymmetry $A_{ZF}(t)$ measured at the lowest temperature (30 mK) in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. (a) Short-time region ($t \leq 0.3 \mu\text{s}$); the solid line shows the fit using Eq. (5.8), with an exponent $\beta \simeq 3.8$. Constraining $\beta = 2$ yields a noticeably poorer agreement with the data; as shown by red dashed line. (b) Background Kubo-Toyabe contribution (A_b) arising from muons stopping in the sample holder; the solid line shows the fit using Eq. (5.8) with σ fixed at the typical value expected for copper, $\sim 0.38 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$. (c) Longitudinal field dependence of the muon-spin relaxation rate (λ') associated with the $(1 - \phi)$ contribution in Eq. (5.10); the red dashed line is shown as a guide to the eye. . 157

List of Tables

1.1	Experimental examples of TLAFs with single-ion anisotropy showing easy-axis and easy-plane anisotropies.	15
3.1	Irreducible representations and basis vectors for the space group $C2/c$ with propagation vector $k = (1,0,0)$, obtained using the Basreps software. The atoms are defined according to Fe1: $(0, 0, 0)$ and Fe2: $(0, 0, 0.5)$	106
4.1	Lattice parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the room temperature powder XRD data of $Sr_3Co(Nb,Ta)_2O_9$ (Monoclinic, $P2_1/c$).	114
4.2	Atomic positions obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the room temperature powder XRD data of $Sr_3Co(Nb,Ta)_2O_9$	116
5.1	Lattice parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the powder XRD data.	137
5.2	Refined atomic positions (x,y,z) , atomic displacement parameters (U_{iso} , in 10^{-2} \AA^2), and site occupancies for $KBaFe_2(PO_4)_3$ at 80 K. The space group is $P2_13$, and the refined lattice parameter is $a = 9.87440(1) \text{ \AA}$	139
5.3	Exchange couplings J_i (in K) in $KBaFe_2(PO_4)_3$, calculated in the present work using DFT, and optimized to achieve the best fit of the experimental magnetic susceptibility [Fig. 5.4(a)]. The labels of $J_1 - J_5$ follow "Nat. Commun. 15 , 7191 (2024)".	142

Chapter 1

Introduction

I think you can improve on everything; you're never perfect.

MAX VERSTAPPEN, *F1 World Champion*

1.1 Motivation

Magnetism has been a topic of renewed interest since the discovery of natural magnets such as magnetite (*magnes lapis*, or commonly known as lodestone) [1]. Its practical use in compasses marked one of the earliest technological applications, enabling navigation during the age of exploration. The modern understanding of magnetism began to take shape with the formulation of Maxwell's electromagnetic theory, which unified electric and magnetic fields [2]. The microscopic origin of magnetism, however, was only clarified after the advent of quantum mechanics, which revealed that the magnetic moment of an electron arises from its combined spin and orbital degrees of freedom. Since then, magnetism has become a central topic in condensed matter physics, where collective interactions among localized spins give rise to a variety of interesting and exotic phases. This evolution from classical to quantum descriptions has expanded the field of magnetism beyond conventional ferromagnetic (FM) and antiferromagnetic (AFM) systems to include more complex magnetic ground states.

In this context, studying exotic quantum phases in magnets has become a cornerstone of

modern condensed matter physics. Among these, *frustrated magnets* constitute a fundamental class of systems, as their ground states often deviate from conventional magnetic long-range order (LRO) [3]. The concept of magnetic frustration was first introduced by Gérard Toulouse in 1977 [4]. In typical magnets, lowering the temperature leads to a stable spin configuration, resulting in a magnetic LRO. However, frustration arising from geometrical constraints (i.e., spin lattice) or competing exchange interactions suppresses such LRO and results in degenerate ground states. As a result, frustrated systems often display unconventional spin dynamics and ground states beyond the classical Néel picture [5, 6].

As far as theory is concerned, in low-dimensional magnets, the magnetic LRO is forbidden down to $T = 0$ in one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) isotropic Heisenberg systems due to strong quantum fluctuations [7]. Such quantum fluctuations are enhanced for systems with reduced spin quantum number. However, weak interchain or interlayer couplings and small anisotropies which are unavoidable in real materials often drive the magnetic LRO at finite temperatures. Magnetic frustration in such systems enhances the effect of quantum fluctuations (with a finite zero-point motion) giving rise to entangled spins through coherent superposition of local singlets and exotic quantum phases. Some examples of such phases include quantum spin liquids (QSLs) [8], spin-ice states [9], and field-induced phases such as the Bose–Einstein condensation (BEC) of triplons [10]. Other well-established phenomena include multiferroicity [11], spin nematic order [12], magnetization plateaux [13, 14], magnetic skyrmion lattices [15], and topological excitations such as Majorana fermions in Kitaev magnets [16]. Furthermore, topological transport responses, including anomalous and thermal quantum Hall effects, demonstrate the broad range of emergent behavior in frustrated magnets [17, 18].

Several lattice geometries are recognized as ideal hosts for frustration-driven physics. In 2D, the triangular and kagome networks serve as canonical examples, while in three dimensions (3D), the hyperkagome, pyrochlore, and trillium lattices represent prominent frustrated frameworks [6]. Apart from lattice geometry, frustration may also arise from competing exchange interactions such as nearest-neighbor (NN) and next-nearest-neighbor (NNN) interactions or

between FM and AFM interactions. These competing interactions often produce complex phase diagrams, as demonstrated in several 1D and 2D model systems [19–23].

In real materials, the idealized conditions proposed in theoretical models are rarely fulfilled. Various intrinsic perturbations, including exchange anisotropy, Dzyaloshinskii–Moriya (DM) interactions, interactions beyond NN coupling, structural disorder, and crystalline defects, can partially lift the ground-state degeneracy [13, 23–26]. Depending on their nature, these perturbations may also stabilize magnetic LRO or lead to complex dynamic or partially ordered states. Therefore, discovering new frustrated magnetic materials and investigating their microscopic spin dynamics through detailed experimental and theoretical studies are essential for understanding the mechanisms that govern these exotic quantum phases.

1.2 Spin Hamiltonians and Dimensionality

According to the Bohr–Van Leeuwen theorem, the magnetism in solids is inherently quantum mechanical in origin. It arises from the intrinsic spin of the electron and its orbital motion around the nucleus. Each electron carries a magnetic moment ($\boldsymbol{\mu}$), which in atomic units can be expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\mu} = -g\mu_B(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{S}), \quad (1.1)$$

where \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{L} are the spin and orbital angular momentum operators, respectively, μ_B is the Bohr magneton, and g is the Landé g -factor. While the behavior of an isolated magnetic moment is relatively simple, the situation becomes remarkably complex in solids where a large number [$\mathcal{O}(\sim N_A)$] of such moments coexist and interact. In such a case, the cooperative nature of these interactions produces emergent properties that cannot be deduced solely based on isolated spins. Therefore, depending on these couplings, strength, symmetry, and dimensionality, magnetic materials can exhibit a wide range of magnetic ground states.

For the magnetic systems discussed in this thesis, the essential physics is often captured by the Heisenberg model, which serves as a toy model. The Heisenberg Hamiltonian can be

written as

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (1.2)$$

where J_{ij} denotes the exchange coupling between spins \mathbf{S}_i and \mathbf{S}_j located at the i^{th} and j^{th} sites, respectively. The sign of J_{ij} determines the favored spin alignment: $J_{ij} < 0$ leads to FM, whereas $J_{ij} > 0$ stabilizes AFM arrangements. This model provides a starting point to explore the interplay between exchange interactions, lattice geometry, and dimensionality.

A fundamental framework for classifying spin systems involves two complementary notions of dimensionality: the spatial dimensionality of the underlying lattice (d) and the spin dimensionality (n) associated with the spin degrees of freedom. The lattice dimensionality d characterizes how magnetic spins are arranged in a material. For instance, 1D ($d = 1$) systems appear as spin chains, while 2D ($d = 2$) lattices are realized in frustrated geometries such as triangular, square, or kagome networks. Such low-dimensional systems ($d = 1, 2$) are identified to be strongly influenced by quantum fluctuations, which often suppress the magnetic LRO, consistent with the Mermin–Wagner theorem [7]. On the other hand, systems with 3D ($d = 3$) networks typically stabilize magnetic LRO at low temperatures. Recently, a particular class of highly frustrated 3D lattices, such as the hyperkagome, pyrochlore, and trillium lattices, is identified as hosts for QSL and various other unconventional magnetic ground states [3, 27–29].

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of (a) Ising, (b) XY, and (c) Heisenberg models.

The second notion, spin dimensionality (n), describes the number of independent components of the spin vector that participate in the interaction. Figure 1.1 summarizes these three canonical spin models. The simplest case is $n = 1$, where only a single spin component

contributes. This is the celebrated Ising model [Fig. 1.1(a)], whose Hamiltonian is

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{Ising}} = \sum_{i,j} J_z S_i^z S_j^z, \quad (1.3)$$

with spins restricted to align parallel or antiparallel along the z -axis. For $n = 2$, spins can fluctuate within a plane, giving rise to the XY model [Fig. 1.1(b)]

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{XY}} = \sum_{i,j} \left(J_x S_i^x S_j^x + J_y S_i^y S_j^y \right), \quad (1.4)$$

which plays a central role in understanding topological phase transitions such as the Berezinskii–Kosterlitz–Thouless (BKT) transition (vortex-antivortex mixing) in 2D [30]. The most general case, $n = 3$, corresponds to the Heisenberg class, where all spin components are active [Fig. 1.1(c)]. In the anisotropic form (the XYZ model), the Hamiltonian is expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{XYZ}} = \sum_{i,j} \left(J_x S_i^x S_j^x + J_y S_i^y S_j^y + J_z S_i^z S_j^z \right), \quad (1.5)$$

which reduces to an isotropic Heisenberg Hamiltonian [Eq. (1.2)] for $J_x = J_y = J_z$.

1.2.1 Spin-Spin Correlation

The spin-spin correlation function is fundamental in understanding the magnetic systems, since it encodes information regarding the degree of order and the nature of excitations in the ground state. For a given Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} , the two-point spin correlation function between sites i and j at temperature T is defined as [31]

$$\langle \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \rangle = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{NZ} \text{Tr} \left[e^{-\frac{\mathcal{H}}{k_B T}} (\vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j) \right], \quad (1.6)$$

where N is the total number of spins, $Z = \text{Tr}(e^{-\mathcal{H}/k_B T})$ is the partition function, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. In real systems, Eq. (1.6) measures how the orientation of one spin

is correlated with another spin located at a distance $|\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j|$ away.

Thus, for a magnetically ordered state, the correlation between two spins remains finite even at infinite separation. In such a case, we can define the condition for a magnetic LRO state in terms of spin-spin correlation as

$$\lim_{|\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j| \rightarrow \infty} \langle \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \rangle \neq 0. \quad (1.7)$$

On the contrary, there are exotic states like QSLs, where spins retain strong entanglement and remain disordered down to $T = 0$ K. In these conditions, the spin-spin correlation function provides crucial insight into the nature of the excitations. For instance, in the case of a gapless spin liquid, low-energy excitations lead to a power-law decay of correlations

$$\langle \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \rangle \propto |\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j|^{-\alpha}, \quad (1.8)$$

with α depending on the universality class of the spin liquid. Alternatively, for a gapped spin liquid, the presence of an excitation gap causes correlations to decay exponentially with distance

$$\langle \vec{S}_i \cdot \vec{S}_j \rangle \propto \exp \left[-\frac{|\vec{x}_i - \vec{x}_j|}{\zeta} \right], \quad (1.9)$$

where ζ is the correlation length. This behavior is a characteristic of resonating-valence-bond (RVB) type spin liquids and other short-range entangled states.

1.3 Magnetic Frustration

In conventional magnetic systems, in order to minimize the interaction energy, the ground state is usually well defined, either spins align parallel in a FM or anti-parallel in an AFM. However, there exist many situations where such a simple arrangement is not possible. When spins cannot satisfy all pairwise exchange interactions simultaneously, the system cannot stabilize in a single unique configuration of lowest energy. Instead, many nearly degenerate states appear,

giving rise to the phenomenon known as *magnetic frustration* [3]. Consequently, it amplifies the role of quantum fluctuations in the low-dimensional frustrated magnets, and often suppresses the onset of magnetic LRO to $T \ll J$.

Figure 1.2: A plot of inverse magnetic susceptibility (χ^{-1}) showing the difference between (a) a non-frustrated and (b) a frustrated AFM spin system

Based on the mean-field approximation, the strength of these interactions is reflected in the Curie-Weiss (CW) temperature (θ_{CW}), given by [32]

$$|\theta_{CW}| = \frac{S(S+1)}{3k_B} \sum_i z_i J_i, \quad (1.10)$$

where, the summation is taken over all nearest-neighbor spins, J_i represent the exchange couplings, z_i is the corresponding coordination number, and S is the spin quantum number. An effective way to visualize the degree of magnetic frustration is by plotting the temperature dependence of the inverse magnetic susceptibility (χ^{-1}). Figure 1.2(a) presents an ideal unfrustrated AFM, where the ordering temperature T_N is of the same order as $|\theta_{CW}|$. In contrast, frustrated systems often order (T_N) at much lower temperatures than $|\theta_{CW}|$ as depicted in Fig. 1.2(b). In certain cases, the magnetic LRO may be suppressed completely to absolute zero temperature, resulting in QSL-like states. To quantify frustration, Ramirez introduced an

empirical quantity, *frustration index* f , defined as [33]

$$f = \frac{|\theta_{\text{CW}}|}{T_{\text{N}}}. \quad (1.11)$$

Materials with $f > 10$ are generally classified as highly frustrated magnets [34]. The two possible sources of magnetic frustration are (i) geometry of the spin lattice and (ii) competing exchange interactions, which will be discussed in the following section.

1.3.1 Geometric Frustration

Figure 1.3: Geometric frustration in a triangular lattice antiferromagnet.

Geometric frustration arises when the spatial arrangement of magnetic ions in a lattice prevents all pairwise exchange interactions simultaneously. The prototypical case is the triangular lattice antiferromagnet (TLAF) (Fig. 1.3), where three spins interacting antiferromagnetically cannot be aligned antiparallel, resulting in a manifold of nearly degenerate configurations. With the triangle as a primary motif, we can realize various other frustrated lattices such as the kagome lattice in 2D and the hyperkagome, pyrochlore, and trillium lattices in 3D.

When the triangular motifs are rearranged into a corner-sharing geometry in 2D, they form the kagome lattice (meaning: *basket eye*) [Fig. 1.4(a)]. Compared to the triangular lattice with a coordination number $z = 6$, the kagome lattice has lesser connectivity ($z = 4$). This reduced

value of z produces numerous degenerate ground states. Interestingly, in the nearest-neighbor Heisenberg AFM on the kagome lattice, the classical ground state is macroscopically degenerate and is predicted to yield unconventional quantum-disordered phases like QSL. In this context, Herbertsmithite $[\text{ZnCu}_3(\text{OH})_6\text{Cl}_2]$, discovered in 2005 [35], remains the archetypal kagome QSL candidate [36]. Extensive studies, including inelastic neutron scattering, revealed a continuum of magnetic excitations consistent with fractionalized spinon excitations, a hallmark of QSL [37]. While early experiments faced challenges due to Cu–Zn site mixing, careful analysis combining nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and neutron measurements has provided evidence that the intrinsic kagome layers host a gapped QSL ground state [38,39]. This interpretation was further supported by the recent NMR work on related materials such as Zn-Barlowite [40].

Beyond Herbertsmithite, polymorphs such as Kapellasite and Haydeeite demonstrate how competing NN and NNN interactions can tune kagome systems toward contrasting ground states, ranging from gapless QSL behavior to FM [41,42]. In addition, kagome FM has recently drawn attention as hosts of topological flat magnon bands and magnon Hall transport, as observed in $\text{Cu}[1,3\text{-bdc}]$ [43,44]. These findings highlight the kagome lattice as a fertile ground for exploring spin-liquid physics and other topological phenomena in quantum magnets.

Figure 1.4: Crystal lattice showing (a) kagome, (b) hyper-kagome, (c) pyrochlore, and (d) trillium geometries.

Extending the idea of corner-sharing triangular motifs into 3D leads to the *hyperkagome* lattice [Fig. 1.4(b)], which consists of a 3D network of corner-sharing triangles. This geometry

is realized in compounds such as $\text{Na}_4\text{Ir}_3\text{O}_8$ and $\text{PbCuTe}_2\text{O}_6$, both of which have been proposed as QSL candidates [45, 46]. Another prominent family of 3D geometrically frustrated systems is the *pyrochlore* lattice, composed of corner-sharing tetrahedra [Fig. 1.4(c)]. Materials with the general chemical formula $A_2B_2O_7$, where A is typically a trivalent ion and B is a transition-metal ion, display an exceptional diversity of emergent behavior [47]. Depending on the interplay of exchange couplings, anisotropy, and multipolar interactions, pyrochlore systems can host exotic states such as spin ice [48], spin glass [49], and cooperative paramagnetism [50]. These compounds clearly illustrate the role of 3D connectivity in enhancing degeneracy and stabilizing unconventional ground states.

Of particular importance to this thesis is the *trillium lattice*, a chiral three-dimensional network of corner-sharing equilateral triangles. This unique geometry combines the simplicity of triangular motifs with the complexity of 3D connectivity, making it a promising platform for realizing exotic phases, including QSL.

1.3.1.1 Triangular Lattice

The simplest motif and the cornerstone of frustrated magnetism is the $S = 1/2$ AFM spins on a triangular lattice (see Fig. 1.3). Interest in this motif dates back to Anderson's RVB theory in 1973, which predicted a quantum superposition of singlet pairs, now known as QSL [3, 51, 52]. This early idea sparked a flurry of research on TLAFs, as potential hosts for various unconventional states driven by quantum fluctuations. However, this model had several caveats.

In the classical (large-spin) limit, a TLAF develops magnetic LRO. The spins arrange themselves in a non-collinear 120° configuration within a plane, where the frustration is released by each spin orienting 120° relative to its neighbors [53–58]. This state, known as the three-sublattice Néel order, represents a unique ground state that balances the competing NN interactions [59]. Remarkably, even for the $S = 1/2$ NN Heisenberg model on a TLAF, quantum fluctuations do not destroy this 120° order. In fact, although the ordered moment is strongly reduced compared to the classical case, a robust *quasi-classical* state still persists [60]. However,

in real materials, the inherent exchange anisotropy and inter-layer couplings often have broad implications, leading to more complex and non-trivial ground states [61]. These features make the triangular lattice a paradigmatic example of geometrical frustration, where strong quantum effects coexist with magnetic LRO. Nevertheless, the introduction of further competing interactions or anisotropies can destabilize the ordered state, allowing the possibility of exotic phases like QSL to emerge [24]. Overall, diverse phase regimes are anticipated in TLAFs while going from a classical (high spin) to quantum (low spin) limit owing to the geometrical frustration in concurrence with magnetic anisotropy and the effect of quantum fluctuations [62, 63].

While the NN Heisenberg model captures the essential physics of the 120° Néel state, it does not fully ponder the richness of frustrated magnetism on the triangular lattice. In real frustrated magnets, further competing interactions beyond the NN exchange are often present and can significantly modify the ground state. Among these, the NNN interaction J_2 plays a pivotal role, as it introduces an additional source of frustration that competes with the 120° order. Inclusion of J_1 and J_2 into Eq. (1.2) leads to the celebrated $J_1 - J_2$ TLAF model.

1.3.1.2 $J_1 - J_2$ model on a Triangular Lattice

Figure 1.5: A section of triangular lattice showing $J_1 - J_2$ model with J_1 and $J_2 > 0$.

The $J_1 - J_2$ model on a TLAF is illustrated in Fig. 1.5 and the corresponding Hamiltonian

Figure 1.6: (a, b) Schematic representation of phase diagrams for a $J_1 - J_2$ model on TLAF.

can be written as

$$\mathcal{H} = J_1 \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j + J_2 \sum_{\langle\langle i,j \rangle\rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (1.12)$$

where J_1 and $J_2 > 0$ denote the NN and NNN exchange interactions, respectively. The classical phase diagram for the $S = 1/2$ case is shown in Fig. 1.6(a). It contains three regimes: (i) a coplanar three-sublattice 120° Néel order for $J_2/J_1 < 1/8$, (ii) a macroscopically degenerate four-sublattice manifold for $1/8 < J_2/J_1 < 1$, which is lifted by quantum fluctuations through the “order-from-disorder” mechanism to yield either a tetrahedral or collinear stripe order, and (iii) an incommensurate spiral phase for $J_2/J_1 > 1$ [64]. These predicted phases highlight the likelihood of delicate competition among interactions, which gives rise to various quantum-disordered ground states near the phase boundaries.

Recent numerical studies have modified the phase diagram in Fig. 1.6(a). Using variational Monte Carlo, density-matrix renormalization group (DMRG), and pseudofermion functional

renormalization group calculations, Iqbal *et al.* established the presence of a QSL phase in the intermediate window $0.08 \lesssim J_2/J_1 \lesssim 0.16$ [23]. The modified phase diagram illustrated in Fig. 1.6(b) shows that the QSL regime is sandwiched between the 120° Néel order and collinear stripe order, a result consistent across various computational methods [65]. Importantly, their variational studies favor a gapless $U(1)$ Dirac spin liquid [66], in contrast to earlier proposal of a gapped \mathbb{Z}_2 state [67].

Figure 1.7: The phase diagram for $J_1 - J_2$ XXZ model on a $S = 1/2$ TLAF.

Very recently, attention has been focussed on the anisotropic extension relevant for spin-orbit coupled TLAFs, captured by the easy-axis $S = 1/2$ $J_1 - J_2$ XXZ model with Hamiltonian [8, 68, 69],

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{n=1,2} J_n \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle_n} (S_i^x S_j^x + S_i^y S_j^y + \Delta S_i^z S_j^z), \quad (1.13)$$

where $\Delta \geq 1$ encodes Ising anisotropy. A comprehensive study by Gallegos *et al.* employed large-scale DMRG to map out its ground-state phase diagram [70]. As shown in Fig. 1.7, the spin-liquid phase is found at the Heisenberg point ($\Delta = 1$), which survives over an extensive range of easy-axis anisotropies, mediating between the three-sublattice ‘‘Y’’ supersolid and

the stripe- z phase. This work reveals that the quantum-disordered regime is not confined to the isotropic limit but persists deep into the easy-axis regime, highlighting the robustness of frustration-induced QSL behavior in a $S = 1/2$ triangular-lattice J_1 - J_2 system.

1.3.1.3 Anisotropic (J - J') Triangular-Lattice model

Figure 1.8: (a) Schematic of an anisotropic Heisenberg TLAF with J (chain) and J' (inter-chain) couplings. (b) Corresponding phase diagram showing the distinct ground states across different J'/J regimes.

A convenient way to tune frustration in the TLAF is to allow two inequivalent NN couplings, J along one set of bonds (chains) and J' along the two zigzag directions as shown in Fig 1.8(a). The corresponding Hamiltonian can be written as

$$\mathcal{H} = J \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j + J' \sum_{\langle\langle i,j \rangle\rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j, \quad (1.14)$$

with $J, J' > 0$. Reducing J'/J enhances quantum fluctuations: in the limit $J' \rightarrow 0$, the system becomes weakly coupled spin chains with spinon-like continua, whereas increasing J'/J toward unity restores two-dimensional correlations. Based on the large-scale quantum Monte-Carlo (QMC) and variational studies, a phase diagram was predicted for varying ratios of J'/J , as shown in Fig. 1.8(b) [71–73]. These results establish that the spatial anisotropy can stabilize QSLs over a finite J'/J parameter window [22,71,74]. In particular, two regimes were identified:

a gapless, fractionalized spin liquid for $J'/J \lesssim 0.6$ and a more conventional spin liquid with a small spin gap for $0.6 \lesssim J'/J \lesssim 0.85$ [71, 73]. Importantly, neither signature of translation-symmetry breaking, a singlet-state, nor a spin-Peierls order was found in either regime.

The well-studied realizations of anisotropic TLAFs are the organic compound κ -(BEDT-TTF)₂Cu₂(CN)₃ (κ -ETCu) and the inorganic salts Cs₂CuCl₄ and Cs₂CuBr₄. In κ -ETCu, no magnetic LRO has been detected down to ~ 32 mK despite a large exchange scale of ~ 250 K and $J'/J \simeq 0.8$, placing it close to the QSL regime of the J - J' phase diagram [75]. In contrast, Cs₂CuCl₄ has a more anisotropic exchange with $J'/J \simeq 0.34$, and neutron scattering experiments reveal signatures of a QSL-like ground state along with field-induced BEC of magnons [76–78]. The isostructural compound Cs₂CuBr₄ has a larger $J'/J \simeq 0.74$ and shows magnetic LRO at $T_N \simeq 1.4$ K, together with an apparent 1/3 magnetization plateau in applied field [79–81].

1.3.1.4 Triangular Lattice Antiferromagnets with Single-ion Anisotropy

Compound	Anisotropy	T_{N1} (K)	T_{N2} (K)	Ref.
CsNiCl ₃	easy-axis	4.84	4.4	[82]
RbNiCl ₃	easy-axis	11.25	11.11	[83]
CsNiBr ₃	easy-axis	14.06	11.51	[84]
CsMnI ₃	easy-axis	11.2	8.17	[85]
Rb ₄ Mn(MoO ₄) ₃	easy-axis	2.42	2.80	[86]
Ba ₃ CoNb ₂ O ₉	easy-axis	1.39	1.13	[87]
Ba ₃ CoTa ₂ O ₉	easy-axis	0.70	0.57	[88]
Ba ₃ MnNb ₂ O ₉	easy-axis	3.4	3.1	[89]
Sr ₃ NiTa ₂ O ₉	easy-axis	5.1	4.8	[90]
Ba ₃ NiSb ₂ O ₉	easy-axis	13.5	13.0	[14]
CsMnBr ₃	easy-plane	8.32	–	[91]
CsVBr ₃	easy-plane	20.4	–	[92]
RbMnBr ₃	easy-plane	10	–	[93]

Table 1.1: Experimental examples of TLAFs with single-ion anisotropy showing easy-axis and easy-plane anisotropies.

In layered TLAF, single-ion anisotropy is often crucial in determining the magnetic ground

state and the sequence of phase transitions. The Hamiltonian that captures this effect is extended from Eq. (1.14) as

$$\mathcal{H} = J \sum_{\langle i,j \rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j + J' \sum_{\langle\langle i,j \rangle\rangle} \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j + D \sum_i (S_i^z)^2 - g\mu_B H \sum_i S_i^z. \quad (1.15)$$

Here, D is the single-ion anisotropy constant and the last term denotes the Zeeman energy in an applied field H . The sign of D defines the preferred spin orientation: $D > 0$ corresponds to easy-plane anisotropy, confining spins to the xy -plane, whereas $D < 0$ corresponds to easy-axis anisotropy, favoring alignment along the z -axis. In the limit $D = 0$, the system reduces to the isotropic Heisenberg model. The presence of anisotropy leads to distinct behaviors in the TLAF. Easy-axis systems ($D < 0$) usually display two successive transitions, a collinear phase stabilized just below the upper ordering temperature T_{N1} , and a coplanar 120° structure appearing at a lower temperature T_{N2} . This has been observed in various TLAFs including the celebrated triple perovskites $\text{Ba}_3(\text{Mn,Co})\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ [87–89, 94–101] and $\text{Li}_2\text{NiW}_2\text{O}_8$ [63]. In contrast, easy-plane systems ($D > 0$) typically undergo a single transition directly into the 120° ordered state.

Some other experimental realizations for easy-axis and easy-plane anisotropy in TLAFs are tabulated in Table 1.1. These examples highlight how the interplay between exchange interactions and single-ion anisotropy controls the low-temperature phase transitions and field-induced phases of TLAFs

1.3.1.5 Phase diagram of TLAF under magnetic field

A simple illustration depicting the field-evolution of magnetic spins is shown in Fig. 1.9. Without an applied magnetic field, the Heisenberg TLAF stabilizes in a coplanar three-sublattice 120° Néel configuration. Upon applying a field, the system follows a well-established sequence of phases before reaching full polarization at the saturation field, $H = H_{\text{sat}}$. At low fields ($\mu_0 H \leq 0.2H_{\text{sat}}$), the spins undergo canting continuously into the Y-state. At intermediate fields, quantum and thermal fluctuations select the collinear *up–up–down* (*uud*) arrangement ($\mu_0 H \approx 0.33 H_{\text{sat}}$), giving rise to the characteristic $1/3$ –magnetization plateau [102, 103].

Figure 1.9: The field evolution of magnetic spins in Heisenberg TLAF

Further, at higher fields, the system enters a canted V-state ($0.6H_{\text{sat}} \leq \mu_0 H \leq 0.8H_{\text{sat}}$), which ultimately evolves into the fully polarized saturation state [104, 105]. This cascade of spin textures: Y, *uud*, and V states, represents one of the canonical hallmarks of geometrical frustration in TLAFs. Beyond this idealized isotropic scenario, perturbations such as spatial anisotropy, further-neighbor interactions, or spin-orbit coupling can substantially reshape the H - T phase diagram. In particular, exchange anisotropy has been shown to broaden the stability range of the $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ magnetization plateau and, depending on its nature and strength, it may even stabilize additional ordered or quantum-disordered phases [106]. Furthermore, the exchange anisotropy explained by Eq. (1.13) has been shown to favor stripe-like correlations, while further-neighbor couplings can suppress the plateau or extend the stability of collinear phases [70].

The field-induced phases predicted for TLAFs have been realized in many candidate materials. A prominent example is the $S = 1/2$ system Cs_2CuBr_4 , which displays a clear $1/3$ magnetization plateau corresponding to the *uud* state, with an excellent agreement with theoretical predictions [80]. Its isostructural counterpart Cs_2CuCl_4 also exhibits field-driven anomalies consistent with the related canted spin phases [78]. Among more ideal realizations, $\text{Ba}_3\text{CoSb}_2\text{O}_9$ has emerged as a benchmark spin- $1/2$ TLAF. Here, the $1/3$ plateau and the sequence of “Y-*uud*-V” phases are clearly observed over a wide field range [13, 107, 108]. In the $S = 1$ compound $\text{Ba}_3\text{NiSb}_2\text{O}_9$, a non-classical $1/3$ plateau has also been reported [14]. Beyond these low-spin systems, high-spin TLAF can also exhibit plateau physics. A notable example is $\text{RbFe}(\text{MoO}_4)_2$, where Fe^{3+} ($S = 5/2$) moments on a triangular lattice give rise to an extended

1/3 magnetization plateau and a rich sequence of field-induced phases driven by anisotropic exchanges [109, 110]. Another high-spin benchmark is CuFeO_2 (Fe^{3+} , $S = 5/2$), which exhibits multiple field-induced commensurate and incommensurate states, including a 1/5 plateau [111]. Lately, the $S = 5/2$ TLAF $\text{Na}_2\text{BaMn}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ has been shown to host an expanded set of field-induced phases for both in-plane and out-of-plane fields, illustrating how large-spin moments and weak anisotropies reorganize the triangular-lattice phase diagram [112]. Other notable examples of TLAFs exhibiting 1/3 magnetization plateaus include $\text{Ba}_2\text{La}_2\text{NiTe}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (Ni^{2+} ; $S = 1$) [113], $\text{Ba}_2\text{La}_2\text{CoTe}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (Co^{2+} ; $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$) [114], and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ (Co^{2+} ; $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$) [115]. Collectively, these experimental realizations underscore the remarkable interplay between geometrical frustration, exchange anisotropy, and external magnetic fields, firmly establishing the TLAF as a paradigmatic platform for exploring exotic field-induced quantum phases.

1.3.1.6 Trillium Lattice

Figure 1.10: Trillium lattices: (a) single trillium lattice, (b) double trillium lattice, and (c) complex exchange pathways ($J_1 \rightarrow J_5$) in a double trillium lattice.

Trillium lattice (meaning: *tri-parted lily*) is a 3D network of corner-sharing equilateral triangles and may be viewed as the natural 3D analog of the Shastry–Sutherland motif. Each trillium unit belongs to three triangular units, producing a highly frustrated geometry as shown in Fig. 1.10(a). Until today, most trillium lattice compounds are crystallized in a non-centrosymmetric cubic space group, $P2_13$. The inherent lack of inversion symmetry offered by

the space group $P2_13$ makes this lattice intrinsically chiral, which provides a breeding ground for unconventional magnetic states when combined with geometrical frustration.

Historically, the trillium motif attracted attention in the context of itinerant magnets such as MnSi, FeGe, and MnGe, where DM interactions stabilized helical spirals and skyrmion lattices [116–118]. These so-called B20 (or FeSi-type) intermetallic compounds also crystallize in the $P2_13$ space group and exemplify how chiral spin topology gives rise to topological excitations such as skyrmions and chiral phonons [119]. Later, the famous oxide-based insulating analog, Cu_2OSeO_3 , revealed that the same trillium geometry, when realized in localized-spin systems, naturally extends triangular-lattice frustration into the 3D with the existence of skyrmions and other novel spin textures [120].

Another striking theoretical proposal of trillium lattices is its potential to host a chiral spin liquid (CSL): a state that lacks magnetic LRO but spontaneously breaks time-reversal and parity symmetries [121, 122]. The CSL arises from three-spin chiral interactions of the form $\mathbf{S}_i \cdot (\mathbf{S}_j \times \mathbf{S}_k)$ acting on triangular units, and is closely related to fractionalized excitations such as spinons or fractons [123]. Furthermore, trillium networks may also realize classical CSL states with algebraic or exponential correlations in the large-spin limit, analogous to Coulomb phases in pyrochlore spin ices [124]. Additionally, Monte Carlo simulations of the Heisenberg model on the trillium lattice AFM demonstrate a unique coplanar 120° state out of a manifold of degenerate wave vectors [122]. On the other hand, Ising models support a “trillium spin ice” with a two-in/one-out rule on triangular plaquettes, in contrast to the two-in/two-out ice rules in pyrochlore [125]. More recently, the line graph of the trillium lattice, also known as the trilline lattice, has been proposed to host a fragile spin liquid with exponentially decaying correlations and orphan-spin excitations [126].

Experimentally, the first realization of oxide-based perfect single-trillium AFM was reported in the $S = 5/2$ metal–organic framework $\text{Na}[\text{Mn}(\text{HCOO})_3]$, which shows 2-k ordering and a field-induced $1/3$ magnetization plateau typical of the *wud* phase [127]. A geometrical extension of the single trillium lattice, where within a unit cell there are two different sub-lattices of trillium

units, referred to as the double trillium lattice, is shown in Fig. 1.10(b). Usually, this bipartite version contains five different exchange couplings, namely J_1 to J_5 , which makes it complicated to visualize. The possible connectivities in a double trillium lattice are depicted in Fig. 1.10(c). The relative strength of exchange couplings and their intricate balance are essential in stabilizing either an ordered or QSL-like state in this lattice. Most of the double trillium compounds reported till date crystallize in the Langbeinite family [128], with a general formula $A_2B_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (double sulfate salts), where A^+ is a monovalent ion and B^{2+} represents magnetic ions forming two interpenetrating trillium sublattices. It is understood that the substitution of PO_4 in place of SO_4 retains the same non-centrosymmetric cubic $P2_13$ symmetry while enriching its chemical tunability [129]. These systems exhibit structural and magnetic complexity, cubic-to-lower-symmetry ferroelastic transitions, and weak ferromagnetism induced by DM interactions [130]. A well know example, $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (Ni^{2+} : $S = 1$) hosts field-induced QSL state and features spinon continuum [131, 132]. Meanwhile, a high spin candidate, $\text{KSrFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (Fe^{3+} : $S = 5/2$) exhibits gapless spin-liquid-like behavior with no magnetic LRO down to lowest temperatures [133]. Further, compounds such as $\text{K}_2\text{CrTi}(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KBaCr}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ demonstrate multiple phase transitions and exotic field-induced phases [134, 135]. Recent reports on a magnetic site diluted double trillium lattice, $\text{K}_2\text{FeSn}(\text{PO}_4)_3$, highlight the coexistence of weak magnetic order with persistent spin dynamics, suggesting its proximity towards a classical spin-liquid regime [136].

1.3.2 Frustration due to competing interactions

Frustration in magnetic systems can also arise from competing interactions rather than purely from lattice geometry, as mentioned in Section 1.3.1. A simple case is the 1D spin chain with NN coupling J_1 and NNN interaction J_2 [Fig. 1.11(a)]. When both J_1 and J_2 are AFM, the system cannot satisfy both interactions simultaneously, creating frustration. A similar effect occurs when J_1 is FM and J_2 is AFM, where the competition again prevents a conventional magnetic LRO. Some well know examples are, CuGeO_3 [137], Li_2CuO_2 [138], $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO})_2(\text{OH})_2$ [139], and

Figure 1.11: Schematic illustration of frustration due to competing interactions in (a) 1D spin chain and (b) square lattice.

$\text{K}_3\text{Cu}_3\text{AlO}_2(\text{SO}_4)_4$ [140].

In 2D, the square lattice serves as a good example of frustration due to competing interactions. As shown in Fig. 1.11(b), if only the NN interaction J_1 is AFM, the system stabilizes in an AFM LRO state. However, when AFM NNN interactions J_2 are included along the diagonals, the system becomes frustrated since J_1 and J_2 favor different spin configurations. In general, the square lattice is frustrated in two scenarios: (i) both J_1 and J_2 are AFM, or (ii) J_1 is FM while J_2 is AFM. Based on the frustration angle $\phi = \tan^{-1}[(J_2/J_1)]$, the possible ground states in square lattice is determined [141]. The resulting (J_1-J_2) model for the square lattice has been extensively studied and is known to host rich phases originating from the competition between the two interactions [142].

1.3.3 Exchange frustration

Exchange-driven frustration arises when the spin interactions are strongly anisotropic and depend on bond direction. The most celebrated example is the Kitaev model, first proposed by Alexei Kitaev in 2006 [143]. He demonstrated that a spin-1/2 honeycomb lattice with bond-dependent anisotropy can be solved exactly, yielding exotic QSL ground states. In this model, the spins fractionalize into emergent Majorana fermions, making it a minimal and influential framework for realizing both gapped and gapless QSL phases as well as in topological quantum

Figure 1.12: The schematic illustration of exchange frustration in a honeycomb lattice based on the Kitaev model.

computation [144–146].

The Kitaev Hamiltonian can be written as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{Kitaev}} = \sum_{\gamma\text{-bond}} K_{\gamma} S_i^{\gamma} S_j^{\gamma}, \quad (1.16)$$

where K_{γ} is the bond-dependent interaction strength and γ corresponds to the x , y , or z spin component of sites i and j . As shown in Fig. 1.12, the bond-directional nature of these couplings makes it impossible to minimize all interactions simultaneously, leading to a frustrated ground state, even when geometrical frustration is not viable.

As proposed by Jackeli and Khaliullin in their seminal paper, the geometrical orientation of metal octahedra plays a crucial role in favoring the Kitaev interactions [145]. In this case, materials featuring edge-sharing metal octahedra, as observed in honeycomb lattices and characterized by strong spin-orbit coupling (SOC), particularly $4d$ and $5d$ transition-metal compounds, have been identified as promising candidates for hosting Kitaev interactions. Notable examples include Na_2IrO_3 [147, 148], $\alpha\text{-Li}_2\text{IrO}_3$ [149, 150], and $\alpha\text{-RuCl}_3$ [151], with $\alpha\text{-RuCl}_3$ showing evidence for a field-induced QSL phase [152]. In addition, certain $3d$ transition-metal systems, such as $\text{Na}_2\text{Co}_2\text{TeO}_6$, have also been explored as potential hosts of Kitaev-like physics [153].

Beyond the conventional honeycomb lattice, recently it has been observed that triangular lattices with effective spin $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ moments also exhibit Kitaev physics. Apart from the edge-sharing metal octahedra, a parallel edge-sharing in a triangular lattice favors Kitaev interactions. Here, the microscopic description is entirely captured by the Heisenberg-Kitaev model given by [154].

$$H = - \sum_{\gamma} J \mathbf{S}_i \cdot \mathbf{S}_j + K S_i^{\gamma} S_j^{\gamma} + \Gamma (S_i^{\alpha} S_j^{\beta} + S_i^{\beta} S_j^{\alpha}), \quad (1.17)$$

with, J being the Heisenberg exchange term and Γ introduces the anisotropic spin interaction. Due to the inherent geometrical frustration of the triangular lattice and exchange frustration, this model could evidence the formation of non-trivial spin textures [155]. Some well-known examples of TLAFs showing Kitaev physics are strong SOC systems like iridates, $\text{Ba}_3\text{IrTi}_2\text{O}_9$ [156], $\text{Ba}_3\text{TlIr}_2\text{O}_9$ [157], and cobaltates $\text{Na}_2\text{BaCo}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [158]

1.4 Physics of Co^{2+} -based systems

Figure 1.13: The high-spin state of Co^{2+} [$3d^7 (t_{2g}^5 e_g^2)$] configuration in an octahedral crystal field.

The ground state magnetic properties of Co^{2+} ions arise from the combined effect of Hund's rules, the surrounding crystal electric field (CEF), spin-orbit coupling (SOC), and trigonal CEF effects. In general, SOC refers to the interaction between an electron's orbital angular momen-

Figure 1.14: The tentative energy diagram that depicts the splitting of 4F state of Co^{2+} under an octahedral crystal field and of the $^4T_{1g}$ state under SOC

tum \mathbf{L} and its spin angular momentum \mathbf{S} , expressed by the Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H}_{\text{SOC}} = \lambda \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{S}, \quad (1.18)$$

where λ is the SOC constant, which determines the strength of SOC. Typically, SOC arises from the fact that in the rest frame of an electron moving around the nucleus, the nuclear electric field appears as a magnetic field, which then couples to the electron spin. This relativistic interaction removes orbital degeneracies and leads to mixed spin-orbital states, which strongly influence the low-energy excitations.

On the other hand, the unpaired electrons on the magnetic ion interact with the surrounding ligands, which generates an electric field, referred to as CEF or ligand field. The resulting CEF potential acts only on the orbital part of the electronic wavefunction, which splits the orbital degeneracies of electronic states. These effects clearly depend on the geometry of the polyhedra (ligand environment), which, in the case of $3d$ -based systems, are the t_{2g} and e_g levels. In a special case, where the metal octahedra get distorted, a special case of crystal field effect called

trigonal CEF splitting emerges [159]. The Hamiltonian governing this effect is of the form

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{trig}} = \delta(3L_z^2 - 2), \quad (1.19)$$

where δ denotes the strength of the trigonal crystal field splitting.

For a free Co^{2+} ion with $3d^7$ electronic configuration, Hund's rules dictate a high-spin ground state with $S = 3/2$ and $L = 3$, as shown in Fig. 1.13, corresponding to the spectroscopic 4F term. Figure 1.14 presents the complete energy level diagram of a Co^{2+} ion under SOC and CEF. First, in the presence of an octahedral crystal field, the cubic component of the electrostatic potential arising from CEF splits the 4F term into three manifolds: ${}^4A_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{2g}$, and ${}^4T_{1g}$. Among these, the ${}^4T_{1g}$ triplet lies lowest in energy and governs the low-temperature physics of Co^{2+} systems.

The next stage of splitting comes from SOC acting on the ${}^4T_{1g}$ orbital triplet. The coupling between L and S reorganizes the states into multiplets characterized by an effective total angular momentum J_{eff} . In this scheme, shown in Fig. 1.14, the ${}^4T_{1g}$ manifold is divided into a $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ doublet, a $J_{\text{eff}} = 3/2$ quartet, and a $J_{\text{eff}} = 5/2$ sextet. The separation between these multiplets is set by the magnitude of λ , with the $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ doublet forming the lowest-lying level. This $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ is separated from $J_{\text{eff}} = 3/2$ by an energy gap of $\Delta_{\text{SL}} = \frac{3\lambda}{2}$. Thus, for $T \ll |\lambda|/k_{\text{B}}$, one expects the magnetism to be determined by the lowest Kramers doublet [13, 160]. As a consequence of this two-fold degeneracy, it ensures a time reversal symmetry even in the presence of SOC. After SOC, if the octahedra have distortions, especially along the z -direction, trigonal CEF becomes relevant, which again downshifts the energy of the $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ state. Later, this degeneracy is completely lifted by an applied field due to Zeeman interaction. Thus, the complicated Co^{2+} ($3d^7$) ion can be mapped onto an effective pseudospin-1/2 degree of freedom, making it a prototypical example in $3d$ systems.

The Co^{2+} -based TLAFs form a special class of compounds that manifest various exotic phases of matter, closely resembling the physics of $4f$ -based $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ systems such as Ce^{3+}

and Yb^{3+} [161–163]. Among them, $\text{Ba}_3\text{CoSb}_2\text{O}_9$ is the most celebrated compound, exhibiting successive magnetic transitions, well-defined $1/3$ and $3/5$ magnetization plateaus, and a recently proposed QSL ground state [13, 160, 164, 165]. Several other Co^{2+} based $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs are also reported to show diverse physics with complex magnetic orderings [101, 114, 166–169]. Because of the localized nature of the $3d$ electrons, cobaltates featuring a honeycomb lattice also offer a promising ground to look for Kitaev QSL [159, 170, 171]. Indeed, a field-induced Kitaev spin-liquid-like behavior has been observed in $\text{Na}_2\text{Co}_2\text{TeO}_6$ [153] and $\text{BaCo}_2(\text{AsO}_4)_2$ [172]. However, their complete phase diagram remains obscure.

1.5 Overview of the thesis

Chapter 1 highlights how frustration in magnetic systems can give rise to unconventional low-temperature properties and exotic ground states, many of which defy classical expectations. In this context, the present thesis is organized in six chapters which addresses a comprehensive study of four distinct frustrated magnets: the classical TLAF, $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, the SOC entangled $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb,Ta})_2\text{O}_9$, and the double trillium lattice AFM, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

Chapter 2 describes the experimental methods and instrumentation employed in this work. The techniques include powder x-ray and neutron diffraction, vibrating sample magnetometer, dc and ac magnetometry, heat capacity (C_p), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), and muon spin resonance (μSR).

Chapter 3 presents the structural and magnetic properties of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Thermodynamic measurements reveal an AFM LRO near $T_N \simeq 10.4$ K, and neutron diffraction measurements reveal a collinear AFM ground state below T_N . Despite the large spin $S = 5/2$ of Fe^{3+} , the system exhibits moderate frustration ($f \simeq 3.6$) and a substantial reduction in the ordered moment ($\sim 1.5\mu_B$), consistent with the influence of frustration and anisotropy. The field-dependent studies establish a spin-flop transition at a field of $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T and a saturation field of $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T. Furthermore, an H - T phase diagram is constructed, outlining the different phases typical of a TLAF with anisotropic exchange interactions (easy-plane type).

Chapter 4 focuses on the TLAFs $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_9$, where strong SOC in Co^{2+} gives rise to an effective $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ state. Both the compounds undergo two successive magnetic transitions driven by weak easy-axis anisotropy. $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ displays a clear $1/3$ magnetization plateau associated with the stabilization of uud configuration, whereas $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ enters an unusual field-induced regime characterized by gapless excitations with $C_p \propto T^2$, a proximate field-induced QSL-like state. An H - T phase diagram is proposed for both compounds, highlighting their key differences and the unusual field-induced regimes.

Chapter 5 talks about the 3D double trillium lattice compound $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Despite strong AFM interaction ($\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -70$ K), this spin-5/2 system evades magnetic LRO down to 30 mK. Local probe techniques, including ^{31}P NMR and μSR , reveal persistent inhomogeneous spin dynamics below a characteristic temperature $T^* \simeq 3.5$ K, without any evidence of static order or spin-glass/ freezing. The resulting unconventional inhomogeneous dynamic state with sporadic spin fluctuation underscores the role of geometric frustration in 3D, positioning $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ as a rare high-spin system that resists classical ordering.

Chapter 6 summarizes the principal results of this thesis and provides an outlook for future investigations.

Chapter 2

Experimental Techniques

Data! Data! Data!', he cried impatiently. 'I can't make bricks without clay'

SIR ARTHUR CONAN DOYLE

In this chapter, we present the details of experimental methods employed in this dissertation. These include bulk measurement techniques such as powder x-ray diffraction, AC and DC magnetometry, and heat capacity measurements. In addition, the fundamental principles and technical aspects of local probe techniques, including neutron powder diffraction, nuclear magnetic resonance, and muon spin resonance, are also discussed. All the experiments were performed on the polycrystalline samples.

2.1 Powder X-ray Diffraction

A polycrystalline sample consists of numerous crystallites, each characterized by a periodic atomic arrangement with lattice planes indexed by Miller indices (hkl). X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a key technique for probing such atomic structures because the x-ray wavelength ($\sim 1 \text{ \AA}$) is comparable to interatomic spacings, as illustrated in Fig. 2.1. In particular, powder XRD is widely employed to determine lattice parameters, structural distortions, disorder, grain boundaries, and phase transitions.

The fundamental principle of XRD, formulated by W. H. and W. L. Bragg in 1913, is the

Figure 2.1: Schematic illustration of Bragg diffraction from lattice planes.

Bragg's law,

$$2d_{hkl} \sin \theta = n\lambda, \quad (2.1)$$

where d_{hkl} is the interplanar spacing, λ is the x-ray wavelength, and n is the reflection order ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$). In a typical θ - 2θ geometry, a 2θ scan records reflections at characteristic angles, each corresponding to a specific set of lattice planes.

The diffracted intensity for a given reflection is proportional to the square of the structure factor, $I_{hkl} \propto |F_{hkl}|^2$, with

$$F_{hkl} = \sum_{j=1}^p N_j f_j(\theta) \exp[2\pi i (hx_j + ky_j + lz_j)], \quad (2.2)$$

where p is the number of atoms in the unit cell, N_j is the site occupancy of the j^{th} atom, $f_j(\theta)$ is its atomic form factor, and (x_j, y_j, z_j) are its fractional coordinates. Furthermore, thermal vibrations at finite temperatures attenuate the diffracted intensity. Assuming isotropic displacements, this is accounted for by the Debye–Waller factor, which multiplies each atomic

term by

$$\exp\left(-\frac{B_{\text{iso}} \sin^2 \theta}{\lambda^2}\right), \quad (2.3)$$

so that, Eq. (2.2) becomes

$$F_{hkl} = \sum_{j=1}^p N_j f_j(\theta) \exp[2\pi i(hx_j + ky_j + lz_j)] \exp\left(-\frac{B_{\text{iso}} \sin^2 \theta}{\lambda^2}\right), \quad (2.4)$$

where

$$B_{\text{iso}} = 8\pi^2 \langle U_{\text{iso}}^2 \rangle \quad (2.5)$$

and $\langle U_{\text{iso}}^2 \rangle$ is the mean-square atomic displacement from equilibrium.

In this thesis, the powder XRD measurements were performed using a PANalytical X'Pert PRO diffractometer with monochromatic Cu K_{α_1} radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Additionally, temperature-dependent XRD was carried out over a temperature range $15 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$. For $T < 300 \text{ K}$, an Oxford PheniX cryostat was used as the low-temperature attachment to the diffractometer.

2.2 Neutron Powder Diffraction

Neutron powder diffraction (NPD) has emerged as a pivotal technique for investigating both nuclear and magnetic structures, serving as a powerful complement to XRD. The neutron, discovered by J. Chadwick [173], is a chargeless spin-1/2 particle with a non-zero magnetic moment that interacts only weakly with the electron cloud of an atom. Moreover, the wavelength of thermal neutrons is comparable to typical interatomic spacings in crystalline solids. Consequently, neutrons can penetrate several millimeters into a material, much deeper than x-rays. Their ability to couple to magnetic moments through magnetic dipole interactions renders them exceptionally suited for probing magnetic structures.

Unlike x-rays, neutron scattering cross-sections do not scale with the atomic number and exhibit irregular atomic form factors. This distinctive property enables neutrons to distinguish light elements such as hydrogen and oxygen from heavier transition-metal or rare-earth ions and

even between isotopes. Thus, neutron scattering remains an indispensable tool for determining crystal and magnetic structures, as well as for studying phonons, magnons, and crystal-field excitations. However, due to the relatively low flux of neutron sources and the small probability of diffraction events, NPD experiments generally require comparatively large sample masses (typically several grams).

Figure 2.2: Schematic representation of a neutron scattering process.

A standard neutron scattering experiment can be treated as a two-body collision problem. An incident neutron with energy E_i and wave vector \vec{k}_i interacts with the sample and emerges with a final energy E_f and wave vector \vec{k}_f . The scattering profile is obtained as a function of both energy and momentum transfer and can be analyzed accordingly. The exchanged energy and momentum are given by $\hbar\omega = E_f - E_i$ and $\vec{Q} = \vec{k}_f - \vec{k}_i$, respectively. Here, \vec{Q} represents the scattering vector, and $\hbar\omega$ is the corresponding energy difference between the incident and scattered neutrons. Depending on their interaction, two fundamental processes occur, an elastic scattering, where $\omega = 0$ and $|\vec{Q}|$ corresponds to reciprocal lattice points [Fig. 2.2(a)], or an inelastic scattering, where $\omega \neq 0$ and $|\vec{Q}|$ varies continuously [Fig. 2.2(b)].

To understand the fundamental concept of NPD, let us examine the elastic (coherent) scattering mechanism more closely. Applying the law of cosines to the scattering triangle in Fig. 2.2(a), we obtain

$$|Q|^2 = k_i^2 + k_f^2 - 2k_i k_f \cos \theta = \frac{2m_n}{\hbar^2} (E_i + E_f - 2\sqrt{E_i E_f} \cos \theta), \quad (2.6)$$

where m_n is the neutron mass. For elastic scattering, $E_i = E_f$ (or $k_i = k_f = k$), which simplifies

to

$$|Q|^2 = 4k^2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad (2.7)$$

$$\boxed{|Q| = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)}, \quad (2.8)$$

where λ is the neutron wavelength.

A salient feature of NPD experiments is their ability to determine absolute scattering intensities. Furthermore, the intensity of the Bragg peaks is governed by three principal factors: (i) the arrangement of magnetic moments within the unit cell, (ii) the magnetic form factor, and (iii) the orientation of scattering vector relative to the ordered moments. Hence, the overall process is quantified by the differential scattering cross section, $d\sigma/d\Omega$.

Considering a spherical wavefront, the scattering intensity as a function of the momentum transfer \vec{Q} can be expressed as

$$I(\vec{Q}) = \left| \sum_j b_j \exp(i\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{r}_j) \right|^2, \quad (2.9)$$

where b_j is the nuclear scattering length and \vec{r}_j is the position vector of the j^{th} nucleus. For elastic coherent scattering, $I(\vec{Q})$ equals $d\sigma/d\Omega$, yielding

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{coh}} = \left| \sum_j b_j \exp(i\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{r}_j) \right|^2. \quad (2.10)$$

For a crystal containing N primitive unit cells, each of volume V_0 , let $r_{ld} = \vec{l} + \vec{d}$ denote the position of the d^{th} atom in the unit cell located at the lattice vector \vec{l} . Substituting this into Eq. (2.10) gives

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{coh}} = \left| \sum_{ld} b_d \exp[i\vec{Q} \cdot (\vec{l} + \vec{d})] \right|^2, \quad (2.11)$$

which can be separated as

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{coh}} = \left| \sum_l \exp(i\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{l}) \right|^2 \left| \sum_d b_d \exp(i\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{d}) \right|^2. \quad (2.12)$$

The first term in Eq. (2.12) represents the sum over all lattice vectors, giving sharp intensity maxima only at $\vec{Q} = \vec{G}$,

$$\left| \sum_l \exp(i\vec{Q} \cdot \vec{l}) \right|^2 = N \frac{(2\pi)^3}{V_0} \sum_G \delta(\vec{Q} - \vec{G}), \quad (2.13)$$

where \vec{G} is a reciprocal lattice vector. The second term corresponds to the coherent sum over atoms within a unit cell and defines the nuclear structure factor $F_N(\vec{G})$. Therefore, the differential cross section for coherent elastic scattering becomes

$$\boxed{\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{coh}} = N \frac{(2\pi)^3}{V_0} \sum_G \delta(\vec{Q} - \vec{G}) |F_N(\vec{G})|^2}. \quad (2.14)$$

By the aforementioned analogy, the differential cross section for coherent magnetic scattering in a magnetic lattice containing N_m unit cells of volume V_m is given by

$$\boxed{\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{mag}} = N_m \frac{(2\pi)^3}{V_m} \sum_{G_m} \delta(\vec{Q} - \vec{G}_m) |F_M(\vec{G}_m)|^2}, \quad (2.15)$$

where \vec{G}_m is the reciprocal lattice vector of the magnetic lattice and $F_M(\vec{G}_m)$ is the magnetic structure factor.

In a typical NPD experiment, diffraction patterns are collected both above and below the magnetic ordering temperature T_N . The high-temperature (paramagnetic) pattern reveals only the nuclear Bragg reflections, from which the crystal structure can be refined. In contrast, below T_N , additional Bragg peaks or enhanced intensities at nuclear positions appear, corresponding to AFM or FM ordering, respectively. By subtracting the diffraction pattern recorded above T_N

from that obtained below T_N , one can isolate the magnetic contribution. Subsequently, Rietveld refinement of the subtracted pattern provides the magnetic structure of the compound.

In this dissertation, the NPD measurements were performed using the powder diffractometer PD-II ($\lambda = 1.2443 \text{ \AA}$) at the Dhruva reactor, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Mumbai, India.

2.2.1 Rietveld Refinement

Rietveld refinement is a powerful method for extracting both structural and magnetic information from powder XRD and NPD data. It requires prior knowledge of the crystal structure, including the space group, lattice parameters, atomic coordinates, and thermal displacement factors. The method is based on a least-squares minimization between the observed and calculated diffraction intensities. The residual quantity minimized during the refinement is

$$R_y = \sum_i w_i (y_i - y_{ci})^2, \quad (2.16)$$

where y_i and y_{ci} represent the observed and calculated intensities at the i^{th} data point, respectively, and w_i is a weighting factor ensuring that all reflections contribute statistically and uniformly to the refinement. The calculated intensity, y_{ci} , is expressed as

$$y_{ci} = s \sum_{hkl} L_{hkl} |F_{hkl}|^2 \Phi(2\theta_{i,hkl}) P_{hkl} A + y_{bi}, \quad (2.17)$$

where L_{hkl} is the Lorentz–polarization factor, F_{hkl} the structure factor, Φ the peak-shape function, P_{hkl} the preferred-orientation correction, A the absorption term, y_{bi} the background intensity, and s an overall scale factor. For an angle-dispersive diffraction data (e.g. powder-XRD data), a commonly employed peak profile is the pseudo-Voigt function,

$$\Phi_{pV}(\theta) = \eta L(\theta, \Gamma_L) + (1 - \eta) G(\theta, \Gamma_G), \quad (2.18)$$

which is a weighted (η) sum of Lorentzian (L) and Gaussian (G) components, characterized by the full widths, Γ_G and Γ_L expressed as

$$\Gamma_G^2 = U \tan^2 \theta + V \tan \theta + W, \quad \Gamma_L^2 = X \tan \theta + \frac{Y}{\cos \theta}. \quad (2.19)$$

Here, U , V , W , X , and Y are refinable profile parameters.

The quality of a Rietveld refinement is evaluated through the weighted pattern factor (R_{wp}), the expected R -factor (R_{exp}), and their ratio (χ^2) defined as

$$R_{wp} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i w_i (y_i - y_{ci})^2}{\sum_i w_i y_i^2}}, \quad R_{exp} = \sqrt{\frac{N - P}{\sum_i w_i y_i^2}}, \quad (2.20)$$

$$\text{and } \chi^2 = \left(\frac{R_{wp}}{R_{exp}} \right)^2. \quad (2.21)$$

Here, N and P are the total number of data points and refined parameters, respectively. Ideally, $\chi^2 \simeq 1$, but in practice, values of $\chi^2 \lesssim 7$ typically indicate an acceptable refinement.

It is important to note, however, that these statistical indicators must be interpreted cautiously. A low R_{wp} or χ^2 value does not always guarantee a physically meaningful model, as refinements can converge to local minima with non-physical parameter sets. Thus, a reliable initial structural model, one that closely approximates the true crystal structure is essential to achieve a meaningful result.

All Rietveld refinements performed in this dissertation were carried out using the FULLPROF software package [174].

2.3 Magnetometry

2.3.1 Vibrating Sample Magnetometer

A vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) is one of the most widely used instruments for studying the magnetic properties of materials. It enables the measurement of magnetization as a function

of both applied magnetic field and temperature. Among the key parameters obtained from VSM measurements is the magnetic susceptibility (χ), defined as

$$\chi(T) = - \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial H^2} \right)_{T,V} = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial H} \right)_{T,V}, \quad (2.22)$$

where F is the Helmholtz free energy, M is the measured magnetization, and H is the applied magnetic field.

The operating principle of a VSM relies on Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction. In this technique, the sample is vibrated sinusoidally within a uniform magnetic field, producing an alternating magnetic flux through a stationary pick-up coil. The resulting change in flux induces a voltage (V_{coil}) in the coil, given by

$$V_{\text{coil}} = - \oint \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{S} = - \frac{d\phi}{dt} = - \frac{d\phi}{dz} \frac{dz}{dt}, \quad (2.23)$$

where ϕ is the magnetic flux, z is the vertical position of the sample, and t is the time. Assuming harmonic oscillation of the sample along the z -direction, and applying the Biot–Savart law, the induced voltage can be expressed as [175]

$$V_{\text{coil}} \propto m\omega \sin(\omega t), \quad (2.24)$$

where m is the magnetic moment of the sample and ω is the angular frequency of vibration. Hence, the induced voltage is directly proportional to the magnetic moment of the sample.

A typical VSM setup consists of a cryostat equipped with a variable temperature insert (VTI) and a superconducting magnet for precise temperature and field control. The sample, mounted on a non-magnetic rod, is driven by a linear motor to oscillate at a controlled amplitude and frequency. The resulting signal is detected by the pick-up coil and processed by the measurement electronics. Furthermore, data acquisition, temperature regulation, and field control are commonly managed through dedicated software packages such as MULTIVU, which

provide automation and synchronization of the entire measurement process.

2.3.2 SQUID (DC) Magnetometer

A superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) is an extremely sensitive volume magnetometer (flux-to-voltage transducer) capable of detecting magnetic flux variations as small as a fraction of a magnetic flux quantum, $\phi_0 = h/2e = 2.073 \times 10^{-15}$ Wb, and magnetic moments as low as 10^{-9} emu. It exploits the Josephson effect to detect minute changes in magnetic flux produced by a magnetic material. A SQUID typically consists of a superconducting loop interrupted by one or more Josephson junctions.

Figure 2.3: Schematic diagram of a DC SQUID loop.

In a DC SQUID [Fig. 2.3], a bias current (I_b) is applied through the superconducting loop, while shunt resistors are incorporated to prevent hysteresis in the I – V characteristic. When magnetic flux from a sample couples into the SQUID loop, it induces screening current that modulates the critical current (I_c) of the Josephson junctions. When I_b slightly exceeds I_c , a voltage appears across the junction. As the magnetic flux ($\Delta\phi$) varies, this voltage changes periodically with a period corresponding to one magnetic flux quantum. The current–phase

relation for a Josephson junction is given by

$$J_s = J_c \sin(\tau), \quad (2.25)$$

where J_s is the supercurrent density and J_c is the critical current, which depends on both the superconducting material and the geometry of the junction. The gauge-invariant phase difference τ between the superconducting wave functions on either side of the junction is expressed as

$$\tau = \theta_1 - \theta_2 - \frac{2\pi}{\phi_0} \int \vec{A}(r, t) \cdot d\vec{l}, \quad (2.26)$$

where $\vec{A}(r, t)$ is the magnetic vector potential, and $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ is the superconducting phase difference across the junction.

In the absence of an applied magnetic field or voltage, a constant supercurrent flows across the junction, referred to as DC Josephson effect. Conversely, if a constant voltage is applied, τ varies linearly with time, resulting in an alternating supercurrent known as the AC Josephson effect. Consequently, the SQUID determines the magnetic flux through the loop by monitoring these voltage oscillations with extraordinary precision.

In this dissertation, all magnetization measurements were performed using a Magnetic Property Measurement System (MPMS-3) SQUID VSM from Quantum Design (QD). The measurements covered a broad temperature range of $0.4 \leq T \leq 380$ K and a magnetic field range of $0 \leq H \leq 7$ T. For measurements below 2 K, a ^3He insert was employed in conjunction with the SQUID magnetometer.

Figure 2.4 illustrates a typical SQUID magnetometer configuration within the MPMS system, employing a second-order gradiometer in Helmholtz geometry [176]. This design consists of a central clockwise loop connected in series with two counterclockwise loops placed 3 cm apart, followed by another clockwise loop. Such an arrangement effectively cancels stray magnetic flux and compensates for linear field gradients.

During operation, a constant magnetic field is applied to both the detection coils and the

Figure 2.4: Configuration of a SQUID magnetometer in a MPMS setup.

sample, which is mounted in a non-magnetic (brass or straw) sample holder and moved along the symmetry (z) axis through the gradiometer coils. The induced voltage in the detection coils is processed such that the SQUID remains flux-locked at its optimal operating point, ensuring high signal linearity and stability. The right panel of Fig. 2.4 schematically depicts the ideal voltage response as a function of the sample position.

The SQUID magnetometer measures magnetization (M) in electromagnetic units (emu). It is often convenient to express the data in CGS units, where $1 \text{ emu} = 1 \text{ G} \cdot \text{cm}^3$ and $1 \text{ Oe} = 1 \text{ G}$. The molar magnetic susceptibility is then given by

$$\chi(T) = \frac{M}{H} \left(\frac{\text{molecular mass}}{\text{sample weight}} \right) \text{ in cm}^3/\text{mol}, \quad (2.27)$$

where H is the applied magnetic field.

2.3.3 AC Magnetometry

In section 2.3.2, we discussed the measurement of the static DC magnetic moment using a SQUID magnetometer. In contrast, AC magnetometry probes the time-dependent magnetic response of a sample under an oscillating magnetic field. The applied field is sinusoidal with an amplitude H_{AC} , and for small excitation fields, the induced AC magnetic moment can be written as

$$M_{AC} = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial H} \right) H_{AC} \sin(2\pi\nu t), \quad (2.28)$$

where ν denotes the frequency of the applied AC field. Equation (2.28) clearly indicates that AC measurements directly probe the differential magnetic susceptibility χ , corresponding to the slope of the magnetization isotherm $M(H)$. This renders AC magnetometry highly sensitive to subtle magnetic transitions or shifts, even when the absolute value of magnetization is large. When a DC magnetic field is superposed on the AC excitation, the total field experienced by the sample becomes

$$H(t) = H_{DC} + H_{AC} \sin(2\pi\nu t), \quad (2.29)$$

allowing one to probe different regions of the $M-H$ curve under varying bias conditions.

In this dissertation, AC susceptibility measurements were performed using the AC Measurement System (ACMS II) option integrated with the Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) from Quantum Design. The ACMS drive coil generates oscillating fields up to ± 10 Oe over a frequency range of 10 Hz to 10 kHz. This wide dynamic range enables the exploration of various magnetic relaxation processes and field-induced transitions occurring over different timescales. Consequently, AC magnetometry serves as a powerful probe for identifying magnetic and dynamic ground states.

As shown in Fig. 2.5, ACMS II option employs a first-order axial gradiometer composed of two counter-wound coils connected in series, which function as a flux-to-voltage converter. To enhance sensitivity and compensate for background drift and noise, a three-point measurement

Figure 2.5: Schematic representation of the coil arrangement in an AC magnetometer.

protocol is typically used, where two measurements are taken at the bottom coil positions and one at the top. Furthermore, at very low frequencies ($\nu \rightarrow 0$), the AC magnetization response approaches that obtained in DC magnetometry. Conversely, at higher frequencies, the deviations appear due to dynamic magnetic relaxation processes within the sample. Hence, AC susceptibility is often termed as measure of dynamic susceptibility. Therefore, it is often expressed as a complex quantity,

$$\chi_{AC} = \chi' - i\chi'', \quad (2.30)$$

where the in-phase (real) component, χ' , corresponds to the reversible magnetization processes, while the out-of-phase (imaginary) component, χ'' , is associated with irreversible magnetic

relaxation and energy dissipation. Using the polar form, these quantities can be related as

$$\chi' = \chi \cos \phi, \quad \chi'' = \chi \sin \phi, \quad \chi = \sqrt{\chi'^2 + \chi''^2}, \quad \phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\chi''}{\chi'} \right), \quad (2.31)$$

where ϕ represents the phase lag between the applied field and the magnetization response.

The frequency dependence of $\chi'(T)$ and $\chi''(T)$ provides valuable information about the magnetic state of a system. For instance, in spin-glass systems, the peak positions in both χ' and χ'' shift to higher temperatures with increasing frequency, reflecting a distribution of relaxation times. In contrast, magnetically ordered systems exhibit negligible frequency dependence. Therefore, the variation of the freezing temperature with frequency serves as a diagnostic tool for distinguishing between disordered (glass) and ordered magnetic states.

Sample mounting and preparation for ACMS measurements follow procedures similar to those employed in DC magnetization measurements, typically using a non-magnetic straw and a gelatin capsule.

2.4 Heat Capacity

The molar heat capacity, expressed in $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, represents the amount of heat (dQ) required per mole of material to change its temperature by dT under specified conditions. Thermodynamically, it can be related to the internal energy (U), entropy (S), and Helmholtz free energy (F) as

$$C_v(T) = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial T} \right)_V = T \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \right)_V = -T \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial T^2} \right)_V. \quad (2.32)$$

In practice, heat capacity is generally measured at constant pressure rather than constant volume. Thus, the heat capacity at constant pressure, $C_p(T)$, can be expressed in terms of the enthalpy (H) and Gibbs free energy (G) as

$$C_p(T) = \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial T} \right)_P = \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial T} \right)_P = -T \left(\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial T^2} \right)_P. \quad (2.33)$$

For solids, $C_p(T)$ and $C_v(T)$ are approximately related by

$$C_p(T) \simeq C_v(T) + \frac{TV\gamma^2(T)}{\beta(T)}, \quad (2.34)$$

where $\gamma(T)$ is the volumetric thermal expansion coefficient and $\beta(T)$ is the isothermal compressibility. Since $\gamma(T)$ is small at low temperatures, one can safely assume $C_p(T) \approx C_v(T)$.

Heat capacity serves as a highly sensitive probe of the lattice, electronic, and magnetic degrees of freedom in materials. It provides valuable insights into phase transitions, including magnetic, structural, and superconducting ones. Therefore, the total heat capacity (C_{total}) can be written as the sum of individual contributions

$$C_{\text{total}} = C_{\text{lat}} + C_{\text{elec}} + C_{\text{nuc}} + C_{\text{mag}}, \quad (2.35)$$

where C_{lat} , C_{elec} , C_{nuc} , and C_{mag} denote the lattice, electronic Schottky, nuclear, and magnetic components, respectively.

2.4.1 Sample Preparation and Measurement

The samples investigated in this dissertation are insulators with intrinsically low thermal conductivity. To ensure reliable heat capacity measurements, the pressed pellets were carefully cut into thin, uniform pieces with smooth surfaces. For each measurement, sintered pellets with a mass of approximately 1–2 mg were used.

Heat capacity measurement was carried out using the heat capacity option of the PPMS. As shown in Fig. 2.6, the sample was mounted on a flat platform of the calorimetric puck, which incorporates a resistive heater and a Cernox thermometer at its base. The platform is thermally linked to the bath via eight fine wires that also serve as mechanical supports. To ensure optimal thermal contact, the sample was attached to the platform using a thin layer of APIEZON N grease. The entire puck assembly is enclosed within a radiation shield to minimize parasitic heat exchange with the surroundings. Furthermore, a high vacuum is maintained inside the sample

Figure 2.6: Schematic diagram of the heat capacity puck used in the PPMS, showing its thermal and electrical connections (adapted from the Quantum Design user manual).

chamber in order to provide an effective thermal insulation during the experiment. Additionally, a charcoal baffle located near the base of the puck maintains thermal stability by suppressing helium adsorption at temperatures below 10 K.

The measurement procedure involves two main steps. First, the heat capacity of the platform with APIEZON N grease (the *addenda*) is measured as a function of temperature. Subsequently, the sample is mounted on the same platform, and the combined (sample + addenda) heat capacity is recorded. The true sample heat capacity is obtained by subtracting the addenda contribution from the total measured value. The experiment follows the thermal relaxation method, in which a known amount of heat is applied to the sample platform for a short period at constant power, followed by an equal cooling interval. The resulting temperature–time response of the platform is recorded and fitted using an appropriate relaxation model to determine the heat capacity. The choice of model depends on the thermal coupling between the sample and the platform, is discussed in the next section.

2.4.2 Thermal Relaxation Technique

Figure 2.7 illustrates the schematic of a conventional thermal relaxation calorimeter, originally developed by Bachmann *et al.* using the relaxation method [177, 178]. The basic principle of this technique is to determine the heat capacity of a sample by analyzing the combined thermal

response of the sample and calorimeter to a controlled heating and cooling cycle.

The calorimeter consists of a sample with an unknown heat capacity (C_{sample}) attached to a sample platform of known heat capacity (C_{plat}) using a thin layer of thermally conductive grease (APIEZON N). The grease ensures efficient thermal coupling between the sample and platform through its high thermal conductance (K_g). The platform, in turn, is thermally linked to a temperature-controlled bath (sink) at T_{bath} via a weak thermal link with conductance K_w . During the measurement, a heating power P_h is applied to the platform heater, causing both the platform and sample to warm up to a temperature $T_{\text{bath}} + \Delta T$, where the steady-state temperature rise is approximately $\Delta T = P_h/K_w$. When the heater is switched off, the system relaxes back towards T_{bath} with an exponential decay in temperature. This transient response forms the basis for determining the heat capacity.

To establish the heat-balance equations governing this system, the heat flow through each component, i.e., the sample, the platform, and the thermal link to the bath must be considered. From Fig. 2.7, the heat flow at the platform is governed by the applied power and the heat capacities and conductances of the system. The corresponding heat-balance equation is given by

$$P_h = C_{\text{plat}} \frac{dT_{\text{plat}}}{dt} + K_g(T_{\text{plat}} - T_{\text{sample}}) + K_w(T_{\text{plat}} - T_{\text{bath}}), \quad (2.36)$$

which states that the input power P_h is distributed among three processes: (i) the rate of change of the platform temperature, (ii) heat transfer to the sample through the grease, and (iii) heat loss to the thermal bath.

Figure 2.7: Schematic of a conventional thermal relaxation calorimeter.

Similarly, the heat balance for the sample is expressed as

$$0 = C_{\text{sample}} \frac{dT_{\text{sample}}}{dt} + K_g(T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{plat}}), \quad (2.37)$$

indicating that no external power is applied directly to the sample. The temperature variation of the sample (T_{sample}) arises solely from the heat conducted from the platform via the thermal grease. In a typical heat capacity measurement, this heat transfer is understood via two mechanisms, single-tau and two-tau models, which are described below.

Single-tau Model: In the simplest case, we assume that the thermal contact between the sample and the platform is sufficiently strong such that they remain in perfect thermal equilibrium throughout the measurement. This condition implies $K_g \gg K_w$ and consequently $T_{\text{sample}} = T_{\text{plat}}$. Under this approximation, Eq. (2.36) reduces to

$$P_h = C_{\text{total}} \frac{dT_{\text{sample}}}{dt} + K_w(T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{bath}}), \quad (2.38)$$

where $C_{\text{total}} = C_{\text{sample}} + C_{\text{plat}}$ represents the total heat capacity of the system. Since T_{bath} is maintained under thermal equilibrium, $\frac{dT_{\text{bath}}}{dt} \rightarrow 0$. Hence, we can express the temperature difference as $\Delta T = T_{\text{sample}} - T_{\text{bath}}$, allowing Eq. (2.38) to be rewritten as

$$P_h = K_w \Delta T + C_{\text{total}} \frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt}. \quad (2.39)$$

Equation (2.39) is a first-order linear differential equation in ΔT . Rewriting it in the standard form gives

$$\frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} + \frac{K_w}{C_{\text{total}}} \Delta T = \frac{P_h}{C_{\text{total}}}. \quad (2.40)$$

Defining the thermal relaxation time constant as

$$\tau = \frac{C_{\text{total}}}{K_w}, \quad (2.41)$$

the equation simplifies to

$$\frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\tau} \Delta T = \frac{P_h}{C_{\text{total}}}. \quad (2.42)$$

To solve Eq. (2.42), we apply the integrating factor method. The integrating factor is

$$\mu(t) = e^{\int \frac{1}{\tau} dt} = e^{t/\tau}. \quad (2.43)$$

Multiplying both sides of Eq. (2.42) by $\mu(t)$ yields

$$e^{t/\tau} \frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\tau} e^{t/\tau} \Delta T = \frac{P_h}{C_{\text{total}}} e^{t/\tau} = \frac{d}{dt} (e^{t/\tau} \Delta T). \quad (2.44)$$

Integrating both sides with respect to time gives

$$e^{t/\tau} \Delta T = \int \frac{P_h}{C_{\text{total}}} e^{t/\tau} dt = \frac{P_h \tau}{C_{\text{total}}} e^{t/\tau} + C, \quad (2.45)$$

where C is the integration constant. Dividing by $e^{t/\tau}$, we obtain

$$\Delta T = \frac{P_h \tau}{C_{\text{total}}} + C e^{-t/\tau}. \quad (2.46)$$

Applying the initial condition $\Delta T(0) = 0$ gives

$$C = -\frac{P_h \tau}{C_{\text{total}}}. \quad (2.47)$$

Therefore, the temperature rise as a function of time during the heating (heater ON) phase is

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{P_h \tau}{C_{\text{total}}} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}). \quad (2.48)$$

Substituting $\tau = \frac{C_{\text{total}}}{K_w}$ back into Eq. (2.48), we obtain

$$\Delta T(t) = \frac{P_h}{K_w} (1 - e^{-t/\tau}). \quad (2.49)$$

For the cooling (heater OFF) condition, i.e., $P_h = 0$, Eq. (2.42) reduces to

$$\frac{d(\Delta T)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\tau} \Delta T = 0. \quad (2.50)$$

Using the initial condition $\Delta T(0) = \Delta T_0$, we integrate to obtain

$$\int_{\Delta T_0}^{\Delta T} \frac{d(\Delta T)}{\Delta T} = - \int_0^t \frac{dt}{\tau}, \quad (2.51)$$

which yields

$$\ln \left(\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta T_0} \right) = -\frac{t}{\tau}. \quad (2.52)$$

Hence, the temperature decay during relaxation (heater OFF) follows an exponential form:

$$\Delta T(t) = \Delta T_0 e^{-t/\tau}, \quad (2.53)$$

where ΔT_0 is the initial temperature difference at $t = 0$, and $\tau = C_{\text{total}}/K_w$. At steady state, Eq. (2.39) yields a simple relationship between the applied power and the temperature rise:

$$K_w = \frac{P_h}{\Delta T}. \quad (2.54)$$

This expression is often used to experimentally determine the thermal conductance (K_w) of the weak link connecting the platform to the thermal bath.

Two-tau Model: When the thermal coupling between the sample and the platform is not significantly stronger than that between the platform and the thermal bath, or when the heat capacity of the connecting wires becomes non-negligible, the temperature of the platform (T_{plat})

can no longer be described by a single exponential decay. Instead, it must be represented as a sum of two exponential components characterized by different time constants, τ_1 and τ_2 . This approach is referred to as the *two-tau model*. In this case, both the heat flow between the sample and platform and that between the platform and thermal bath must be taken into account, following the coupled differential equations given by Eq. (2.36) and Eq. (2.37). To obtain expressions for τ_1 and τ_2 , Eq. (2.36) and Eq. (2.37) can be rewritten as

$$C_{\text{plat}} \frac{dT_{\text{plat}}}{dt} + (K_w + K_g)T_{\text{plat}}(t) - K_g T_{\text{sample}}(t) = P_h + K_w T_{\text{bath}}, \quad (2.55)$$

$$C_{\text{sample}} \frac{dT_{\text{sample}}}{dt} - K_g T_{\text{plat}}(t) + K_g T_{\text{sample}}(t) = 0. \quad (2.56)$$

We now define the state vector $\mathbf{T}(t)$ and its time derivative as

$$\mathbf{T}(t) = \begin{pmatrix} T_{\text{plat}}(t) \\ T_{\text{sample}}(t) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \frac{d\mathbf{T}(t)}{dt} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{dT_{\text{plat}}}{dt} \\ \frac{dT_{\text{sample}}}{dt} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.57)$$

The system can then be written in matrix form using the coefficient matrix \mathbf{A} and excitation vector \mathbf{b} :

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{(K_w + K_g)}{C_{\text{plat}}} & \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} \\ \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}} & -\frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{P_h + K_w T_{\text{bath}}}{C_{\text{plat}}} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.58)$$

Hence, the coupled system can be expressed compactly as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{T}(t)}{dt} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{T}(t) + \mathbf{b}. \quad (2.59)$$

To determine the time constants, we find the eigenvalues λ of the matrix \mathbf{A} by solving the characteristic equation

$$\det(\mathbf{A} - \lambda\mathbf{I}) = 0, \quad (2.60)$$

which expands to

$$\begin{vmatrix} -\frac{(K_w + K_g)}{C_{\text{plat}}} - \lambda & \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} \\ \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}} & -\frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}} - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (2.61)$$

This yields

$$\left(-\frac{(K_w + K_g)}{C_{\text{plat}}} - \lambda\right) \left(-\frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}} - \lambda\right) - \left(\frac{K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}}\right) \left(\frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}}\right) = 0, \quad (2.62)$$

which reduces to

$$\lambda^2 + \lambda \left(\frac{K_w + K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}}\right) + \frac{K_w K_g}{C_{\text{plat}} C_{\text{sample}}} = 0. \quad (2.63)$$

This quadratic equation can be expressed as $\lambda^2 + b\lambda + c = 0$, where

$$b = \frac{K_w + K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}}, \quad c = \frac{K_w K_g}{C_{\text{plat}} C_{\text{sample}}}. \quad (2.64)$$

Solving for the roots gives

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4c}}{2} = \frac{-\left(\frac{K_w + K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}}\right) \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{K_w + K_g}{C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{C_{\text{sample}}}\right)^2 - 4\frac{K_w K_g}{C_{\text{plat}} C_{\text{sample}}}}{2}. \quad (2.65)$$

Defining

$$\alpha = \frac{K_w}{2C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{2C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{2C_{\text{sample}}}, \quad \beta = \sqrt{\left(\frac{K_g}{2C_{\text{plat}}} + \frac{K_g}{2C_{\text{sample}}}\right)^2 + \frac{K_g K_w}{C_{\text{plat}} C_{\text{sample}}}}, \quad (2.66)$$

the eigenvalues can be written as $\lambda_{1,2} = -\alpha \pm \beta$. The general solution for the platform temperature is therefore

$$T_{\text{plat}}(t) = A_1 e^{-\lambda_1 t} + A_2 e^{-\lambda_2 t}, \quad (2.67)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are constants determined by the initial conditions. The associated time

constants are

$$\tau_1 = -\frac{1}{\lambda_1} = \frac{1}{\alpha - \beta}, \quad \tau_2 = -\frac{1}{\lambda_2} = \frac{1}{\alpha + \beta}. \quad (2.68)$$

In summary, Fig. 2.8 compares the heating and cooling curves for the *single- τ* and *two- τ*

Figure 2.8: Temporal profiles of heater power and platform temperature in (a) the *single-tau* model and (b) the *two-tau* model.

models. The experimental temperature–time data are fitted using a nonlinear least-squares method, and the goodness of fit is evaluated using the chi-squared statistic (χ^2). The thermal coupling efficiency between the sample and platform is quantified as

$$\text{Coupling (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{K_g}{K_g + K_w}. \quad (2.69)$$

These analyses yield the experimental value of C_p .

In this dissertation, all heat capacity measurements were performed using a Quantum Design PPMS in the temperature range $0.1 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$ and in magnetic fields up to 14 T. For temperatures below 2 K, additional ^3He and dilution refrigerator inserts were employed.

2.5 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR)

The discovery of nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) dates back to the early 20th century. Isidor Isaac Rabi first demonstrated magnetic resonance in molecular beams, a contribution that earned him the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1944. Subsequently, in late 1940s, Edward M.

Purcell at Harvard University and Felix Bloch at Stanford University independently developed the technique into a practical spectroscopy tool. Their groundbreaking work laid the foundation for modern NMR, and they were jointly awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1952.

NMR is now a powerful and versatile local probe extensively employed across Physics, Chemistry, and Biology to investigate the structural and dynamic properties of matter. At its core, *“NMR is applicable to any nucleus possessing a non-zero nuclear spin ($I \neq 0$), provided there is a finite hyperfine interaction with the surrounding electronic environment”*. The method exploits the Zeeman interaction between nuclear magnetic moments and an external magnetic field, enabling precise microscopic characterization of material properties.

In the field of Chemistry, NMR has become an indispensable technique for exploring the molecular structure and bonding characteristics of organic compounds. Similarly, in Biology, it plays a pivotal role in investigating the conformations and dynamic behaviors of complex biomolecules, including proteins and nucleic acids. Within Condensed Matter Physics, NMR serves as a powerful microscopic tool for probing magnetic and electronic properties of solids. It allows for the investigation of local spin dynamics, internal magnetic fields, and low-energy excitations, which are crucial for understanding the ground states and excitations in complex materials.

2.5.1 Basic Principles of NMR

When a nucleus possessing angular momentum \vec{I} and a corresponding magnetic moment $\vec{\mu} = \gamma_N \vec{I}$ (where γ_N denotes the nuclear gyromagnetic ratio) is placed in a static external magnetic field $\vec{H}_z = H_0 \hat{z}$, the interaction generates a torque given by $\vec{\tau} = \frac{d\vec{I}}{dt}$. Further, this τ exerted by \vec{H} results in the time evolution of both \vec{I} and μ , which can be described by the classical equations of motion:

$$\frac{d\vec{I}}{dt} = \vec{\mu} \times \vec{H}_z, \quad (2.70a)$$

$$\frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt} = \vec{\mu} \times (\gamma_N \vec{H}_z). \quad (2.70b)$$

Equation (2.70b) indicates that the μ precesses around \vec{H}_z with a constant frequency called Larmor frequency, $\omega_L = \gamma_N \vec{H}_z$. Since the precession frequency of nuclear magnetization vector \vec{M} is of the $\mathcal{O}(10 - 150)$ MHz, even a short pulse of $5\mu\text{s}$ would correspond to hundreds of revolutions, making the motion look really fast and mathematically cumbersome. To simplify the mathematical description of NMR, a transformation of Eq. (2.70b) from the laboratory frame of reference (stationary frame) to a rotating frame is commonly employed.

It is known from the rigid body mechanics, for a vector $\vec{S} = S_x \hat{x} + S_y \hat{y} + S_z \hat{z}$ in the laboratory frame one can define the transformation of \vec{S} rotating with angular velocity $\vec{\omega}$ (rotating frame) as

$$\left. \frac{d\vec{S}}{dt} \right|_{\text{rot}} = \left. \frac{d\vec{S}}{dt} \right|_{\text{lab}} - \vec{\omega} \times \vec{S}. \quad (2.71)$$

Using the above transformation, the motion of μ in the laboratory frame, Eq. (2.70b), can be rewritten in the rotating coordinate system as

$$\left. \frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt} \right|_{\text{rot}} = \left. \frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt} \right|_{\text{lab}} - \vec{\omega} \times \vec{\mu}, \quad (2.72)$$

$$= \vec{\mu} \times (\gamma_N \vec{H}_z) - \vec{\omega} \times \vec{\mu}, \quad (2.73)$$

$$= \vec{\mu} \times \left(\gamma_N \vec{H}_z + \vec{\omega} \right), \quad (2.74)$$

$$= \gamma_N \vec{\mu} \times \left(\vec{H}_z + \frac{\vec{\omega}}{\gamma_N} \right). \quad (2.75)$$

Thus, Eq. (2.75) is the same as Eq. (2.70b) with an effective field $H_{\text{eff}} = \vec{H}_z + \omega/\gamma_N$.

In an NMR experiment, along with the static field, we apply a time-varying oscillating magnetic field in the form of radio-frequency (rf). This rf -field is generated by an alternating current passed through the NMR coil, driven by a pulse generator. Typically, rf -field consists of two circularly polarized components rotating in opposite directions, expressed mathematically as

$$\vec{H}_{\pm}(t) = H'_1(\hat{x} \cos \omega t \pm \hat{y} \sin \omega t). \quad (2.76)$$

Of these, only the component rotating in sync (i.e., $\vec{H}_1 = \vec{H}_+ + \vec{H}_-$) with the precessional motion of the spin contributes significantly [via the rotating wave approximation (RWA)]. This results in $\vec{H}_1(t) = 2H_1' \cos\omega t \hat{x} = H_1 \cos\omega t \hat{x}$. Physically, RWA is valid when the amplitude of the *rf*-field H_1 is much smaller than the Larmor field H_z (i.e., $\gamma H_1 \ll \omega$), and the applied *rf*-frequency ω is close to resonance. This ensures that the spin can adiabatically follow the co-rotating field component while the other component effectively cancels out due to its rapid oscillations. Now, if we shift our attention to the rotating frame which moves with ω along the *z*-direction, \vec{H}_1 and H_z are both static. Hence, the time evolution of the magnetic moment $\vec{\mu}$ in the laboratory frame is given by

$$\frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt} = \gamma_N \vec{\mu} \times (\vec{H}_z + \vec{H}_1(t)). \quad (2.77)$$

In the rotating frame the time derivative of magnetic moment Eq. (2.77) transforms into

$$\left(\frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt}\right)_{\text{rot}} = \vec{\mu} \times (\gamma_N \vec{H}_z + \gamma_N \vec{H}_1 - \vec{\omega}). \quad (2.78)$$

Thus, the final equation of motion becomes

$$\left(\frac{d\vec{\mu}}{dt}\right)_{\text{rot}} = \gamma_N \vec{\mu} \times \vec{H}_{\text{eff}}. \quad (2.79)$$

We thereby obtain the effective magnetic field (H_{eff}) in the rotating frame as:

$$\vec{H}_{\text{eff}} = \left(H_z - \frac{\omega}{\gamma_N}\right) \hat{z} + H_1 \hat{x}. \quad (2.80)$$

This result illustrates that, in the rotating frame, the dynamics of the spin resemble simple precession around a static field \vec{H}_{eff} as depicted in Fig. 2.9(a). Here, the effective field combines the Larmor field and the transverse *rf* field.

Based on Eq. (2.80), we can now consider its limiting cases, which are very important

Figure 2.9: (a) Visualization of the \vec{H}_{eff} in the rotating frame. The static field component $(H_z - \omega/\gamma_N)\hat{z}$ (magenta) and the transverse rf field $H_1\hat{x}$ (blue) combine to form the effective field \vec{H}_{eff} (red). The magnetic moment vector $\vec{\mu}$ (green) precesses about \vec{H}_{eff} in a conical trajectory, as shown by the dotted circular path. (b) Response of magnetic moment towards a 90° pulse, and its relaxation back to equilibrium. (c) Schematic representation of FID: variation of transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) with delay time (t).

in the context of performing NMR experiments. Since, we are considering the dynamics in a rotating coordinate system, we define the azimuthal angle θ [shown in Fig. 2.9(a)], by which the moment is tilted away from the z -axis. For an angular frequency $\omega = \gamma_N H_z$, the moments will be completely projected on to the x -axis with $\vec{H}_{\text{eff}} = H_1\hat{x}$. Thus, we can define $\theta = \gamma_N H_1 \tau_w$, where τ_w is the time for which the rf -pulse is switched on. This implies that, by adjusting the values of H_1 and τ_w we can control the phase of moments, either it could be a 90° -pulse ($\theta = \pi/2$) or a 180° -pulse ($\theta = \pi$), which are very fundamental for NMR experiments.

In an NMR experiment, when a 90° rf -pulse is applied, the moments along the z -axis will be projected on to x -axis [see Fig. 2.9(b)], which will be alternating along x and $-x$

directions, thereby producing an induced emf in the NMR coil. Once the *rf*-pulse is turned off, the moment returns to its original *z*-direction, a phenomenon known as Free-Induction Decay (FID). As depicted in Fig. 2.9(c), during the FID process, transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) decreases exponentially, while it relaxes back to its equilibrium. More details about NMR detection will be discussed later.

Apart from the classical picture mentioned in the previous discussion, under the influence of a static and homogeneous magnetic field, one can treat μ and its response as a quantum mechanical phenomena. The corresponding Zeeman Hamiltonian can expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{Zeeman}} = -\vec{\mu} \cdot \vec{H}_z = -\gamma_{\text{N}} H_0 \hat{I}_z, \quad (2.81)$$

where, \hat{I}_z is the component of nuclear moment in *z*-direction with eigenvalues $m\hbar$, where m is the magnetic quantum number. Under an external magnetic field ($H_z = H_0 \hat{z}$), the energy levels splits into $2I + 1$ degenerate states with eigen values given by

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{Zeeman}} |m\rangle = -\gamma_{\text{N}} H_0 \hat{I}_z |m\rangle = \underbrace{-\gamma_{\text{N}} H_0 m \hbar}_{E_m} |m\rangle. \quad (2.82)$$

The obtained eigenvalue E_m is $2I + 1$ degenerate with values of m ranging from I to $-I$. Inorder to observe NMR, we need to induce a transition between $|m\rangle$'s by an external perturbation, which in our case is the H_1 assuming $H_1 \ll H_z$. Since H_1 is periodic and time-dependent, we apply Fermi's Golden Rule to determine the transition probability between $|m\rangle$ and $|m'\rangle$, expressed as

$$W_{m \rightarrow m'} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle m | \mathcal{H}_1 | m' \rangle|^2 \delta(\hbar\omega_{m,m'} - \hbar\omega). \quad (2.83)$$

Figure 2.10: Diagram showing the Zeeman energy level splitting for $I = 1/2$ nucleus.

Based on Eq. (2.83), for a non-zero probability of transition, $\langle m | \mathcal{H}_1 | m' \rangle \equiv \langle m | \mathcal{I}_z | m' \rangle \neq 0$, which is satisfied only for $m' = m \pm 1$. The simplest example to visualize this scenario is the case of a $I = 1/2$ nucleus (see Fig. 2.10), the allowed transition is between $|1/2\rangle$ and $|-1/2\rangle$ levels with an energy difference $\Delta E = E_{1/2} - E_{-1/2}$.

2.5.2 Electron-nucleus interactions

The theoretical framework introduced thus far has considered nuclear spins in isolation, neglecting their interactions with the surrounding electromagnetic environment. In real materials, nuclei inevitably interact with their immediate surroundings, such as electron clouds, neighboring nuclear spins, and the crystalline lattice. These interactions introduce additional terms into the total Hamiltonian, consequently modifying the resonance condition from the ideal Larmor frequency, ω_L . The characteristics of hyperfine and quadrupolar interactions are discussed in the following section.

2.5.2.1 Hyperfine interaction

The electron-nucleus interactions generally consist of two primary contributions: the hyperfine interaction (\mathcal{H}_{hf}) and the electric quadrupolar interaction (\mathcal{H}_Q). The Hamiltonian that governs

Figure 2.11: Schematic representation of all possible hyperfine interactions in an Fe^{3+} -based system.

the hyperfine interaction is given by [179, 180]

$$\mathcal{H}_{ne} = 2\mu_B \left[\frac{\vec{l}}{r^3} + 3 \frac{(\vec{S} \cdot \vec{r})\vec{r}}{r^5} - \frac{\vec{S}}{r^3} + \frac{8\pi}{3} \vec{S} \delta(\vec{r}) \right] \cdot \vec{\mu}_N. \quad (2.84)$$

In Eq. (2.84), the first term represents the interaction between the orbital angular momentum of the electron and the nuclear magnetic moment, $\vec{\mu}_N$. The second and third terms collectively represent the dipolar contribution to the hyperfine coupling. The last term is known as the Fermi contact interaction, which arises primarily from the s -electron due to its finite probability amplitude at the nucleus (i.e., at $r = 0$). Mathematically, this is represented by the Dirac-delta function, $\delta(r)$, in Eq. (2.84). Compared to the dipolar interaction, which rapidly decreases as the distance between nuclei increases, the Fermi contact term is usually dominant. The Fermi contact interaction itself can be separated into two distinct contributions. The first one arises from the indirect coupling of an electron wave function at a given atomic site with the nucleus at a different atomic site, mediated via overlapping wave functions. This indirect coupling is referred to as the transferred hyperfine coupling (A_{trans}). The second contribution originates from the direct overlap between the nuclear wave function and the s -orbital wave function at

the same atomic site, known as onsite coupling (A_{onsite}).

Figure 2.11 schematically depicts these hyperfine interactions in the context of material discussed in this thesis, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The diffuse black circles represent the s -orbitals of P ($3s$), O ($2s$), and Fe ($4s$). The solid blue lobes illustrate the O $2p$ and Fe $3d$ orbitals. The orange dashed lines symbolize the direct dipolar hyperfine coupling (H_{dipolar}) between Fe $3d$ electrons and P $3p$ electrons. The red dotted line shows the pathway for the transferred hyperfine coupling interaction (A_{trans}), specifically following the electron orbital overlap route: P($3p$)–O($2p$)–O($3s$)–O($2p$)–Fe($3d$). Thus, in an NMR experiment probing the ^{31}P nuclei, the observed hyperfine interaction is predominantly due to the transferred hyperfine coupling mediated by the oxygen p orbitals, along with a minor contribution from direct dipolar coupling between Fe and P nuclei.

2.5.2.2 Electric Quadrupolar Interaction

From classical electrodynamics, for a charge density distribution $\rho(\vec{r})$ in an electrostatic potential $V(\vec{r})$, the total Hamiltonian is given by:

$$\mathcal{H} = \int \rho(\vec{r})V(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}. \quad (2.85)$$

Expanding the potential $V(\vec{r})$ using a multipole expansion around the origin yields:

$$V(\vec{r}) = V_0 + \sum_j x_j \left[\frac{\delta V}{\delta x_j} \right]_{r=0} + \sum_{i,j} x_i x_j \left[\frac{\delta^2 V}{\delta x_i \delta x_j} \right]_{r=0} + \dots \quad (2.86)$$

In Eq. (2.86), the first term corresponds to the monopole contribution and vanishes for systems with zero net charge. If the charge distribution exhibits spherical or spheroidal symmetry, the second (dipole) term also vanishes. However, even under these conditions, the quadrupolar (third-order) term remains finite. The quadrupole moment is defined as:

$$Q_{ij} = \int \rho(r) \left(x_i x_j - \frac{r^2}{3} \delta_{ij} \right) dr, \quad (2.87)$$

resulting in the quadrupolar Hamiltonian:

$$\mathcal{H}_Q = \sum_{i,j} V_{ij} Q_{ij} = \frac{e^2 q Q}{4I(2I-1)} \left[3\hat{I}_z^2 - \hat{I}(\hat{I}+1) + \frac{\eta}{2}(\hat{I}_+^2 + \hat{I}_-^2) \right], \quad (2.88)$$

where V_{ij} is a symmetric and traceless tensor known as the electric field gradient (EFG). The largest eigenvalue of the EFG tensor is commonly denoted as $V_{zz} = eq$. It is well-established that a non-zero quadrupolar interaction occurs only for nuclear spins with $I \geq 1$, since it arises from shifts in the nuclear energy levels caused by interactions with non-uniform electric fields.

Quantum mechanically, the quadrupolar interaction is represented using a second-rank irreducible spherical tensor operator $T_q^{(2)}$, with q taking integer values from -2 to 2 , where each q identifies a particular component of the quadrupole tensor. According to the Wigner-Eckart theorem, the matrix elements of $T_q^{(k)}$ in the angular momentum eigenbasis factorize into an angular momentum-independent part and a Clebsch-Gordan coefficient $C_{mqm'}^{IkI}$ [181]:

$$\langle I, m' | T_q^{(k)} | I, m \rangle \propto \langle I || T^{(k)} || I \rangle \cdot C_{mqm'}^{IkI}. \quad (2.89)$$

These matrix elements are non-zero only when the triangle inequality is satisfied:

$$|I - I| \leq k \leq I + I \quad \Rightarrow \quad k \leq 2I. \quad (2.90)$$

Specifically, for the quadrupole operator ($k = 2$), the condition simplifies to:

$$2I \geq 2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad I \geq 1. \quad (2.91)$$

This condition clearly indicates that finite quadrupolar interactions occur exclusively for nuclei with spin quantum numbers $I \geq 1$.

The EFG tensor V_{ij} , being symmetric and traceless, has three principal components V_{xx} , V_{yy} , and V_{zz} , ordered as $|V_{zz}| \geq |V_{yy}| \geq |V_{xx}|$. The degree of asymmetry is quantified by the

parameter $\eta = (V_{xx} - V_{yy})/V_{zz}$, with η ranging between 0 and 1. Axial symmetry ($V_{xx} = V_{yy}$) corresponds to $\eta = 0$, while maximum asymmetry ($V_{xx} = 0$ and $V_{yy} = -V_{zz}$) corresponds to $\eta = 1$.

In actual NMR experiments, knowledge of η and the quadrupolar frequency $\nu_Q \equiv \frac{3e^2qQ}{2hI(2I-1)}$ enables prediction of the quadrupolar splitting using the expression:

$$\delta_Q = \frac{1}{2}\nu_Q(3\cos^2\theta - 1 + \eta\sin^2\theta\cos 2\phi), \quad (2.92)$$

where θ and ϕ are angles defining the orientation of the external magnetic field relative to the principal axis of the EFG tensor [182].

For a probed nucleus with spin $I \geq 1$, there are typically $2I - 1$ quadrupolar resonances for axial symmetry ($\eta = 0$), appearing at frequencies $n\nu_Q$ ($n = 1, \dots, 2I - 1$). For non-axial symmetry ($\eta \neq 0$), the quadrupolar splitting intervals become unequal. However, in this thesis, the NMR experiments were performed on ^{31}P nuclei ($I = \frac{1}{2}$), for which the quadrupolar interaction is absent, yielding $\delta_Q = 0$.

2.5.3 NMR Shift

When a nucleus is irradiated with an *rf*-pulse, the energy difference between m and $m + 1$ levels is proportional to the applied magnetic field. Here, the proportionality factor γ_N varies according to the electronic environment which is specific to a particular nuclei (e.g. $[^{31}\text{P}] \gamma_N/2\pi = 17.2356 \text{ MHz/T}$, $[^1\text{H}] \gamma_N/2\pi = 42.5774 \text{ MHz/T}$). Once the electron spins interact, it induces an excess field, ΔH at the nuclear site. Due to this, the position of NMR lineshape is shifted away from the resonance line of the nuclei (H_{ref}) by ΔH .

In the linear response limit, the NMR shift (\mathcal{K}) can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{K}(\%) = \frac{\Delta H}{H_p} \times 100 = \frac{H_{\text{ref}} - H_p}{H_p} \times 100, \quad (2.93)$$

Here, H_p denotes the resonance field of the sample. Converting this into frequency domain we

Figure 2.12: Effect of effective field in the NMR spectra.

obtain

$$\mathcal{K}(\%) = \frac{\omega_p - \omega_{\text{ref}}}{\omega_{\text{ref}}} \times 100, \quad (2.94)$$

where ω_{ref} and ω_p corresponds to resonance frequencies of reference nuclei (zero-shift position) and the sample respectively. Thus, the effective shift in both field and frequency domain can be written from Eq. (2.93) and Eq. (2.94), respectively as

$$\boxed{H_{\text{ref}} = H_p(1 + \mathcal{K}) \text{ and } \omega_p = \omega_{\text{ref}}(1 + \mathcal{K}).} \quad (2.95)$$

In this thesis, we focus on magnetic insulators, where localized electrons associated with paramagnetic ions generate a local magnetic field that interacts with the nuclear spins. Consequently, to describe the response of a nucleus to an external magnetic field, the complete Hamiltonian can be written as [179]

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{nuclei}} = \mathcal{H}_{\text{Zeeman}} + \mathcal{H}_{\text{ne}} + \mathcal{H}_Q + \mathcal{H}_{\text{dia}} + \mathcal{H}_{\text{nn}}. \quad (2.96)$$

As discussed in the above sections, $\mathcal{H}_{\text{Zeeman}}$, \mathcal{H}_{ne} , and \mathcal{H}_Q denotes the Zeeman, electron-nucleus, and quadrupolar interactions, respectively. In addition to these, the Hamiltonian con-

sists of diamagnetic contribution \mathcal{H}_{dia} (coupling between the nuclear magnetic vector potential and the applied field) and nuclear-nuclear interactions \mathcal{H}_{nn} . These contributions are mathematically expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{dia}} = \frac{e^2}{2mc^2} (\vec{H}_0 \times \vec{r}) \cdot \vec{\mu}_{\text{N}}, \quad (2.97)$$

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{nn}} = \frac{e^2}{2mc^2} \left[\frac{\vec{\mu}_{\text{N}} \times \vec{r}}{r^3} \right]^2. \quad (2.98)$$

In a nutshell, the effect of individual terms in Eq. (2.96) towards the NMR shift is as follows. $\mathcal{H}_{\text{Zeeman}}$ sets the reference Larmor frequency of the nucleus, \mathcal{H}_{nn} causes spectral line broadening due to nuclear-nuclear dipolar interactions [182], \mathcal{H}_Q splits the NMR line in accordance with the first order perturbation theory, as discussed earlier, \mathcal{H}_{dia} gives rise to the diamagnetic shift K_{dia} , and \mathcal{H}_{ne} represents the electron-nucleus interaction in which the orbital contribution [see Eq. (2.84)] produces the orbital shift K_{orb} . These two terms later translate into diamagnetic (χ_{dia}) and Van Vleck (χ_{vv}) susceptibilities.

The temperature-dependent spin contribution to the NMR shift, $K_{\text{spin}}(T)$, originates from hyperfine coupling between the nuclear and electronic spins. This spin term can be decomposed into a dipolar part K_{dipolar} , arising from the anisotropic hyperfine interaction, and a Fermi contact part K_{contact} . Thus, the total NMR shift (K) and the corresponding total susceptibility (χ) can be expressed as

$$K(T) = K_{\text{chemical}} + K_{\text{spin}}(T), \quad (2.99)$$

$$= (K_{\text{dia}} + K_{\text{orb}}) + (K_{\text{dipolar}} + K_{\text{contact}}), \quad (2.100)$$

$$\chi = \chi_{\text{dia}} + \chi_{\text{vv}} + \chi_{\text{spin}}(T). \quad (2.101)$$

On the basis of Eq. (2.84), the nucleus experiences a local magnetic field generated by the surrounding electronic moments. For an isotropic contribution, these couplings can be

summarized by a hyperfine constant A_{hf} in the unit of T/μ_{B} , such that

$$\vec{H}_{\text{loc}}^{\text{spin}} = A_{\text{hf}} \langle \vec{\mu} \rangle, \quad (2.102)$$

where $\langle \vec{\mu} \rangle$ is the thermal average of the electronic magnetic moment per formula unit.

In the linear-response limit, the molar spin magnetization is defined as

$$\vec{M}_{\text{spin}} = N_{\text{A}} \mu_{\text{B}} \langle \vec{S} \rangle = \chi_{\text{spin}}(T) \vec{H}_{\text{p}}, \quad (2.103)$$

where N_{A} is Avogadro's number, μ_{B} is the Bohr magneton, and $\chi_{\text{spin}}(T)$ is the molar spin susceptibility. From this, one obtains

$$\langle \vec{S} \rangle = \frac{\chi_{\text{spin}}(T)}{N_{\text{A}} \mu_{\text{B}}} \vec{H}_{\text{p}}. \quad (2.104)$$

Substituting back into Eq. (2.102), the hyperfine field takes the form

$$\vec{H}_{\text{loc}}^{\text{spin}} = \frac{A_{\text{hf}}}{N_{\text{A}} \mu_{\text{B}}} \chi_{\text{spin}}(T) \vec{H}_{\text{p}}. \quad (2.105)$$

Finally, the NMR shift, defined as the fractional change of the resonance field relative to H_{p} , becomes

$$K(T) = \frac{\Delta H}{H_{\text{p}}} = K_0 + \frac{A_{\text{hf}}}{N_{\text{A}} \mu_{\text{B}}} \chi_{\text{spin}}(T), \quad (2.106)$$

where K_0 denotes the temperature-independent orbital/diamagnetic contribution. Equation (2.106) demonstrates that the NMR shift directly probes the intrinsic spin susceptibility, and is insensitive to extrinsic impurities as opposed to bulk magnetic susceptibility. A plot of K versus χ with temperature as an implicit parameter (the Clogston-Jaccarino plot [183]) yields a straight line, whose slope gives A_{hf} and intercept gives K_0 .

2.5.4 Relaxation

In the previous section, we established that the NMR shift provides direct insight into the local static magnetic susceptibility of the system. Complementary to this, the dynamic properties are probed through NMR relaxation measurements, namely the nuclear spin-lattice relaxation rate ($1/T_1$) and the nuclear spin-spin relaxation rate ($1/T_2$).

2.5.4.1 Nuclear Spin-Lattice Relaxation (T_1)

In NMR, the term *spin-lattice relaxation* refers to the mechanism by which perturbed nuclear spins return to thermal equilibrium with their environment. Usually, in an NMR experiment, this process is induced by a *rf*-pulse, which disturbs the magnetization, which gradually recovers its maximum/equilibrium value M_0 by exchanging energy with lattice. The characteristic time scale at which this process occurs is given by spin-lattice relaxation time T_1 .

A practical description for this phenomena is given by a set of equations introduced by Felix Bloch, referred as Bloch equations [179]. Under an external magnetic field $\vec{H}_z = H_0 \hat{z}$, as mentioned in Eq. (2.70b), the total magnetization \vec{M} obeys

$$\frac{d\vec{M}}{dt} = \gamma \vec{M} \times \vec{H}_0, \quad (2.107)$$

which describes the precession of nuclear spins, together with mathematical nature of longitudinal and transverse components in relation to their equilibrium magnetization (M_0) given by

$$\frac{dM_z}{dt} = \frac{M_0 - M_z}{T_1}, \quad \frac{dM_x}{dt} = -\frac{M_x}{T_2}, \quad \frac{dM_y}{dt} = -\frac{M_y}{T_2}, \quad (2.108)$$

where T_2 is the transverse or spin-spin relaxation time.

Combining Eq. (2.108), including effects from both static and *rf* field (\vec{H}), one obtains the

vector form,

$$\boxed{\frac{d\vec{M}}{dt} = \gamma\vec{M} \times \vec{H} - \frac{(M_x\hat{i} + M_y\hat{j})}{T_2} - \frac{(M_z - M_0)\hat{k}}{T_1}}. \quad (2.109)$$

Hence, T_1 controls the recovery of the longitudinal magnetization, while T_2 is responsible for the recovery of transverse magnetization.

A microscopic picture of the longitudinal relaxation is obtained by introducing the notion of *spin temperature* T_s for two adjacent levels $|m\rangle$ and $|n\rangle$. Even when the nuclear spins are not in equilibrium with the lattice, their level populations based on Boltzmann distribution can be described by

$$\frac{p_m}{p_n} = \exp\left(\frac{\gamma\hbar H}{k_B T_s}\right), \quad (2.110)$$

with p_m and p_n are the probabilities for the Zeeman states $|m\rangle$ and $|n\rangle$, respectively.

To derive the expression for $1/T_1$ in terms of T_s and the probability of transition between the states, we start with Eq. (2.108)

$$\frac{dM_z}{dt} = -\frac{(M - M_0)}{T_1}. \quad (2.111)$$

Using Curie's law, $M \propto 1/T \propto \beta$, the relaxation corresponding to the decay of T_s towards the lattice temperature T_L can be written as

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = -\frac{1}{T_1}(\beta - \beta_0), \quad (2.112)$$

where $\beta = 1/k_B T_s$ and $\beta_0 = 1/k_B T_L$. By definition, the average energy \bar{E} can be written in terms of density matrix ρ and the Hamiltonian of the total system \mathcal{H}_0 as $\bar{E} = \text{tr}\{\rho\mathcal{H}_0\}$. Thus, the energy exchange between spin and lattice can be written in terms of the rate of change of \bar{E} as

$$\frac{d\bar{E}}{dt} = \frac{1}{Z}(\beta - \beta_0)\langle H_0^2 \rangle. \quad (2.113)$$

Since, we consider a discrete energy level, \bar{E} can be expressed in terms of probability as $\bar{E} = \sum_m E_m P_m$. The rate of change of \bar{E} can be expressed as

$$\frac{d\bar{E}}{dt} = \sum_m \frac{dP_m}{dt} E_m. \quad (2.114)$$

Let P_m be the population of m^{th} level and W_{nm} be the transition rate from n^{th} to m^{th} level.

The rate of change in population can be written as

$$\frac{dP_m}{dt} = \sum_n [W_{mn} P_n - W_{nm} P_m]. \quad (2.115)$$

At equilibrium, $\frac{dP_m}{dt} = 0$

$$0 = \sum_n [W_{mn} P_n^0 - W_{nm} P_m^0]. \quad (2.116)$$

Hence, in the state of equilibrium and during the process of excitation, the rate of change in population can be obtained by subtracting Eq. (2.116) from Eq. (2.115) to give

$$\frac{dP_m}{dt} = \sum_n [W_{mn} (P_n - P_n^0) - W_{nm} (P_m - P_m^0)]. \quad (2.117)$$

Probability of m^{th} level can be expressed in terms of partition function Z as $P_m = \exp(-\beta E_m)/Z$.

In the linear limit, we can write this as $P_m = (1 - \beta E_m)/Z$. Substituting this into Eq. (2.117),

we get

$$\frac{dP_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{Z} (\beta_0 - \beta) \sum_n [W_{mn} E_n - W_{nm} E_m]. \quad (2.118)$$

Now, considering $W_{nm} = W_{mn}$ (transition between $|m\rangle$ and $|n\rangle$ states), Eq. (2.114) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d\bar{E}}{dt} = \frac{1}{Z} (\beta_0 - \beta) \sum_{m,n} [W_{mn} E_m (E_n - E_m)]. \quad (2.119)$$

Now, we symmetrize the double sum by adding the same expression in [...] of Eq. (2.119) with

$m \leftrightarrow n$ and dividing by two

$$\frac{d\bar{E}}{dt} = -\frac{1}{2Z}(\beta_0 - \beta) \sum_{m,n} W_{mn}(E_n - E_m)^2. \quad (2.120)$$

Here, the terms $(E_n - E_m)^2$, W_{mn} , and Z are all ≥ 0 . The most important aspect of Eq. (2.120) is the negative sign, which ensures that the spin system always evolves towards the lattice temperature T_L . Equating Eqns. (2.113) and (2.120) finally yields the expression of $1/T_1$ in terms of W_{mn} as

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sum_{m,n} W_{mn}(E_n - E_m)^2}{\langle \mathcal{H}_0^2 \rangle}. \quad (2.121)$$

It is important to highlight that the expression Eq. (2.121) represents a semi-classical treatment for determining $1/T_1$. Furthermore, a more clear picture of the nuclear relaxation is understood on the basis of fluctuations in the local magnetic field at the nuclear site, attributed to the electronic degrees of freedom. Hence, $1/T_1$ essentially measures how these time-dependent hyperfine fields couple to the nuclear moments.

To understand this phenomena of $1/T_1$ analytically, we consider a perturbing Hamiltonian (\mathcal{H}'_{\perp}) with a finite hyperfine interaction, of the form

$$\mathcal{H}'_{\perp} = -\gamma \hbar \vec{I} \cdot \vec{H}_{\text{hf}} = -\frac{\hbar \gamma}{2} (I^+ H_{\text{hf}}^- + I^- H_{\text{hf}}^+), \quad (2.122)$$

where \vec{H}_{hf} denotes the fluctuating hyperfine field, and I^{\pm} are the nuclear spin raising and lowering operators. Also, Eq. (2.122) ensures that the nuclear spin flips are driven by the transverse components of the fluctuating hyperfine field.

Near equilibrium, $1/T_1$ is the sum of up and down spin-flip rates averaged over initial thermal bath states and summed over the final bath states as

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \sum_n P_n \sum_m [W_{mn} + W_{nm}], \quad (2.123)$$

where W_{mn} can be expressed following the Fermi's Golden rule

$$W_{mn} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle m | \mathcal{H}'_{\perp} | n \rangle|^2 \delta(E_f - E_i \pm \hbar\omega_0). \quad (2.124)$$

Here, the term $|\langle m | \mathcal{H}'_{\perp} | n \rangle|^2$ tells us how efficiently the fluctuations during $m \leftrightarrow n$ can drive a nuclear flip and $\delta(E_f - E_i \pm \hbar\omega_0)$ ensures energy conservation. Now, we can write the expression for $1/T_1$ in term of fluctuation field as

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} \left(\frac{\gamma\hbar}{2} \right)^2 \sum_n \frac{e^{-\beta E_n}}{Z} \sum_m \left[|\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle|^2 \delta(E_f - E_i + \hbar\omega_0) + |\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^- | n \rangle|^2 \delta(E_f - E_i - \hbar\omega_0) \right]. \quad (2.125)$$

Further solving yields,

$$1/T_1 = \frac{2\pi\gamma^2}{4} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{-\beta E_n}}{Z} \left[|\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle|^2 \delta\left(\frac{E_f - E_i + \hbar\omega_0}{\hbar}\right) + |\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^- | n \rangle|^2 \delta\left(\frac{E_f - E_i - \hbar\omega_0}{\hbar}\right) \right]. \quad (2.126)$$

We now replace the δ -functions by the Fourier integral representation as

$$\delta(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{ixt}, \quad (2.127)$$

and rewrite each δ -function term in Eq. (2.126) as a time integral

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{2\pi\gamma^2}{4} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{-\beta\epsilon_n}}{Z} & \left[|\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle|^2 \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i(\epsilon_m - \epsilon_n + \hbar\omega_0)t/\hbar} \right. \\ & \left. + |\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^- | n \rangle|^2 \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i(\epsilon_m - \epsilon_n - \hbar\omega_0)t/\hbar} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.128)$$

Now, the term $|\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle|^2$ can be written in terms of correlation-like form as

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle|^2 &= \langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle \langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle^\dagger \\ &= \langle m | H_{\text{hf}}^+ | n \rangle \langle n | H_{\text{hf}}^- | m \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (2.129)$$

Thus, using Eq. (2.129) we can rewrite Eq. (2.128) as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{\gamma^2}{4} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{-\beta\epsilon_n}}{Z} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} & \left[\langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^+|n\rangle \langle n|H_{\text{hf}}^-|m\rangle e^{i(\epsilon_m - \epsilon_n)t/\hbar} \right. \\ & \left. + \langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^-|n\rangle \langle n|H_{\text{hf}}^+|m\rangle e^{-i(\epsilon_m - \epsilon_n)t/\hbar} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.130)$$

As we can see in Eq. (2.130), we change the operators to time-dependent Heisenberg operators.

Using the Heisenberg picture, we can write the operators in the following form

$$\langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^+|n\rangle e^{i(\epsilon_m - \epsilon_n)t/\hbar} = e^{i(\epsilon_m)t/\hbar} \langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^+|n\rangle e^{-i(\epsilon_n)t/\hbar} = \langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^+|n\rangle. \quad (2.131)$$

Thus, Eq. (2.130) can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T_1} &= \frac{\gamma^2}{4} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{-\beta\epsilon_n}}{Z} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} \left[\langle n|H_{\text{hf}}^-|m\rangle \langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^+(t)|n\rangle + \langle n|H_{\text{hf}}^+|m\rangle \langle m|H_{\text{hf}}^-(t)|n\rangle \right]. \\ &= \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \sum_{n,m} \frac{e^{-\beta\epsilon_n}}{Z} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} \left[\langle n|H_{\text{hf}}^- H_{\text{hf}}^+(t)|n\rangle \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.132)$$

By the definition of correlation function, we can simplify Eq. (2.132) in terms of correlation of hyperfine fields as

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} \langle H_{\text{hf}}^-(0) H_{\text{hf}}^+(t) \rangle.} \quad (2.133)$$

Equation (2.133) implies that $1/T_1$ is determined by the Fourier transform of the time correlation function of the transverse components of the fluctuating hyperfine field, evaluated at the nuclear Larmor frequency ω_0 .

It is often more convenient to evaluate the hyperfine correlator in Eq. (2.133) in the frequency domain. In order to do that, we use the Fluctuation–Dissipation (FD) theorem [184], where one can relate the hyperfine field correlation function to the imaginary part of the dy-

namical susceptibility (χ''). We can apply FD theorem in Eq. (2.133) to obtain

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_0}{2k_B T}\right) \frac{\hbar\omega_0}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} \langle H_{\text{hf}}^-(0) H_{\text{hf}}^+(t) \rangle. \quad (2.134)$$

Further, $H_{\text{hf}}(t)$ can be expressed in terms of the electronic spin operators as

$$H_{\text{hf}}(t) = \sum_{\vec{q}} A_{\vec{q}} S_{\vec{q}}(t), \quad (2.135)$$

where $A_{\vec{q}}$ is the hyperfine tensor and $S_{\vec{q}}(t)$ is the Fourier component of the electronic spin operator. Substituting this form yields

$$\langle H_{\text{hf}}^+(0) H_{\text{hf}}^-(t) \rangle = \sum_{\vec{q}} |A_{\vec{q}}|^2 \langle S_{\vec{q}}^+(0) S_{\vec{q}}^-(t) \rangle. \quad (2.136)$$

Now, Eq. (2.134) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{T_1} &= \frac{\gamma^2}{2} \coth\left(\frac{\hbar\omega_0}{2k_B T}\right) \frac{\hbar\omega_0}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{i\omega_0 t} \sum_{\vec{q}} |A_{\vec{q}}|^2 \langle S_{\vec{q}}^+(0) S_{\vec{q}}^-(t) \rangle \\ &\simeq \gamma^2 k_B T \sum_{\vec{q}} |A_{\vec{q}}|^2 \frac{\chi''(q, \omega_0)}{\omega_0} \end{aligned} \quad (2.137)$$

2.5.4.2 Nuclear Spin-Spin Relaxation (T_2)

Let's recall the transverse components (M_x and M_y) of Bloch equation in Eq. (2.108). The transverse relaxation time (T_2) tells us how quickly the transverse nuclear magnetization loses phase coherence. The fundamental reason behind this decoherence is due to static and dynamic dephasing.

In case of static dephasing (spatially varying time-independent fields), different nuclei precess at slightly different local Larmor frequencies, leading to the spreading out of the transverse moments in the xy -plane. To further explain this transverse dephasing, it is convenient to explain in terms of nuclear dipole-dipole interactions. For such an interaction, the z -component

of the field at a position \vec{r} due to a neighboring nuclear moment $\vec{\mu}_N = \gamma_N \hbar \vec{I}$ can be written as

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{loc},z}(\vec{r}) \propto \frac{\gamma_N \hbar}{r^3} (3 \cos^2 \theta - 1), \quad (2.138)$$

where θ the angle between \vec{r} and the external field direction. Thus, nuclear dipole-dipole interaction introduces an additional field, which affects the instantaneous precession rate of individual nuclei. Due to this reason, each nuclei experiences slightly different local field, making the spins gradually drift apart from each other in phase.

For simplicity, we assume that these local perturbation in magnetic field dephases individual spins by one radian. Then, we can write the dephasing condition in terms of dephasing time T_2 as

$$\gamma_N H_{\text{loc},z} T_2 \simeq 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{T_2} \simeq \gamma_N H_{\text{loc},z} \propto \gamma_N^2 \frac{\hbar}{r^3}. \quad (2.139)$$

This implies that the static contribution to $1/T_2$ grows with γ_N^2 and decreases with increasing inter-nuclear distance.

However, time-dependent local fields also dephases M_{xy} . In this case, hyperfine field (H_{hf}) stochastically modulates the Larmor frequency, which contributes directly to $1/T_2$, without any nuclear spin flip process. Instead, the transverse component at the Larmor frequency drives $1/T_1$ and provides an additional channel for the transverse decay.

To summarize, in the weak-fluctuation limit, T_2 has two major contributions. (i) Motional-narrowing: the fast longitudinal hyperfine-field fluctuations ($\omega_0 \tau_0 \ll 1$) cause pure dephasing. (ii) The spin flips (T_1 process) destroys transverse coherence which contributes to the decay in M_{xy} . Macroscopic field variations due to inhomogeneity in applied field and dipole-dipole coupling also introduce static line broadening. Together, we can write this as:

$$\frac{1}{T_2} = \underbrace{\gamma_N^2 \langle H_{\text{hf},z}^2 \rangle \tau_0}_{\text{pure dephasing}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2T_1}}_{\text{lifetime broadening}} + \underbrace{\gamma \Delta H_0}_{\text{field-inhomogeneity}}. \quad (2.140)$$

2.5.5 NMR Data Acquisition and Analysis

In this section, we will provide the basic principles and detection methods used in the NMR experiments. The discussion will be solely based on a classical picture of time evolution of nuclear spin ensembles.

2.5.5.1 Free Induction Decay and Fourier Transform NMR

Figure 2.13: NMR signal detection setup: A *rf* coil wound around the sample which can experience an oscillating *rf* field H_1 along the x -direction. The coil is placed inside the magnet with static field H_0 along the z -direction.

A most simplified schematic of the NMR probe used in our experiment is shown in Fig. 2.13. As discussed in section 2.5.1 previously, an *rf* pulse can tip the nuclear magnetization from the static external field (H_0) direction (z -axis) into the transverse (xy) plane. Once the resonance condition is satisfied, the spins precess coherently around the transverse *rf* field H_1 , with the precession angle given by $\theta = \gamma_N H_1 \tau_p$, where τ_p is the pulse duration. Thus, one can tune H_1 and τ_p , in order to control the tipping angle θ . Hence, $\theta = \pi/2$ yields a 90° pulse, while $\theta = \pi$ corresponds to a 180° pulse.

Figure 2.14: Schematic representation of FID as mentioned in the text.

In an NMR experiment, typically, a $\pi/2$ pulse lasts for a few microseconds to rotate the nuclear magnetization from the z -axis into the transverse plane. Once the pulse ends, the spins precess around H_0 , which in turn generates an oscillating transverse magnetization that decays with time. This decaying signal, which reflects the gradual loss of phase coherence among spins, is referred to as *Free Induction Decay* (FID). As discussed in the previous section, the decay in the xy -plane is primarily governed by T_2 mechanism. However, in real samples, there occurs a decoherence of nuclear spins due to the applied field inhomogeneities across the volume fraction of the sample, leading to additional dephasing. This effectively stretches the decay time due to FID (T_2^*), making it shorter than the T_2 measured in the experiment.

To transform the time-domain FID to the frequency domain we use Fourier transform (FT), which is fundamental to NMR. Since, FID decays exponentially with a time constant T_2^* , we consider the FID signal of the form $S(t) = S_0 \exp(-t/T_2^*)$. Then, its Fourier transform can be

written as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{S}(\omega) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{t}{T_2^*}\right) \exp(-i\omega t) dt \\ &= \frac{1/T_2^*}{2\pi \left[(1/T_2^*)^2 + \omega^2\right]} - i \frac{\omega}{2\pi \left[(1/T_2^*)^2 + \omega^2\right]}.\end{aligned}\quad (2.141)$$

Equation (2.141) implies that the FT of FID signal is a Lorentzian, where the real and imaginary parts correspond to the absorption and dispersion modes, respectively. Typically, in NMR experiment, the absorption line reflects the energy absorbed by nuclear spins at resonance, directly linking to transition probabilities and magnetic interactions within the system. However, the dispersion component is more susceptible to noise and phase shifts, and is commonly avoided.

To quantitatively understand the spin dynamics and spectral resolution, we can estimate the full width at half maximum (FWHM). Recalling Eq. (2.141), the absorption mode of the spectra can be written as

$$\text{Re}[S(\omega)] = \frac{1/T_2^*}{2\pi \left[(1/T_2^*)^2 + \omega^2\right]}.\quad (2.142)$$

Here, the maximum intensity occurs at $\omega = 0$ and the spectral density becomes $S(0) = \frac{T_2^*}{2\pi}$. Now, by definition, FWHM is obtained by setting $S(\omega_{1/2}) = S(0)/2$, yielding $\omega_{1/2}^2 = \frac{1}{(T_2^*)^2}$. Thus, the FWHM in frequency units is expressed as

$$\boxed{\Delta\nu_{\text{FWHM}} = \frac{1}{\pi T_2^*}}.\quad (2.143)$$

This indicates that a shorter T_2^* results in broader lines, reflecting faster transverse relaxation.

2.5.5.2 Spin Echo

In the previous section, we understood that the transverse decay observed in FID is reduced by field inhomogeneities, causing additional broadening and, consequently, a significant reduction in T_2^* . Since an NMR spectrometer has a finite recovery period for the receiver (commonly referred to as the dead time), a portion of the initial signal may be lost. In extreme cases, when T_2^* is much shorter than the dead time, the FID may not be detected at all. To overcome this, Erwin Hahn [185] introduced the *spin echo* technique in 1950, which effectively separates the effects of field inhomogeneities from the intrinsic T_2 processes. The entire spin-echo process is illustrated in Fig 2.15.

The concept is quite straightforward, following an initial $\pi/2$ pulse at $t = 0$, a π pulse is applied after a delay τ . This inverts the spin precession, causing the spins to refocus at $t = 2\tau$, thereby forming an echo signal. During this refocusing, the dephasing caused by static field variations is canceled, while preserving the dephasing associated with intrinsic spin-spin interactions. This allows an accurate determination of T_2 . In practice, the intensity of NMR signal at $t = 2\tau$ decays exponentially with a time constant T_2 , such that it follows

$$I(2\tau) = I(0)e^{-2\tau/T_2}, \quad (2.144)$$

where $I(2\tau)$ is the NMR signal intensity after a time 2τ . Eventhough the spin echo method compensates for inhomogeneous broadening, this method fails to recover the signal if the loss of signal is due to local dipolar fields. In such a case, spin inversion due to π -pulse does not change the dot product $\mu_i \cdot \mu_j$ of any two spin moments, which clearly affects the intrinsic T_2 .

2.5.5.3 Measuring T_1

There are several methods to measure T_1 , and the choice of the method primarily depends on the experimental conditions. In this dissertation, we have implemented the *saturation recovery* method to estimate T_1 . The schematics of this approach is illustrated in Fig. 2.16.

Figure 2.15: Spin-echo process by employing a $\pi/2 - \pi$ pulse sequence.

Figure 2.16: (a) Pulse sequence for T_1 measurement. (b) Variation of longitudinal magnetization as a function of τ_1 .

In saturation recovery method, a series of $\pi/2$ pulses are first applied to completely saturate the nuclear magnetization on to xy -plane, effectively eliminating the magnetization along the z -direction. After saturation, the system is allowed to recover for a variable delay time τ_1 , during which the longitudinal magnetization begins to return back to z -direction. Following this τ_1 , a spin-echo pulse sequence is applied to probe the recovered magnetization. By varying τ_1 , one obtains a series of echo intensities that track the recovery process. Plotting the integrated spin-echo intensity as a function of τ_1 yields a recovery curve, as shown in Fig. 2.16(b).

The spin-lattice relaxation time T_1 is then extracted by fitting the recovery profile to the

Bloch equation:

$$M_z(t) = M_0 \left(1 - e^{-\tau_1/T_1}\right), \quad (2.145)$$

where $M_z(t)$ is the longitudinal magnetization at time τ_1 , and M_0 represents the equilibrium magnetization after full recovery.

2.5.5.4 Measuring T_2

Figure 2.17: (a) Pulse sequence for T_2 measurement. (b) Variation of transverse magnetization as a function of τ

As described earlier, using a spin-echo sequence, we can determine T_2 . The idea of this measurement is that the intensity of the spin-echo decreases with increasing delay time (τ), between initial $\pi/2$ and π pulses. A schematic of the measurement protocol is presented in Fig. 2.17(a). The spin echo intensity at time 2τ is expressed as

$$M_{xy}(2\tau) = M_{xy}(0)e^{-2\tau/T_2}. \quad (2.146)$$

By repeating the spin-echo experiment for a series of delay times (τ), the decay of the integrated spin-echo intensity is recorded. Plotting this decay curve as a function of τ yields an exponential curve as shown in Fig. 2.17(b). Fitting the experimental data to Eq. (2.146) allows an accurate estimation of the transverse relaxation time T_2 .

2.5.6 NMR Experimental Details

Figure 2.18: Schematic representation of a NMR resonant circuit in (a) parallel-tuned series-matched (b) series-tuned parallel-matched configurations. C_T and C_M are the capacitors used for tuning and impedance matching, respectively, while L denotes the coil inductance.

In an NMR experiment, the rf signal generated by the transmitter is directed to the probe. Usually, the sample is positioned inside an inductor coil that forms a part of the LC resonant circuit. The response obtained from the coil, typically of the order μV , is sent back through a coaxial cable to a preamplifier. The preamplifier amplifies this weak signal to a much higher voltage without significantly adding noise, which later is transmitted to the receiver for detection and processing.

In general, the quality of acquired NMR spectra depends on the efficiency of this setup as well as the characteristics of the probe's LC circuit. Since NMR operates in rf , at this frequency, the skin-depth ($\delta = \sqrt{2\rho/\omega\mu}$) is very small. Thus, in our experiments, we used copper coil due to its high electrical conductivity, which can minimize resistive losses at shallow depths. In addition, being a cost-effective material, Cu provides superior thermal and mechanical stability, while its inherently non-magnetic nature plays a crucial role in preserving the homogeneity of the static magnetic field during NMR measurements.

The tank circuit is an essential part of the NMR probe. The resonance frequency (ω_0) of

the circuit that consists of an inductance (L) and a capacitance (C) can be expressed as

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{LC}}. \quad (2.147)$$

In practice, the capacitance of the probe is fixed and inductance of the coil is varied to achieve the desired frequency. A typical NMR coil follows a solenoidal geometry, where the inductance of the coil scales with the number of turns and its dimensions. The inductance can be written as

$$L \propto n^2 \left(\frac{\pi r^2}{l} \right), \quad (2.148)$$

where n denotes the number of turns, r is the coil radius, and l is the average length of the winding. This implies that modifying the coil dimensions, either by adjusting its r , l , or n , enables fine control over the resonance frequency of the NMR coil.

While designing the NMR coil, one of the most important aspect that strongly relates to the NMR signal intensity is the *filling factor*. This is defined as the ratio of the sample volume to the volume of the coil. A higher filling factor is achieved, when the coil dimension closely matches with the size/amount of the sample. A high filling factor ensures good rf coupling and produces a stronger NMR response.

In our NMR experiments, we have used a probe with two LC configurations for tuning and matching the probes. Figure 2.18 presents the schematic diagram of the tuning and matching configurations. The capacitors C_T and C_m are used for tuning and matching, respectively, while L denotes the inductance of the coil. Figure 2.18(a) depicts the parallel-tuned series matched circuit, which is optimized for low-frequency experiments, and Fig. 2.18(b) shows the series-tuned parallel matched circuit, which is better suited for high-frequency measurements.

Apart from tuning and matching, in a resonant circuit, we need to adjust the quality factor (Q), which determines the efficiency of the probe response, defined as

$$Q = \frac{\omega_0 L}{R}, \quad (2.149)$$

where R is the coil resistance. Increasing Q can significantly enhance the signal intensity but also prolongs the dead time, making it more difficult to detect fast-decaying signals. For optimal performance, Q is carefully tuned rather than maximized. The Q -factor can also be expressed in terms of the resonant frequency f_0 and the half-power bandwidth Δf as

$$Q = \frac{f_0}{\Delta f}. \quad (2.150)$$

In practice, to precisely measure Q during our measurements, we used a network analyzer.

All the measurements presented in this dissertation were carried out using a home-built, phase-coherent spin-echo spectrometer.

2.6 Muon-Spin Resonance (μ SR)

Muon spin resonance (μ SR) spectroscopy is a powerful microscopic technique for probing local magnetic properties in condensed matter systems. It complements other local probes such as neutron scattering and NMR by providing sensitivity to both static and dynamic magnetism at the microscopic level. While the NMR typically probes the spin dynamics in the frequency range of a few MHz ($\sim 10^{-6}$ – 10^{-8} s time window), μ SR can access the dynamics over a broader range, spanning from MHz to GHz ($\sim 10^{-5}$ – 10^{-11} s). This difference in time scales makes μ SR particularly valuable for detecting slow fluctuations which is beyond the detection limit of NMR. Moreover, the implanted muons are capable of detecting internal static fields as small as $10 \mu\text{T}$, enabling a clear distinction between magnetic LRO and persistent spin dynamics. Therefore, μ SR acts as an excellent probe to study the ground state properties of the spin systems.

In a standard μ SR experiment, polarized positive muons (μ^+) are generated through pion decay and subsequently implanted into the sample. These muons originate from proton collisions, described by the reactions:

and

where p , n , and π^+ denote the proton, neutron, and positive pion, respectively. The positive pion decays with a mean lifetime $\tau_\pi = 26$ ns into a muon and muon neutrino according to

These muons, having an intrinsic spin $S = 1/2$ which precess about the local magnetic fields until it decays via the reaction

Here, the emitted positrons anisotropically follow the spin direction of muons, as shown in Fig. 2.19(a). This unique property, the anisotropic positron emission, facilitates the measurement of the muon spin polarization as a function of time, thereby providing us an exceptionally sensitive probe of local magnetic environments.

Figure 2.19: (a) The probability of positron emission in the direction of each blue arrow is indicated by its length. Positrons are preferentially emitted along the muon spin direction (shown in a red arrow). Experimental geometries for (b) zero-field (ZF- μ SR), (c) longitudinal-field (LF- μ SR), and (d) transverse field (TF- μ SR).

μ SR experiments are commonly conducted using three configurations: zero-field (ZF),

longitudinal-field (LF), and transverse-field (TF). ZF μ SR experiments [Fig. 2.19(b)] yield information about spontaneous internal magnetic fields, crucial for distinguishing between magnetically ordered and disordered states. To probe spin dynamics and fluctuations, LF μ SR experiments are performed by applying an external magnetic field parallel to the initial muon spin direction [Fig. 2.19(c)]. Furthermore, TF μ SR measurements allow precise quantification of internal magnetic fields and their distributions. In this configuration, an external magnetic field applied perpendicular to the muon spin polarization induces precession [see Fig. 2.19(d)], with the precession frequency directly proportional to the internal magnetic field.

Muon beamlines typically comprise positron detectors positioned along the muon beam axis, one placed in front and another behind the sample. Muon counts from these detectors are used to calculate the asymmetry function, $A(t)$, defined as:

$$A(t) = \frac{N_F(t) - \alpha N_B(t)}{N_F(t) + \alpha N_B(t)}, \quad (2.155)$$

where $N_F(t)$ and $N_B(t)$ represent the number of muons detected at the forward and backward detectors, respectively. Here, α is a calibration factor specific to each sample, which is generally close to unity, this accounts for sample thickness, density, and detector efficiency. The factor α is experimentally determined through calibration measurements performed in a small TF at selected temperatures. The time dependence of the asymmetry function reflects the nature and onset temperature of magnetic ordering, which can be analyzed using various theoretical models. For our experiments, the data analysis was carried out using the MUSRFIT software suite, which was used to fit the measured asymmetry curves to the appropriate polarization functions.

Our μ SR experiments were carried out on the Flexible Advanced MuSR Environment (FLAME) spectrometers at the Swiss Muon Source ($S\mu S$) facility, Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland. Samples were wrapped with a thin copper foil ($\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ thick) (see Fig. 2.20) and mounted on a silver holder attached to a dilution refrigerator, enabling measurements down to 30 mK and

applied magnetic fields upto 3.5 T. Silver was specifically chosen due to its negligible nuclear magnetic moment, minimizing background contributions to the muon spin relaxation.

This experimental technique allowed us to gain comprehensive insights into the low-temperature spin dynamics of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, facilitating the characterization of its complex magnetic ground state, which was inaccessible via bulk measurements.

Figure 2.20: Pelletized powder sample of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ loaded on to the sample holder of FLAME spectrometer in $S\mu$ S for dilution measurements.

Chapter 3

Collinear order in spin- $\frac{5}{2}$ triangle lattice antiferromagnet $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$

In this chapter, we present the structural and magnetic properties of the spin- $\frac{5}{2}$ triangular-lattice antiferromagnet $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [186]. A comprehensive study has been carried out using powder x-ray diffraction, dc magnetic susceptibility, heat capacity, high-field magnetization, and neutron powder diffraction techniques. These experimental results are further supported by quantum monte-carlo and full diagonalization simulations.

Recently, a series of compounds with general formula $AA'M(\text{XO}_4)_2$ ($A = \text{Ba}, \text{K}, \text{Rb},$ and Sr , $A' = \text{Na}_2$ and Ag_2 , $M = \text{Mn}, \text{Ni}, \text{Co}, \text{Cr}, \text{Fe},$ and Cu , and $X = \text{P}$ and V) are reported with varying crystal structures [187–195]. Interestingly, this series of compounds are projected as low-dimensional spin systems where the superexchange takes place in an elongated path involving VO_4 or PO_4 units. Though majority of the compounds in this series are described in terms of anisotropic triangular lattice model, yet some of them are found to be exceptions. $\text{BaAg}_2\text{Cu}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ with triclinic ($P\bar{1}$) structure was initially proposed to be a spin-1/2 anisotropic triangular lattice system, due to its unequal Cu–Cu bond lengths [188]. Subsequently, the band structure calculations ruled out this proposal and established a superposition of double spin-1/2 chains: one is ferromagnetic and another is antiferromagnetic [195]. Similarly, the

Figure 3.1: (a) Crystal structure of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ showing triangular layers sculpted by the corner-shared FeO_6 octahedra and PO_4 tetrahedra. Location of Na^+ ions is also shown. (b) A section of the layer showing Fe^{3+} ions linked via PO_4 tetrahedra on an anisotropic triangular lattice.

monoclinic ($C2/c$) compound $\text{BaNa}_2\text{Cu}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ features antiferromagnetic spin-1/2 crossed chains arranged 62° with respect to each other [187]. Moreover, the signature of QSL is reported in the structurally perfect spin-1/2 TLA $\text{BaNa}_2\text{Co}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ [196] and spin-3/2 TLAs $(\text{K,Rb})\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ [194, 197], piquing further interest in this series of compounds. Thus, this series of materials serve as a cradle for novel ground states where one can tune the ground state properties by changing the chemical pressure.

In the following, we delineate a comprehensive study of the thermodynamic properties of the frustrated spin-5/2 magnet $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in which the spins are embedded in a triangular lattice. It crystallizes in a monoclinic space group ($C2/c$) and belongs to the family $AA'M(\text{XO}_4)_2$ [198, 199]. The crystal structure is presented in Fig. 3.1 where the slightly distorted FeO_6 octahedra are corner shared with distorted PO_4 tetrahedra in order to form the triangular Fe^{3+} ($3d^5$, spin-5/2) layers in the ab -plane which are stack along the c -direction. Isolated Na atoms are found between the layers. In each layer, the Fe^{3+} triangles are slightly anisotropic with

two Fe^{3+} - Fe^{3+} distances of 5.182 Å and one of 5.028 Å [Fig. 3.1(b)]. Further considering the analogy that the shortest Fe^{3+} - Fe^{3+} distance leads to a strong exchange interaction and the longer distance leads to a weak interaction, the spin lattice can also be viewed as coupled spin chains. Of course, the magnitude and sign of the interactions may vary depending on the actual path involved. Our magnetization data could be described well using the spin-5/2 isotropic triangle lattice model. It shows the onset of a magnetic ordering at $T_N \simeq 10.4$ K which is incisively detected to be a collinear AFM type. The $H - T$ phase diagram with a spin-flop (SF) transition confirms magnetic anisotropy in the compound.

3.1 Experimental details

Polycrystalline sample of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ was synthesized following the conventional solid-state reaction technique. Prior to synthesis, the precursor FePO_4 was prepared by heating stoichiometric mixture of Fe_2O_3 (Aldrich, 99.99%) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Aldrich, 99.995%) at 880 °C for 12 hours in air. In the next step, the raw materials Na_2CO_3 (Aldrich, 99.995%) and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Aldrich, 99.995%) were mixed with FePO_4 in stoichiometric ratios, grounded thoroughly, and pressed into pellets. The pellets were then sintered in an alumina crucible at 730 °C for three days in air with several intermediate grindings.

The phase purity of the sample was confirmed from the powder x-ray diffraction (XRD) performed at room temperature. For the powder XRD experiment, a PANalytical powder diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda_{\text{avg}} \simeq 1.54182$ Å) was used. The temperature-dependent powder XRD measurement was performed over the temperature range $12.5 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$ using a low-temperature attachment (Oxford Phenix) to the diffractometer. The dc magnetization (M) was measured on the powder sample using a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) (MPMS-3, Quantum Design) magnetometer. The measurements were performed in the temperature range $1.8 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 380 \text{ K}$ and in the magnetic field range $0 \leq H \leq 7 \text{ T}$. High-field magnetization was measured in pulsed magnetic field at the Dresden high magnetic field laboratory. The details of the experimental procedure are described in Refs. [200, 201].

Heat capacity as a function of temperature and magnetic field was measured on a small pellet using a Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS, Quantum Design).

Neutron powder diffraction (NPD) experiments were carried out in the temperature range $1.6 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 15 \text{ K}$ using the powder diffractometer (PD-II, $\lambda \simeq 1.2443 \text{ \AA}$) at Dhruva reactor, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre (BARC), Mumbai, India. The 1D neutron-depolarization measurements were performed using the polarized neutron spectrometer (PNS) at the Dhruva reactor, BARC, Mumbai ($\lambda \simeq 1.205 \text{ \AA}$). For this experiment, polarized neutron beam was produced and analysed using the magnetized Cu_2MnAl [reflection from (111) plane] and $\text{Co}_{0.92}\text{Fe}_{0.8}$ [reflection from (200) plane] single crystals, respectively. The two states of the polarization of incident neutron beam were achieved by a flipper placed just before the sample. The flipping ratio (R) of the neutron beam was determined by measuring the intensities of neutrons in non-spin flip and spin flip channels with the flipper on and off, respectively. Rietveld refinement of the powder XRD and NPD data was performed using FullProf software package [202].

Quantum Monte-Carlo (QMC) simulation and full diagonalization were performed using the loop and fulldiag algorithms [203] of the ALPS package [204].

3.2 Results

3.2.1 X-ray Diffraction

In order to check the structural phase transition or lattice distortion, the sample was examined by measuring XRD pattern at different temperatures. Figure 3.2 displays the powder XRD pattern at two end temperatures along with the Rietveld fits. The obtained lattice parameters from the refinement at room temperature are $a = 9.0714(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.032(1) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.8683(3) \text{ \AA}$, and $\beta = 91.44(1)^\circ$ and the unit cell volume $V_{\text{cell}} \simeq 632.96 \text{ \AA}^3$, which are in close agreement with the previous report [198]. Temperature variation of the lattice constants (a , b , and c) and V_{cell} are shown in Fig. 3.3. All of them are found to decrease systematically upon cooling down to 12.5 K, as expected. No anomaly at the temperature corresponding to the magnetic transition suggests the absence of significant magnetoelastic coupling.

Figure 3.2: Powder XRD pattern of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ measured at (a) $T = 300 \text{ K}$ and (b) $T = 12.5 \text{ K}$. The open circles are the experimental data and the solid black line is the Rietveld refined fit. The Bragg positions are indicated by green vertical bars and the bottom solid blue line indicates the difference between the experimental and calculated intensities.

Figure 3.3: The lattice constants (a , b , and c), and unit cell volume (V_{cell}) are plotted as a function of temperature from 12.5 to 300 K. The solid line in (b) represents the fit using Eq. (3.1).

Such a temperature dependence of V_{cell} is usually described well by [205]

$$V(T) = \gamma U(T)/K_0 + V_0, \quad (3.1)$$

where V_0 is the cell volume in the zero temperature limit, K_0 is the bulk modulus, and γ is the Grüneisen parameter. $U(T)$ is the internal energy, which can be derived in terms of the Debye approximation as

$$U(T) = 9nk_{\text{B}}T \left(\frac{T}{\theta_{\text{D}}}\right)^3 \int_0^{\theta_{\text{D}}/T} \frac{x^3}{e^x - 1} dx. \quad (3.2)$$

Here, n is the number of atoms in the unit cell and k_{B} is the Boltzmann constant. As shown in Fig. 3.3(b), $V_{\text{cell}}(T)$ above 12.5 K was fitted reasonably by Eq. (3.1) producing the parameters: Debye temperature $\theta_{\text{D}} \simeq 400$ K, $\gamma/K_0 \simeq 8.41 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa $^{-1}$, and $V_0 \simeq 627.6$ Å 3 .

3.2.2 Magnetization

Temperature-dependent magnetic susceptibility χ ($\equiv M/H$) of the polycrystalline $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ sample measured in 0.5 T applied field is shown in Fig. 3.4(a). The most significant feature in $\chi(T)$ is the presence of a broad maximum at $T_{\chi}^{\text{max}} \simeq 15$ K, mimicking the AFM short-range order, typical for low-dimensional spin systems. While going further below this broad maxima, a change in slope is observed at $T_{\text{N}} \simeq 10.4$ K, which marks an alteration towards an AFM long-range-order (LRO). The ordering temperature is very well evident in the $d\chi/dT$ vs T plot. To understand the nature of the magnetic ordering, $\chi(T)$ was measured at different applied fields upto 7 T [upper inset of Fig. 3.4(b)]. With increasing H , T_{N} remains unchanged upto 3 T and then moves weakly towards high temperatures above 3 T. For $H \geq 3$ T, $\chi(T)$ below T_{N} develops into a contour, which emphasizes that there is some field-induced spin canting prevailing in the system.

The zero-field cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) susceptibilities as a function of temperature were measured in a low field of 0.01 T [lower inset of Fig. 3.4(b)]. The absence of splitting between ZFC and FC $\chi(T)$ s certainly rules out the possibility of any spin-glass transition or

Figure 3.4: (a) χ as a function of temperature in an applied field $\mu_0 H = 0.5$ T. The downward arrow points to the transition temperature (T_N). The solid line represents the fit using isotropic triangular lattice model [Eq. (3.4)]. Inset: comparison of experimental data with spin-5/2 uniform chain model and isotropic triangular lattice simulated using QMC and full diagonalization (FD), respectively. (b) Inverse susceptibility $1/\chi$ vs T and the solid line represents the CW fit, as discussed in the text. Upper inset: $\chi(T)$ measured in different fields, below T_N . Lower inset: $\chi(T)$ measured under ZFC and FC conditions in $\mu_0 H = 0.01$ T.

Figure 3.5: (a) Magnetization (M) vs H measured at various temperatures from 1.8 K to 50 K. The encircled portion depicts the field induced transition regime. (b) The derivative dM/dH vs H is plotted at various temperatures from 1.8 K to 9 K in-order to highlight the field induced transition.

spin freezing at low temperatures.

For the purpose of analysis, $\chi(T)$ data in the high temperature regime were fitted using the Curie-Weiss (CW) law,

$$\chi(T) = \chi_0 + \frac{C}{T + \theta_{\text{CW}}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where χ_0 is the temperature-independent susceptibility, C is the Curie constant, and θ_{CW} is the characteristic CW temperature. The fit shown in Fig. 3.4(b) for $T \geq 150$ K yields the parameters: $\chi_0 \simeq -5.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$, $C \simeq 4.9906 \text{ cm}^3\text{K}/\text{mol}$, and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq 37.01$ K. A positive value of θ_{CW} indicates the presence of dominate AFM interactions between the Fe^{3+} ions. From the θ_{CW} and T_{N} values, we can quantify frustration by the frustration ratio, $f (= |\theta_{\text{CW}}/T_{\text{N}}|) \simeq 3.6$, which appries us that the system is moderately frustrated. The core diamagnetic susceptibility χ_{core} of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ was calculated to be $-1.23 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$ by summing the core diamagnetic susceptibilities of individual ions Na^+ , Fe^{3+} , P^{5+} , and O^{2-} [206, 207]. The Van-Vleck paramagnetic susceptibility (χ_{VV}), which arises from the second-order contribution to free energy in the presence of magnetic field was obtained by subtracting χ_{core} from χ_0 to be $\sim -4.03 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$. Further, from the value of Curie constant C , the effective moment calculated using the relation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{3k_{\text{B}}C/N_{\text{A}}}$ to be $\mu_{\text{eff}} \simeq 6.319\mu_{\text{B}}$, where k_{B} is the Boltzmann constant, μ_{B} is the Bohr magneton, and N_{A} is the Avogadro's number. For a spin-5/2 system, the spin-only effective moment is expected to be $\mu_{\text{eff}} = g\sqrt{S(S+1)}\mu_{\text{B}} \simeq 5.916 \mu_{\text{B}}$, assuming Landé g -factor $g = 2$. However, our experimental value of $\mu_{\text{eff}} \simeq 6.31 \mu_{\text{B}}$ is slightly higher than the spin-only value and corresponds to $g \simeq 2.15$. This value of g is consistently reproduced from the spin model fit discussed later, suggesting a remnant orbital contribution. In the mean-field approximation, θ_{CW} is a measure of energy scale of the total exchange interactions which is related to the exchange coupling via Eq. (1.10) [32]. Here, $z = 6$ is the number of nearest-neighbours of Fe^{3+} ion. In this way, we estimated the average exchange coupling within the triangular planes to be $J/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 2$ K.

Further, for a direct estimation of exchange coupling between the Fe^{3+} ions and to under-

stand the spin-lattice, we decomposed $\chi(T)$ into two components,

$$\chi(T) = \chi_0 + \chi_{\text{spin}}(T). \quad (3.4)$$

Here, $\chi_{\text{spin}}(T)$ typifies the intrinsic spin susceptibility which can be chosen according to the intrinsic magnetic model. As the Fe^{3+} ions in the crystal structure are arranged in triangles, we took the expression of high temperature series expansion (HTSE) of χ_{spin} for a spin-5/2 Heisenberg isotropic TLA model which has the form [208]

$$\frac{N_A \mu_B^2 g^2}{3|J|\chi_{\text{spin}}} = x + 4 + \frac{3.20}{x} - \frac{2.186}{x^2} + \frac{0.08}{x} + \frac{3.45}{x^4} - \frac{3.99}{x^5}, \quad (3.5)$$

with $x = k_B T / |J|S(S+1)$. This expression is valid for $T \geq JS(S+1)$ [209]. The solid line in Fig. 3.4(a) represents the best fit to the $\chi(T)$ data above 20 K by Eq. (3.4) resulting $\chi_0 \simeq -6.22 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$, $g \simeq 2.11$, and the average AFM exchange coupling $J/k_B \simeq 1.8 \text{ K}$. Indeed, this value of J/k_B is in good agreement with the value estimated from θ_{CW} . We also tried to fit the $\chi(T)$ data using HTSE for $\chi_{\text{spin}}(T)$ of the spin-5/2 Heisenberg 1D chain model in Eq. (3.4) [210]. The fit however did not converge giving unphysical parameters. Thus, the agreement of our experimental $\chi(T)$ data with the isotropic TLA model suggests frustrated triangular spin-lattice in the system.

To look for the field-induced transition, we measured the magnetization isotherms (M vs H) at different temperatures up to 7 T. As shown in Fig. 3.5(a), for $T < 10 \text{ K}$ a bend is observed in the intermediate magnetic fields which is the signature of a metastable field-induced transition. It is more pronounced in the dM/dH vs H plots shown in Fig. 3.5(b) where this feature is manifested in a well defined peak. As the temperature rises, one can observe that the peak is moving slightly towards higher fields and then disappears completely for $T > 9 \text{ K}$.

Further details about field induced transition and saturation magnetization can be obtained from the high field magnetization measurements. The M vs H data measured in pulsed

Figure 3.6: Magnetization (M) and its field derivative dM/dH vs H measured at $T = 1.4$ K using pulsed magnetic field in the left and right y -axes, respectively. The pulse field data are scaled with respect to the SQUID data measured up to 7 T. The dash-dotted line represents the saturation magnetization $M_{\text{sat}} \sim 5.2 \mu_B$ per Fe^{3+} ion. The sharp peaks in dM/dH vs H plot depict the spin-flop and saturation fields $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T and $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T, respectively.

magnetic field up to 50 T at $T = 1.4$ K are plotted in Fig. 3.6. The pulse field magnetization curve is quantified by scaling it with respect to the SQUID data measured up to 7 T at $T = 1.8$ K¹. It exhibits a kink at $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T, similar to that observed in Fig. 3.5, reminiscent of a spin-flop (SF) transition. Above H_{SF} , M increases almost linearly with H and develops a sharp bend towards saturation above $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T. These two critical fields are very well visualized as sharp peaks in the dM/dH vs H plot. No obvious features associated with the $1/3$ magnetization plateau is observed in the intermediate field range. In the polycrystalline sample, the random orientation of the grains with respect to the applied field direction might obscure this plateau. Above H_{sat} , M shows a slightly upward trend which may be due to a small Van-Vleck paramagnetic contribution. The linear interpolation of a straight line fit to the magnetization above H_{sat} intercepts y -axis at $M_{\text{sat}} \sim 5.25 \mu_{\text{B}}$. This saturation magnetization corresponds to the value expected for a spin-5/2 (Fe^{3+}) ion with $g = 2.1$. Further, in a spin system H_{sat} defines the energy required to overcome the AFM interactions and to polarize the spins in the direction of applied field. In particular, in a Heisenberg TLA, H_{sat} can be written in terms of the intra-layer exchange coupling as $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} = 9JS/g\mu_{\text{B}}$ [211]. Our experimental value of $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T yields an average exchange coupling of $J/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 1.95$ K which is indeed close to the value obtained from the analysis of $\chi(T)$ and θ_{CW} . A small difference can be attributed to the magnetic anisotropy present in the compound.

3.2.3 Heat Capacity

The temperature-dependent heat capacity C_{p} of the polycrystalline sample measured in zero field is shown in Fig. 3.7(a). As we go lower in temperature, C_{p} also goes down systematically and then shows a pronounced λ -type anomaly at $T_{\text{N}} \simeq 10.4$ K, illustrating the crossover to a magnetically ordered state. Typically, in high temperatures, $C_{\text{p}}(T)$ in magnetic insulators has a dominant contribution from phonon excitations (C_{ph}), whereas in low-temperatures, the

¹Note that, as the pulse-field magnetization measurements are performed adiabatically at $T = 1.4$ K, there would be an adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{ad}) with increasing field due to magnetocaloric effect (MCE). At $T = 1.4$ K, we calculated $\Delta T_{\text{ad}} \sim 0.6$ K which sets an error bar of $T = (1.4 \pm 0.6)$ K. Thus, the scaling of pulse-field data at $T = 1.4$ K with respect to the SQUID data at $T = 1.8$ K is reasonable.

Figure 3.7: (a) Heat capacity (C_p) as a function of temperature in zero applied field. The solid line represents the phonon contribution (C_{ph}) [Eq. (3.6)] while the dashed line indicates the magnetic contribution (C_{mag}). Inset: Field dependence of $C_p(T)$ around T_N . (b) C_{mag}/T and S_{mag} vs T in the left and right y -axes, respectively. Inset: C_{mag}/T vs T^2 and the solid line is the linear fit.

magnetic part of the heat capacity (C_{mag}) predominates over C_{ph} . Therefore, in magnetic systems with low energy scale of the exchange coupling, one can separate the magnetic part from the phononic part by analyzing C_p in the high temperature regime.

In order to demarcate C_{mag} from the total heat capacity C_p , the phonon contribution was first estimated by fitting the high- T data by a linear combination of one Debye and three Einstein terms [Debye-Einstein model] as [187, 212]

$$C_{\text{ph}}(T) = f_{\text{D}}C_{\text{D}}(\theta_{\text{D}}, T) + \sum_{i=1}^3 g_i C_{\text{E}_i}(\theta_{\text{E}_i}, T). \quad (3.6)$$

The first term in Eq. (3.6) represents the Debye model,

$$C_{\text{D}}(\theta_{\text{D}}, T) = 9nR \left(\frac{T}{\theta_{\text{D}}} \right)^3 \int_0^{\frac{\theta_{\text{D}}}{T}} \frac{x^4 e^x}{(e^x - 1)^2} dx, \quad (3.7)$$

where, $x = \frac{h\omega}{2\pi k_{\text{B}}T}$, ω is the frequency of oscillation, R is the universal gas constant, and θ_{D} is the characteristic Debye temperature. The flat optical modes in the phonon spectra is accounted by the second term in Eq. (3.6), known as the Einstein term

$$C_{\text{E}}(\theta_{\text{E}}, T) = 3nR \left(\frac{\theta_{\text{E}}}{T} \right)^2 \frac{e^{\left(\frac{\theta_{\text{E}}}{T}\right)}}{\left[e^{\left(\frac{\theta_{\text{E}}}{T}\right)} - 1 \right]^2}, \quad (3.8)$$

where, θ_{E} is the characteristic Einstein temperature. In Eq. (3.6) one can tentatively assign θ_{D} to the low-energy vibrations of the heavy atom (Fe) and the remaining three lighter atoms (Na, P, O) can be accounted separately by the three Einstein terms, respectively. The coefficients f_{D} , g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 are the weight factors, which take into account the number of atoms per formula unit (n) and are chosen in such a way that at high temperatures the Dulong-Petit value ($\sim 3nR$) is satisfied [213].

The zero field $C_p(T)$ data above ~ 20 K are fitted by Eq. (3.6) [see, solid curve in Fig. 3.7(a)] and the obtained parameters are $f_{\text{D}} \simeq 0.075$, $g_1 \simeq 0.205$, $g_2 \simeq 0.30$, $g_3 \simeq 0.42$, $\theta_{\text{D}} \simeq 155$ K,

$\theta_{E_1} \simeq 220$ K, $\theta_{E_2} \simeq 360$ K, and $\theta_{E_3} \simeq 930$ K. One may notice that the sum of f_D , g_1 , g_2 , and g_3 is close to one, as expected. Finally, the high- T fit was extrapolated down to 2 K and subtracted from $C_p(T)$ to get $C_{\text{mag}}(T)$ [see, Fig.3.7(a)]. Figure 3.7(b) presents $C_{\text{mag}}(T)/T$ and the corresponding magnetic entropy [$S_{\text{mag}}(T) = \int_{2\text{K}}^T \frac{C_{\text{mag}}(T')}{T'} dT'$] vs T . The obtained magnetic entropy which saturates above 50 K approaches a value $S_{\text{mag}} \simeq 14.85$ J/mol-K which is close to the expected theoretical value $S_{\text{mag}} = R \ln(2S + 1) = 14.89$ J/mol K for a $S = 5/2$ system.

$C_p(T)$ measured in different applied fields in the low temperature regime is shown in the inset of Fig. 3.7(a). No noticeable shift in T_N is apparent for a field change from 0 to 9 T. Further, well below T_N , $C_{\text{mag}}(T)$ follows a T^3 behaviour [inset of Fig. 3.7(b)], depicting the dominance of 3D magnon excitations [214, 215].

3.2.4 Neutron diffraction

Temperature evolution of the NPD pattern at different temperatures (1.6 to 15 K) are shown in Fig. 3.8. New peaks were found to appear below T_N at $Q \sim 0.6921, 0.8180, 1.1227, 1.2503,$ and 1.5455 \AA^{-1} . As we reduce the temperature, the intensity of these peaks increases gradually, suggesting the emergence of magnetic reflections. The appearance of new magnetic reflections suggests the AFM nature of the transition [216, 217]. In Fig. 3.8, the x -axis is shown in log-scale in order to highlight these magnetic reflections in the low- Q (momentum transfer vector) regime. The magnetic peaks developed below T_N can be indexed with an ordering vector $k = (1, 0, 0)$, which insinuates a commensurate magnetic ordering. The Rietveld refinement of the nuclear pattern at $T = 15$ K was performed considering monoclinic crystal structure (space group: $C2/c$). The best fit of the data [see, Fig. 3.9 (a)] yields $a = 9.1085(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 5.0532(1) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.8733(3) \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 91.32(1)^\circ$, and $V_{\text{cell}} \simeq 638.4 \text{ \AA}^3$. These obtained lattice parameters are in close agreement with the refined values from the powder XRD data at room temperature [198].

In the crystal structure of Na₃Fe(PO₄)₂, magnetic Fe-atom occupies $4a$ (0,0,0) crystallo-

Figure 3.8: (a) Temperature evolution of the neutron powder diffraction (NPD) patterns of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the low- Q regime and for temperatures below 15 K. The emergence of magnetic reflections with $k = (1,0,0)$ is evident below T_N .

graphic site. For determining the magnetic structure, the standard representational theory was used [218]. For the propagation vector $k = (1, 0, 0)$, the little group G_k can be generated using two symmetry elements, $-x, y, -z + 1/2$ and $-x, -y, -z$. Our symmetry analysis shows that the magnetic representation for $4a$ site can be written in terms of the irreducible representations (IR) as $\Gamma(4a) = 3\Gamma_1^{(1)} + 3\Gamma_3^{(1)}$. Here, both IRs (Γ_1 and Γ_3) are one-dimensional and are composed of basis vectors $\Psi_{1,2,3}$ and $\Psi_{4,5,6}$, respectively (see, Table 3.1).

The observed NPD patterns cannot be fitted with the magnetic structure corresponding to the representations Γ_1 . Whereas, the magnetic structure corresponding to the representation Γ_3 is found to be appropriate to describe the observed NPD patterns. The magnetic structure belonging to the representation Γ_3 corresponds to an antiferromagnetic structure, where moments are aligned in the bc -plane with dominant component along the crystallographic c -axis (see Fig. 3.10). Further details of the spin structure is discussed in the next section. From the magnetic structure refinement, we were able to quantify the magnetic moment values along different crystallographic directions. At the lowest temperature ($T = 1.6$ K), these values are $\mu_b \simeq 0.83 \mu_B$ and $\mu_c \simeq 1.27 \mu_B$ along the b - and c -directions, respectively. The temperature variation of total moment ($\mu = \sqrt{\mu_b^2 + \mu_c^2}$) is shown in the inset of Fig. 3.9(a). The observed reduced value of ordered moment with respect to the theoretically expected classical value of $5\mu_B$ for spin-5/2 could be attributed to the effect of low-dimensionality and magnetic frustration and/or presence of covalence effect [193, 219].

Further, to check the presence of any ferromagnetic-type correlations, we have also carried out the neutron depolarization measurements. The absence of depolarization is apparent from the flipping ratio (R) vs T plot, where R is found to be constant over the entire temperature range ($5 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$) [see, inset of Fig. 3.9(b)]. This rules out the possibility of any ferromagnetic-type correlations or spin canting in the system.

Figure 3.9: Rietveld refinement of the neutron powder diffraction data at (a) $T = 15$ K and (b) $T = 1.6$ K, considering only nuclear reflections and nuclear + magnetic reflections, respectively. The experimental data are depicted as open black circles. The red solid line represents the calculated pattern. The difference in intensities of experimental and calculated data is shown as blue solid line at the bottom. The allowed Bragg peaks corresponding to the nuclear (green) and magnetic (pink) reflections are shown as vertical bars. Inset of (a) presents the temperature variation of ordered magnetic moment, below T_N . Inset of (b) presents the variation of flipping ratio (R) in the T -range $5 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$.

Table 3.1: Irreducible representations and basis vectors for the space group $C2/c$ with propagation vector $k = (1,0,0)$, obtained using the Baslreps software. The atoms are defined according to Fe1: $(0, 0, 0)$ and Fe2: $(0, 0, 0.5)$.

Basis vector components for $k = (1,0,0)$			
IR	Basis Vectors	Fe1	Fe2
Γ_1	Ψ_1	(1 0 0)	(-1 0 0)
	Ψ_2	(0 1 0)	(0 1 0)
	Ψ_3	(0 0 1)	(0 0 -1)
Γ_3	Ψ_4	(1 0 0)	(1 0 0)
	Ψ_5	(0 1 0)	(0 -1 0)
	Ψ_6	(0 0 1)	(0 0 1)

Figure 3.10: (a) Spin structure of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ derived from the neutron powder diffraction at $T = 1.6$ K. (b) A section of the triangular layer (ab -plane) showing the spin orientation and exchange interactions.

3.3 Discussion and Summary

Theoretically, for a spin-5/2 chain system, the broad maxima in $\chi(T)$ is expected at $k_B T_\chi^{\max}/J = 10.6$ [220]. The broad maximum in our experimental data appears at $T_\chi^{\max} \simeq 15$ K which corresponds to the intra-chain coupling of $J/k_B \simeq 1.41$ K. In order to reproduce the overall shape of the $\chi(T)$ plot, we simulated the data using QMC technique, assuming a spin-chain model with $S = 5/2$ and $J/k_B \simeq 1.41$ K. As depicted in the inset of Fig. 3.4(a), the simulated data show a significant deviation from the experimental data, discarding the possibility of spin-chain physics. On the other hand, the fit assuming isotropic triangular lattice [Eq. (3.4)] reproduces the experimental $\chi(T)$ data very well in the high temperature regime, despite a small spatial anisotropy. As a further test for the TLA model, we performed the full diagonalization for a spin-5/2 isotropic TLA with $J/k_B \simeq 1.8$ K [obtained from the $\chi(T)$ analysis]. As evident from the inset of Fig. 3.4(a), the simulated data using full diagonalization superimpose the experimental data, above T_χ^{\max} . This confirms that the spin-lattice in $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ behaves more of a 2D triangular lattice, rather than a 1D spin-chain.

This compound orders antiferromagnetically below $T_N \simeq 10.4$ K which is clear from the appearance of magnetic reflections in the NPD pattern, λ -type anomaly in $C_p(T)$, and slope change in $\chi(T)$. The magnetic structure refined from the NPD data is shown in Fig. 3.10 which demonstrates a collinear AFM ordering. The spins are coupled ferromagnetically (J_1) along the b -axis or in the [100] plane which is the direction of the shortest Fe^{3+} - Fe^{3+} distance. The AFM interchain coupling (J_2) ties the chains into a 2D anisotropic triangular layer in the ab -plane. Alternatively, one can visualize it as AFM cross chains running along the [110] and [-110] directions which are coupled ferromagnetically in the ab -plane. Though a non-collinear 120° structure is understood as a hallmark of TLA, some compounds tend to deviate from this spin structure either due to anisotropy or inter-layer coupling [221, 222].

The crystal symmetry plays a key role in deciding the ground states of the compounds in the $AA'M(\text{XO}_4)_2$ family. The correspondence between crystal symmetry and exchange couplings

is well demonstrated for the series $A\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ ($A = \text{Ag}, \text{K}, \text{Rb}$) [197]. Here, replacement of A site induces a symmetry change in the CrO_6 octahedra. Therefore, $\text{Ag}_3\text{Cr}(\text{VO}_4)_2$ (space group: $C2/c$) is a distorted/anisotropic TLA with a collinear AFM ordering below $T_N \simeq 10$ K, whereas the other compounds ($A = \text{K}, \text{Rb}$) with higher symmetry (space group: $P\bar{3}$) are undistorted/isotropic TLAs and are reported show signature of QSL [197]. Several other compounds with higher symmetry in this series also feature isotropic triangular lattices [158, 189, 193, 194, 197]. As pointed out in Fig. 3.1(b), for $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, the PO_4 tetrahedra which acts as a medium of interaction among the Fe^{3+} ions is distorted where the P-O bond distance varies from 1.50 Å to 1.56 Å and the $\angle O-P-O$ angles are also different. These give rise to non-equivalent exchange interactions along the edges of the triangle. The anisotropic interactions can also be assessed from the deviation of O-Fe-O bond angles from 90° , typically expected for an isotropic triangular lattice formed by undistorted FeO_6 octahedra. It is also to be noted that despite the shortest $\text{Fe}^{3+}\text{-Fe}^{3+}$ distance, the interaction along the [100] direction is FM. A close inspection of the bond angles reveals that $\angle O-P-O$ along the [100] direction has the smallest value of 97.13° compared to the other directions which possibly favours parallel alignment. The collinear order in $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ may thus be attributed to the distortion in FeO_6 octahedra and inter-layer coupling along the stacking c -direction, similar to $\text{Ag}_3\text{Cr}(\text{VO}_4)_2$.

The obtained T_N from $\chi(T)$ and $C_p(T)$ data and the critical field (H_{SF}) corresponding to the metastable transition obtained from the magnetic isotherms are summarized in Fig. 3.11 as a $H-T$ phase diagram. It displays three well defined regions represented as paramagnetic (PM), antiferromagnetic (AFM), and spin-flop (SF) phases. Majority of TLAs feature a magnetization plateau at $1/3$ of the saturation magnetization in the magnetic isotherms [80, 160, 223–225], where the system evolves from a 120° AFM order, which is the true ground state of a Heisenberg TLA [56] to a up-up-down (uud) phase. The uud phase is stabilized by the magnetic field that introduces axial (Ising) anisotropy and disfavors the noncollinear 120° order. Though our low temperature isotherms illustrate a plateau but it is well below the $1/3$ of the saturation

Figure 3.11: $H - T$ phase diagram of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ drawn from the magnetic isotherm, $\chi(T)$, and $C_p(T)$ measurements. H_{SF} represents the critical field at which the SF transition takes place. The point $(T_{\text{Bc}}, H_{\text{Bc}})$ denotes the bi-critical point, where the SF transition ends.

magnetization [104]. Further, the magnetic ordering in zero field is a collinear AFM order rather than a noncollinear 120° order. Hence, the $1/3$ magnetization plateau is overruled. Moreover, the presence of a easy-plane (XY-type) anisotropy often triggers field emergent phenomenon like SF transition [226] above a critical field H_{SF} , where the moments flip from parallel to perpendicular direction with respect to the applied field. Thus, the metastable/SF transition in $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ can be attributed to the easy-plane anisotropy in the compound. $\text{Na}_2\text{BaMnV}_2\text{O}_8$, which belongs to the same series also shows a SF transition at low temperatures [191]. Similar phase diagram is also reported previously in the frustrated spin chain compounds $\text{SrCuTe}_2\text{O}_6$ and $\alpha\text{-Cu}_2\text{As}_2\text{O}_7$ [227, 228].

In summary, we have demonstrated the ground state properties of the frustrated magnet $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$. Based on the structural data one may anticipate a small anisotropy in the exchange couplings in the triangular unit. However, the analysis of our experimental data emphasizes that the system behaves more like a spin- $5/2$ isotropic triangular lattice. It stabilizes in a collinear antiferromagnetic ordering below T_N likely due to moderate inter-layer coupling. The occurrence of a field induced SF transition in the low temperature magnetic isotherms insinuates the presence of XY-type anisotropy. A comparison with other members of the $AA'M(\text{XO}_4)_2$ family reveals that the bond distances between metal ions and the corresponding angles become more anisotropic with reduced symmetry, leading to a potential structural complexity and exotic ground states.

Chapter 4

Double magnetic transitions and exotic field induced phase in the triangular lattice antiferromagnets

$\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_9$

In this chapter, we report the structural and magnetic properties of the spin-orbit entangled TLAFs $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ [115]. Polycrystalline samples were investigated by powder x-ray diffraction with Rietveld refinement, dc magnetic susceptibility, high-field magnetization up to 60 T, and heat capacity measurements down to 0.1 K. This comprehensive study reveals successive magnetic transitions in zero-field and field-induced phases that are characteristic of frustrated $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ triangular-lattice systems.

$\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ is reported to crystallize in a monoclinic structure with space group $P2_1/c$ [229, 230]. Its crystal structure is illustrated in Fig. 4.1. There are two inequivalent Co atoms residing at the Co(1) $2a(0,0,0)$ and Co(2) $2d(1/2,1/2,0)$ sites, respectively which are coordinated with O atoms forming slightly distorted CoO_6 octahedra. Two-dimensional (2D) triangular layers are formed by the corner sharing of magnetic CoO_6 and non-magnetic NbO_6 octahedra in the

Figure 4.1: (a) A 3D view of the crystal structure of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$. The dashed lines guide the triangular layers composed of corner shared CoO_6 and NbO_6 octahedra. The Co(1)O_6 and Co(2)O_6 octahedra are shown in different colours. (b) A section of the triangular layer that depicts nearly parallel edge-shared arrangement of CoO_6 octahedra and presents the honeycomb lattice, after removing NbO_6 octahedra.

ab-plane. Figure 4.1(b) presents nearly parallel edge-sharing CoO_6 octahedra (NbO_6 omitted) displaying possible superimposed honeycomb lattices. The non-magnetic Sr atoms are located at the interstitial positions. In each layer, an isosceles triangular unit is made up of either one $\text{Co}(1)^{2+}$ and two $\text{Co}(2)^{2+}$ or two $\text{Co}(1)^{2+}$ and one $\text{Co}(2)^{2+}$ ions. Moreover, the Co^{2+} triangular layers are arranged in an *AAA*-type stacking perpendicular to the *c*-axis which results in minuscule inter-layer frustration [231]. Magnetic measurements reveal double transitions at low temperatures typical for compounds with easy-axis anisotropy. Despite structural similarity, $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ exhibits a $1/3$ magnetization plateau which is absent for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. Further, $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ manifests an extended field induced critical regime where the ground state appears to be of QSL type while this regime is found to be narrow for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$.

4.1 Experimental details

Polycrystalline samples of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ were synthesized by the traditional solid-state reaction method. Stoichiometric amount of SrCO_3 (99.99%, Sigma Aldrich), CoO (99.999%, Sigma Aldrich), and $\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_5/\text{Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ (99.999%, Sigma Aldrich) were mixed and ground thoroughly for three hours. The mixtures were pressed into disc shaped pellets and sintered at 1100°C for 24 hours. In the next step, the heat treatment was repeated at 1250°C for 24 hours after regrinding and re-pelletization. The powder x-ray diffraction (XRD) was recorded using a PANalytical powder diffractometer (CuK_α radiation, $\lambda = 1.54182 \text{ \AA}$) at room temperature. Rietveld refinement of the powder XRD data for both the compounds was carried out using the FULLPROF software package [202] to check the phase purity of the samples and to calculate the structural parameters.

The *dc* magnetization (M) measurement was performed with a superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID, MPMS-3, Quantum Design) magnetometer as a function of temperature ($1.8 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 350 \text{ K}$) and magnetic field ($0 \leq H \leq 7 \text{ T}$). High-field magnetization $M(H)$ was measured in a pulsed magnetic field at the Dresden High Magnetic Field Laboratory [200,201]. Heat capacity (C_P) as a function of T ($0.1 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$) and H ($0 \leq H \leq 9 \text{ T}$)

was measured using thermal relaxation technique in a physical property measurement system (PPMS, Evercool-II, Quantum Design). For $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, the measurements were performed down to 0.4 K and 0.1 K using ^3He and dilution inserts, respectively in PPMS.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 X-ray Diffraction

Table 4.1: Lattice parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the room temperature powder XRD data of $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_9$ (Monoclinic, $P2_1/c$).

Parameters	$\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$	$\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$
a (Å)	9.7867(5)	9.7790(5)
b (Å)	5.6460(2)	5.6643(4)
c (Å)	17.0057(4)	16.957(1)
β (°)	125.32(3)	125.20(3)
V_{cell} (Å ³)	766.67(5)	767.46(8)
Bragg R-factor	2.2	11
Rf-factor	6.5	6.0
χ^2	2.5	7.7
Co(1) - Co(1) (Å)	5.6460(1)	5.6644(5)
Co(2) - Co(2) (Å)	5.6460(1)	5.6644(5)
Co(1) - Co(2) (Å)	5.6493(3)	5.6505(3)

Powder XRD data collected at room temperature for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ are shown in Fig. 4.2(a) and (b), respectively. With the help of Rietveld refinement, all the peaks could be modeled assuming monoclinic structure ($P2_1/c$) for both the compounds and taking initial parameters from Refs. [229, 230]. This suggests that the new compound obtained by replacing Nb by Ta also stabilizes in the same crystal structure. During refinement, the positions of oxygen atoms for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ couldn't be refined and kept fixed to the values of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$. For a comparison, the refined lattice parameters and atomic positions for both the compounds are tabulated in Table 4.1 and 4.2, respectively. The obtained structural parameters for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ are in close agreement with the previous reports [229, 230].

Upon replacing Nb by Ta, the lattice constants a and c are found to decrease while b

Figure 4.2: Room temperature powder XRD patterns of (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The black circles show the XRD data and the red line represents the calculated pattern. The blue small vertical lines represent the Bragg positions. The green line at the bottom represents the difference between observed and calculated intensities.

Table 4.2: Atomic positions obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the room temperature powder XRD data of $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_9$.

Atom	Wyckoff	x	y	z	Occ.
Sr1	4e	0.2500	0.500	0.08321(6)	1.0
		0.2500	0.500	0.0803(7)	1.0
Sr2	4e	0.7500	0.000	0.08262(3)	1.0
		0.7500	0.000	0.07348(3)	1.0
Sr3	4e	0.2500	0.00	0.2500	1.0
		0.2500	0.00	0.2500	1.0
Co1	2a	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.5
		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.5
Co2	2d	0.500	0.500	0.000	0.5
		0.500	0.500	0.000	0.5
Nb1	4e	0.50949(5)	0.500	0.33735(3)	1.0
Ta1		0.51011(3)	0.500	0.33661(7)	1.0
Nb2	4e	0.00710(4)	0.500	0.16336(8)	1.0
Ta2		0.00975(4)	0.500	0.16713(6)	1.0
O1	4e	0.97200(3)	0.74250(1)	0.2430(6)	1.0
		0.97200(3)	0.74250(1)	0.2430(6)	1.0
O2	4e	0.5260(3)	0.78710(5)	0.27160(6)	1.0
		0.5260(3)	0.78710(5)	0.27160(6)	1.0
O3	4e	0.2500(0)	0.5528(4)	0.26260(2)	1.0
		0.2500(0)	0.5528(4)	0.26260(2)	1.0
O4	4e	0.97210(9)	0.7330(7)	0.90670(4)	1.0
		0.97210(9)	0.7330(7)	0.90670(4)	1.0
O5	4e	0.0279(6)	0.2518(6)	0.92020(5)	1.0
		0.0279(6)	0.2518(6)	0.92020(5)	1.0
O6	4e	0.4721(6)	0.2777(0)	0.89190(1)	1.0
		0.4721(6)	0.2777(0)	0.89190(1)	1.0
O7	4e	0.52790(9)	0.79650(6)	0.9352(5)	1.0
		0.52790(9)	0.79650(6)	0.9352(5)	1.0
O8	4e	0.74060(8)	0.04280(5)	0.9110(3)	1.0
		0.74060(8)	0.04280(5)	0.9110(3)	1.0
O9	4e	0.24060(7)	0.5428(0)	0.90780(3)	1.0
		0.24060(7)	0.5428(0)	0.90780(3)	1.0

increases. This results in an overall increase in the unit cell volume (V_{cell}). In the crystal structure, all the magnetic Co^{2+} layers are equally spaced with an inter-layer separation of $\sim 17.0057 \text{ \AA}$ and $\sim 16.9574 \text{ \AA}$ for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively.

4.2.2 Magnetization

Temperature dependent magnetic susceptibility χ ($\equiv M/H$) of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ measured in a magnetic field of $H = 10 \text{ kOe}$ is shown in Fig. 4.3(a) and (b), respectively. As the temperature is lowered, $\chi(T)$ increases in a Curie-Weiss (CW) manner. No clear indication of any magnetic long-range ordering (LRO) is observed down to 2 K. When the inverse susceptibility ($1/\chi$) is plotted against temperature, it exhibits a linear behaviour at high temperatures and a change in slope at around $\sim 50 \text{ K}$. This change in slope is a possible indication of the crossover of spin state of Co^{2+} from high temperature $S = 3/2$ state to an effective $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ ground state [166, 168, 232, 233]. In order to extract the magnetic parameters, $1/\chi$ in the low and high temperature linear regions is fitted by the modified CW law using Eq. (3.3).

The fit in high temperature ($T > 200 \text{ K}$) range yields ($\chi_0 \simeq 5.315 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$, $C \simeq 3.37 \text{ cm}^3\text{K}/\text{mol}$, and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -24 \text{ K}$) and ($\chi_0 \simeq 2.84 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$, $C \simeq 3.24 \text{ cm}^3\text{K}/\text{mol}$, and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -21.2 \text{ K}$) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. These values of C correspond to an effective moment of $\mu_{\text{eff}} \simeq 5.2 \mu_{\text{B}}$ and $\sim 5.1 \mu_{\text{B}}$, respectively which are close to the expected spin-only value for a $S = 3/2 \text{ Co}^{2+}$ ion.

Similarly, the CW fit [Eq. (3.3)] to the $1/\chi$ data was performed in the low temperature region by varying the fitting range between 20 K and 60 K. The obtained parameters are [$C \simeq 1.85(5) \text{ cm}^3\text{K}/\text{mol}$ and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -7.5(5) \text{ K}$] and [$C \simeq 1.93(3) \text{ cm}^3\text{K}/\text{mol}$ and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -8(1) \text{ K}$], for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. During the fitting procedure, χ_0 was fixed to the Van-Vleck susceptibility (χ_{VV}) obtained from the high-field magnetization data (discussed later). To visualize the low temperature linear behaviour, we have plotted $1/(\chi - \chi_{\text{VV}})$ vs T in the right y -axis for both the compounds. These values of C provide the effective magnetic moment of $\mu_{\text{eff}} \simeq 3.84(1) \mu_{\text{B}}$ and $3.92(2) \mu_{\text{B}}$ for Nb and Ta compounds, respectively which

Figure 4.3: χ vs T measured in $\mu_0 H = 1$ T for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. $1/\chi$ after subtracting χ_{VV} is plotted as a function of T in the right y -axis to emphasize the low- T linear portion. Solid line represents the Curie-Weiss fit in the low temperature linear regime, as discussed in the text.

are indeed close to the value expected for $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$, assuming $g = 4$. Such a large value of g is not unusual and is typically observed for Co^{2+} systems from the electron-spin-resonance (ESR) experiments due to dominant spin-orbit coupling, at low temperatures [158, 160]. The negative value of θ_{CW} indicates that the dominant interaction between the spins is AFM in nature. In a spin system, θ_{CW} is a measure of the exchange coupling and is given by Eq. (1.10), with the Heisenberg Hamiltonian $H = J \sum S_i \cdot S_j$ [32]. As both the compounds are having the triangular geometry, we have $z = 6$. Thus, using the value of θ_{CW} , z , and j_{eff} in place of S in the above expression, we obtained $J/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 5$ K and 5.3 K for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively.

Further validation of the $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ ground state and the estimation of exchange coupling were obtained from the high-field magnetization data. The high-field magnetization measured as a function of field upto 60 T using the pulsed magnetic field at the base temperature of $T = 1.4$ K is shown in Fig. 4.4(a) and (b) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. The pulsed field data are scaled with respect to the magnetization data measured in the SQUID magnetometer up to 7 T at $T = 1.8$ K. For $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, M increases linearly with H and then shows a sharp bend at the saturation field $H_{\text{S}} \simeq 7.2$ T. Such a sharp bend in the powder sample demonstrates isotropic g -factor and/or exchange interaction, as in the case of $\text{Ba}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb},\text{Sb})_2\text{O}_9$ [160, 234]. For $H > 8$ T, though it shows the tendency of saturation, still there is a slow increase. This slow increase of magnetization above H_{S} is attributed to the temperature independent Van-Vleck paramagnetism associated with the Co^{2+} ion in the non-cubic environment [13]. The slope of a linear fit for $H > 15$ T and its intercept in the y -axis result in the Van-Vleck paramagnetic susceptibility $\chi_{\text{VV}} \simeq 7.32 \times 10^{-3}$ cm³/mol and saturation magnetization $M_{\text{S}} \simeq 2.13$ $\mu_{\text{B}}/\text{Co}^{2+}$, respectively. Using this value of M_{S} , the g -factor ($M_{\text{S}} = gS\mu_{\text{B}}$) is calculated to be $g \simeq 4.26$, assuming $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$. Similar g -value is also reported for other Co^{2+} based $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs [13, 87, 88, 168]. The corrected magnetization (M_{corr}) after subtracting the Van-Vleck contribution is also plotted in the same graph. To precisely pinpoint the saturation field we have plotted the derivative dM_{corr}/dH vs H in the right y -axis. The curve exhibits a valley at $H \simeq 2$ T which corresponds to $1/3$ of M_{S} and then a sharp drop at $\mu_0 H_{\text{S}} \simeq 7.2$ T (or, a slope

Figure 4.4: Magnetization (M) vs H measured at $T = 1.4$ K using pulsed magnetic field for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The dash-dotted line represents the linear fit to the data in high fields which is extrapolated down to zero field to obtain the Van-Vleck magnetization. The corrected magnetization M_{corr} after the subtraction of Van-Vleck contribution is also plotted vs H . The dashed lines mark the critical fields. dM_{corr}/dH vs H is plotted in the right y -axis to highlight the features at the critical fields.

change in the M_{corr} vs H curve) indicating the saturation field or critical field above which the spin system attains the fully polarized state [13].

Unlike $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, the magnetic behaviour of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ is found to be somewhat different. Magnetization shows a broad bend between two critical fields $\mu_0 H_{S1} \simeq 3.6$ T and $\mu_0 H_{S2} \simeq 10.5$ T. Above H_{S2} , the magnetization saturates, yet there is a slow increase, similar to $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$. A straight line fit above 20 T yields $\chi_{\text{VV}} \simeq 7.2 \times 10^{-3}$ cm³/mol and $M_S \simeq 1.8 \mu_{\text{B}}/\text{Co}^{2+}$. This value of M_S corresponds to $g \simeq 3.6$ with $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$. The Van-Vleck corrected magnetization M_{corr} and its derivative dM_{corr}/dH as a function of H are plotted in the left and right y -axes, respectively in Fig. 4.4(b) which show pronounced features at H_{S1} and H_{S2} . These features are quite different from the broad contour expected due to g -factor anisotropy. This is an indication of the existence of an exotic field-induced state between H_{S1} and H_{S2} , similar to $\text{Na}_2\text{Co}_2\text{TeO}_6$ [153]. No obvious feature is seen at the field corresponding to the 1/3 magnetization.

The saturation field defines the energy required to overcome the antiferromagnetic exchange energy and polarize the spins in the direction of magnetic field. In particular, in a Heisenberg TLAF, H_S can be written in terms of the intralayer exchange coupling as $\mu_0 H_s = 9JS/g\mu_{\text{B}}$ [211]. For $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, our experimental value of $\mu_0 H_s \simeq 7.2$ T yields an average exchange coupling of $J/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 4.7$ K. Similarly, for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, $\mu_0 H_{S2} \simeq 10.5$ T gives $J/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 5.8$ K. These values of J/k_{B} are in reasonable agreement with the ones obtained from the analysis of θ_{CW} . The slight difference in magnitude can be attributed to the magnetic anisotropy present in the compounds.

Heisenberg TLAFs typically show a 1/3 magnetization plateau in an intermediate field range where the spins evolve from a conventional 120° spin structure to a uud state [104, 235, 236]. Though a weak anomaly is visible for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ but it is completely absent for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. Please note that, since our $M(H)$ is measured at $T = 1.4$ K, which is above T_{N1} , the impact of magnetic anisotropy would be minimal. Therefore, $M(H)$ measurements well below T_{N2} may reveal these features more clearly. In order to confirm the absence of 1/3 plateau in

Figure 4.5: M vs H measured at different temperatures for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. dM/dH vs H is plotted on the right y -axis.

$\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, we measured a few $M(H)$ curves below and above T_{N1} and T_{N2} . Figure 4.5 depicts magnetic isotherms measured using SQUID magnetometer in the ^3He temperatures. At $T = 0.4$ K, it shows a well-defined feature in the dM/dH vs H curve at around $\mu_0 H_{S1} \sim 3$ T but with no $1/3$ plateau which could be due to the polycrystalline nature of the sample where random orientation of the crystallites average out this effect.

4.2.3 Heat Capacity

To delineate the low-energy excitations, $C_p(T)$ measured in different applied fields is shown in Fig. 4.6(a) and (b) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. The overall temperature variation of C_p for both the compounds is found to be nearly same. In zero-field, as the temperature decreases, C_p decreases monotonically and below ~ 10 K it displays a weak and broad maximum, a possible indication of short-range ordering due to two-dimensionality of the spin-lattice. With further decrease in temperature, two well defined peaks appear at $T_{N1} \simeq 1.47$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 1.22$ K for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and at $T_{N1} \simeq 0.88$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 0.67$ K for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, indicating the onset of two successive magnetic transitions at low temperatures. When external

Figure 4.6: Temperature dependent heat capacity [$C_p(T)$] measured in different magnetic fields for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The red dash-dotted line represents the lattice heat capacity using Eq. (4.1). The black solid lines are the power law and power law + nuclear Schottky fits to the low- T data of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. The dashed line in (b) marks the power law with $\alpha = 2$. Lower insets: Variation of α and γ with H in the left and right y -axes, respectively, obtained from the low temperature data fit. Upper inset in (b) is the plot of A vs H^2 with solid line being a linear fit.

magnetic field is applied the height of the peaks is reduced substantially and the peak positions shift towards low temperatures. At higher fields, both the transition peaks are merged into a broad peak and gradually vanishes from the measurement window. This reflects AFM nature of both the transitions. In addition, as the field increases, the broad maxima initially shifts towards low temperatures as expected for a short-range magnetic order. For higher fields, the position of the maxima shifts in the reverse direction (to high temperatures), its height increases, and shows a drastic broadening, reminiscent of a Schottky anomaly due to CEF splitting. Furthermore, the zero-field $C_p(T)$ of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ shows an upturn below ~ 0.2 K which moves towards high temperatures with increasing field. This is a typical behaviour of nuclear Schottky arising due to a quadrupole splitting of ^{59}Co ($I = 7/2$) nuclear levels [237, 238].

In a magnetic insulator, C_p in zero-field has three major contributions: lattice heat capacity (C_{ph}) due to phonons which usually dominates at high temperatures, magnetic heat capacity (C_{mag}) due to spins which becomes predominant at low temperatures, and the nuclear Schottky contribution (C_{n}) which is effective only at very low temperatures (below $\sim 10^{-2}$ K). In the absence of a non-magnetic analogue, $C_{\text{ph}}(T)$ is evaluated by fitting $C_p(T)$ in the high temperature region by a linear combination of one Debye and four Einstein terms [187]

$$C_{\text{ph}}(T) = f_{\text{D}}C_{\text{D}}(\theta_{\text{D}}, T) + \sum_{i=1}^4 g_i C_{\text{E}_i}(\theta_{\text{E}_i}, T). \quad (4.1)$$

The first term in Eq. (4.1) is the Debye model as mentioned in Eq. (3.7) and θ_{D} is the characteristic Debye temperature. The flat optical modes in the phonon spectra are accounted for by the second term in Eq. (4.1), called the Einstein term [Eq. (3.8)], where θ_{E} is the characteristic Einstein temperature. The coefficients f_{D} , g_1 , g_2 , g_3 , and g_4 are the weight factors, which take into account the number of atoms per formula unit (n) and are chosen in such a way that $f_{\text{D}} + g_1 + g_2 + g_3 + g_4 = 1$ and the Dulong-Petit value ($\sim 3nR$) is satisfied at high temperatures. The zero-field $C_p(T)$ above 40 K is fitted by Eq. (4.1) and the obtained fitting parameters are ($f_{\text{D}} \simeq 0.066$, $g_1 \simeq 0.066$, $g_2 \simeq 0.20$, $g_3 \simeq 0.13$, $g_4 \simeq 0.533$, $\theta_{\text{D}} \simeq 178$ K,

Figure 4.7: Difference in heat capacity $\Delta C (= C_p - C_{\text{ph}} - C_n)$ vs T in different magnetic fields for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. The solid lines are the fits using Eq. (4.2). Inset of (b) shows the plot of Δ/k_B and n as a function of H for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ in the left and right y -axes, respectively. The change in magnetic entropy ΔS vs T in different magnetic fields for (c) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (d) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$.

$\theta_{E1} \simeq 117$ K, $\theta_{E2} \simeq 206$ K, $\theta_{E3} \simeq 328$ K and $\theta_{E4} \simeq 520$ K) and ($f_D \simeq 0.066$, $g_1 \simeq 0.066$, $g_2 \simeq 0.20$, $g_3 \simeq 0.13$, $g_4 \simeq 0.533$, $\theta_D \simeq 163$ K, $\theta_{E1} \simeq 117$ K, $\theta_{E2} \simeq 195$ K, $\theta_{E3} \simeq 294$ K and $\theta_{E4} \simeq 490$ K) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. The fit was extrapolated down to the lowest measured temperature (see Fig. 4.6) to obtain $C_{\text{ph}}(T)$. The estimation of C_{n} is discussed later. The magnetic and/or Schottky contributions, ΔC , obtained by subtracting C_{ph} and C_{n} from total C_{p} are plotted as a function of T for different fields in Fig. 4.7(a) and (b) for the Nb and Ta compounds, respectively. The respective change in magnetic entropies evaluated by integrating $\Delta C/T$ with respect to T [i.e. $\Delta S = \int_0^T \frac{\Delta C(T')}{T'} dT'$] for different fields are shown in Fig. 4.7(c) and (d). The saturation value of ΔS approaches $R \ln 2$ above ~ 30 K irrespective of the applied field for both the compounds, further evidencing $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ ground state for Co^{2+} .

$\Delta C(T)$ in different fields can be fitted by the following two-level Schottky function

$$C_{\text{S}} = n_{\text{S}} R \left(\frac{\Delta}{k_{\text{B}} T} \right)^2 \frac{e^{-\frac{\Delta}{k_{\text{B}} T}}}{\left(1 + e^{-\frac{\Delta}{k_{\text{B}} T}} \right)^2}, \quad (4.2)$$

where n_{S} is the number of free spins per formula unit contributing to the Schottky behaviour and Δ/k_{B} is the Zeeman gap in magnetic fields. We fitted the data in different magnetic fields by Eq. (4.2) making n and Δ/k_{B} as fitting parameters [Fig. 4.7(a) and (b)]. The fit reproduces the experimental data reasonably well, especially in the broad maximum regime. However, the deviation in the high temperature regime can be ascribed to the unreliable subtraction of phonon contribution and the presence of magnetic contribution. The obtained Δ/k_{B} and n are plotted as a function of field in the inset of Fig. 4.7(b) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$. With increasing H , n increases systematically suggesting the excitation of more free spins to the higher energy levels. It is expected to reach the maximum value (~ 1) in the fully polarized state, above $H_{\text{S}2} \simeq 10.5$ T. Similarly, Δ/k_{B} varies linearly with H . Taking the value of $\Delta/k_{\text{B}} \simeq 21.65$ K at $H = 9$ T which is close to the saturation field, we obtained $g \simeq 3.58$. This value of g is indeed

close to the one obtained from the magnetization analysis. This further elucidates that the Schottky effect in heat capacity is arising from the Co^{2+} Kramers' doublets with $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$.

4.3 Discussion

For both the compounds, double magnetic transitions are observed at T_{N1} and T_{N2} ($T_{\text{N2}} < T_{\text{N1}}$) in zero-field. It is predicted that double transitions can occur in TLAFs when the magnetic anisotropy is of easy-axis type, while the TLAFs with easy-plane type anisotropy may show only single transition [63, 94, 239, 240]. On lowering the temperature, the collinear *wud* state appears before 120° state in TLAFs with easy-axis anisotropy. When magnetic field is applied, an additional high-field 2:1 canted phase is also stabilized [104]. The temperature range of the intermediate phase $(T_{\text{N1}} - T_{\text{N2}})/T_{\text{N1}}$ reflects the relative strength of easy-axis anisotropy with respect to the isotropic intralayer coupling. Similar type of double transitions are reported for $\text{Ba}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb}, \text{Ta}, \text{Sb})_2\text{O}_9$ and some other compounds [87, 88, 164, 164, 234]. Thus, the two consecutive magnetic transitions at low temperatures is attributed to the easy-axis anisotropy in both our compounds and the 120° ordering below T_{N2} is preceded by a collinear order between T_{N1} and T_{N2} . The observed narrow temperature regime between T_{N1} and T_{N2} in both the compounds suggests considerably weak anisotropy compared to the isotropic exchange coupling in the Hamiltonian [13]. This implies that these compounds are more close to Heisenberg model in contrast to strong anisotropy anticipated for Co-based compounds [241, 242] and the local environment of Co^{2+} is close to a cubic symmetry as in KCoF_3 and $\text{Ba}_3\text{CoSb}_2\text{O}_9$ [13]. Recent theoretical studies claim that the Heisenberg model on a triangular lattice with no anisotropy can also show double phase transition [104]. It is also suggested that the transition from *wud* to 120° state (at T_{N2}) can be described by the conventional Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless (BKT) universality class. The magnetic ($T - H$) phase diagram constructed using the transition temperatures from $C_p(T)$ and saturation fields from the magnetization data are presented in Figs. 4.8(a) and (b) for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. Both the compounds exhibit two common phase regimes I and II known to be 120° and collinear spin

Figure 4.8: T vs H phase diagram for (a) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and (b) $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ constructed using the heat capacity and magnetization data. The exotic field induced regime (III) between H_{S1} and H_{S2} for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ is highlighted in a different color.

states, respectively, as typically observed in majority of the TLAFs. On increasing field, both the transitions are merged into one and are expected to approach zero temperature at around ~ 7 T for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and ~ 3 T for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, respectively. These fields are very close to their respective saturation fields.

The most striking difference between these two compounds is that $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ shows the appearance of an exotic phase in an extended field range [regime III in Fig. 4.8(b)] while for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ this phase is either absent or exists over a narrow field range. In order to understand the peculiar behaviour in the magnetization data, we fitted $C_p(T)$ in the low temperature regime by a power law of the form $C_p = \gamma T^\alpha$ for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$. To accommodate the low- T upturn, $C_p(T)$ data of $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ were fitted with a sum of A/T^2 and γT^α from the lowest temperature to 1 K [8]. Here, A/T^2 accounts for the high temperature part of the nuclear Schottky (C_n) anomaly, which is nothing but the high temperature approximation of Eq. (4.2) [212]. The constant A is related to the nuclear level splitting Δ (both quadrupolar and Zeeman) with $A \propto \Delta^2$ for $T \gg \Delta$. A is found to increase quadratically with H [upper inset of Fig. 4.6(b)], which is consistent with the theoretical prediction [238].

The obtained values of γ and α are plotted against H in the lower insets of the respective figures. For $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, the value of α is found to be close to 3 for all the measured fields [inset of Fig. 4.6(a)], as expected in a 3D AFM ordered state. Only at $H = 9$ T which is well above H_S , the fitted parameters were not reliable, possibly because of large scattering in the low temperature data and low heat capacity values. On the other hand, for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, the value of α is found to be close to 3 (with $\gamma \simeq 1042$ mJ/mol.K^{3.75}) for $H = 3$ T, as expected [lower inset of Fig. 4.6(b)]. For $H > 4$ T, it is reduced significantly to about ~ 2 and remains almost field independent. Interestingly, these fields fall within the exotic regime (between $\mu_0 H_{S1} \simeq 3.6$ T and $\mu_0 H_{S2} \simeq 10.5$ T) found from the magnetization measurements. In these fields, the value of γ varies from ~ 300 to 90 mJ/mol.K³ which is a significant reduction from the 3 T value but it is still considerably large.

Typically, one expects a T^3 behaviour for $C_p(T)$ due to 3D spin-wave dispersion in the

AFM ordered state [243]. On the other hand, a more conventional characteristic feature of QSL is the linear temperature dependency of low temperature $C_p(T)$ i.e. $C_p = \gamma T$ where, γ is related to the spinon density of states at the spinon Fermi surface. Likewise, a quadratic temperature dependency ($C_p \propto T^2$) is predicted theoretically for the gapless Dirac QSLs at low temperatures [244, 245]. Indeed, several QSL candidates with triangular, kagome, and hyperkagome geometries are reported to evince such a behaviour at low temperatures [8, 45, 246–248]. Thus, the suppression of magnetic LRO and power law behaviour of C_p with a reduced value of $\alpha \sim 2$ in the critical field region unambiguously point towards an exotic phase regime, possibly the field induced QSL in $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ [249, 250]. Moreover, the obtained large value of γ can also be considered as a generic feature of low-energy gapless excitations, as observed for gapless QSL candidates $\text{Ba}_3\text{CuSb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_2\text{Cu}(\text{Te}_{0.5}\text{W}_{0.5})\text{O}_6$ [107, 251].

This type of field induced behaviour is observed in some honeycomb lattices with strong Kitaev interaction. The Kitaev physics demands the presence of bond-dependent anisotropy which can be realized in honeycomb lattices as well as spin dimers with strong spin-orbit coupling where the metal octahedra are either edge shared or parallelly edge shared [144, 145]. Further, it is predicted that spin-orbit coupled honeycomb systems with $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ are an ideal platform to host a Kitaev spin liquid [252]. Indeed, $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ honeycomb lattices $\alpha\text{-RuCl}_3$ [152], $\text{Na}_2\text{Co}_2\text{TeO}_6$ [153], $\text{BaCo}_2(\text{AsO}_4)_2$ [172], and $\text{BaCo}_2(\text{P}_{1-x}\text{V}_x)\text{O}_8$ [253] with strong anisotropy show the onset of conventional magnetic LRO at low temperatures. Under magnetic field, the LRO is suppressed (i.e. the anisotropic bond dependent coupling dominates over the isotropic coupling) and the system eventually crosses over to a low temperature non-magnetic or disordered state which is understood to be the field induced Kitaev spin-liquid [144]. A triangular lattice can also be viewed as a superposition of honeycomb layers in certain stacking sequence. This analogy can be extended to the TLAFs $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb,Ta})_2\text{O}_9$. A careful inspection of the crystal structure reveals that the CoO_6 octahedra in both the compounds are parallel edge shared, when the non-magnetic $(\text{Nb,Ta})\text{O}_6$ octahedra are removed. In Fig. 4.1(b), we have schematized the ways in which parallel edge sharing could be feasible in $\text{Sr}_3\text{Co}(\text{Nb,Ta})_2\text{O}_9$. As one

can clearly see that the identical Co-octahedra are perfectly parallel edge shared, which might facilitate a bond-dependent anisotropy and hence Kitaev interaction [158,254]. Meanwhile, due to low symmetry crystal structure, there is an inherent distortion in the metal octahedra due to which the edge sharing between two dissimilar octahedra [Co(1)O₆ and Co(2)O₆] is deviating slightly from the perfect parallel edge sharing. It is to be noted that the recent theoretical work on TLAFs has also predicted a transition from an ordered magnetic state in the isotropic case into a QSL state in the easy-axis regime, with increasing easy-axis anisotropy [255]. Nevertheless, to conclusively establish this novel phenomena in these TLAFs, inelastic neutron scattering and μ SR experiments in dilution temperatures and under magnetic fields on good quality single crystals would be imperative.

Experimentally, the extent of frustration in any magnetically frustrated material is quantified by the frustration ratio $f = |\theta_{CW}|/T_N$ [33]. From the value of θ_{CW} and T_{N1} , the frustration parameter is calculated to be $f \sim 5$ and ~ 9 for Sr₃CoNb₂O₉ and Sr₃CoTa₂O₉, respectively. Despite same crystal structure, the latter shows stronger frustration and a fluctuating regime over an extended field range while for the former, the extent of frustration is less and hence the fluctuating regime is narrowed down. The possible origin of such a drastic difference in magnetic properties can be attributed to the hierarchy of the exchange couplings. It is to be noted that the Co²⁺ - Co²⁺ superexchange involves Co²⁺(3d) - O²⁻(2p) - Nb⁵⁺(4p) - O²⁻(2p) - Co²⁺(3d) and Co²⁺(3d) - O²⁻(2p) - Ta⁵⁺(4f) - O²⁻(2p) - Co²⁺(3d) pathways for Sr₃CoNb₂O₉ and Sr₃CoTa₂O₉, respectively. Hence, the difference in coupling strength is likely due to the participation of different orbitals of Nb⁵⁺(4p) and Ta⁵⁺(4f) in the interaction mechanism [234,256].

4.4 Conclusion

We report a detailed study of the thermodynamic properties of two new quantum magnets Sr₃Co(Nb,Ta)₂O₉ possessing Co²⁺ triangular layers. Their low temperature properties are unequivocally described by $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ Kramers doublet of Co²⁺ ions interacting antiferro-

magnetically. Similar to many other TLAFs with easy-axis anisotropy, both the compounds undergo two sequential magnetic transitions at low temperatures. $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ exhibits a weak plateau type feature at the $1/3$ magnetization while this feature is smeared for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, likely due to the effect of magnetic anisotropy and/or random orientation of the crystallites. Despite same crystal structure, $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ with $f \simeq 9$ is found to be more frustrated than $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ with $f \simeq 5$, which can be attributed to the involvement of different orbitals of Ta^{5+} and Nb^{5+} in the interaction paths. The existence of an exotic field induced quantum phase is detected for $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ over a wide field range, below the fully polarized state while this behaviour is either absent or exists over a narrow field range for the Nb analogue. Because of this non-trivial character, $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ is a model system for further experimental as well as theoretical investigations at low temperatures and under magnetic fields.

Chapter 5

Inhomogeneous dynamic state in the double trillium lattice antiferromagnet

$\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$

In this chapter, we present an in-depth investigation of spin dynamics and static magnetic properties of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ employing local probes like ^{31}P NMR and muon spin resonance (μSR), electron spin resonance (ESR), dc and ac susceptibility, and heat capacity measurements, complemented by density-functional theory (DFT) calculations [257]. We also briefly discuss

Figure 5.1: A coupled trillium unit of Fe^{3+} ions, connected via PO_4 tetrahedra.

the iso-structural compound $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, belonging to the same structural family for a comparison. Being a member of the langbeinite family, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ crystallizes in the cubic space group $P2_13$, where Fe^{3+} ($S = 5/2$) ions are embedded in a double-trillium lattice [see Fig. 5.1]. Owing to its highly frustrated geometry, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ evades LRO, with AFM fluctuations prevailing down to 30 mK. Our local probes strongly suggest inhomogeneous spin dynamics of the fluctuating spins; a notable feature observed for the first time in a double trillium lattice AFM.

5.1 Experimental Details

Polycrystalline samples of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, and $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ were synthesized by the conventional solid-state reaction method. Stoichiometric amounts of K_2CO_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%), PbO (Sigma Aldrich, 99.99%), BaCO_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.997%), In_2O_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.997%), Fe_2O_3 (Sigma Aldrich, 99.999%), and $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4$ (Sigma Aldrich, 99.995%) were thoroughly ground for several hours to achieve fine powders. The powder samples were then pressed into pellets, placed in platinum crucibles, and preheated at 600°C for 12 h each in air. The resulting products were reground, pressed into pellets again, and fired at 1100°C , 950°C and 900°C for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, and $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, respectively, with multiple intermediate grindings to ensure homogeneity. The phase purity of the synthesized polycrystalline samples were confirmed by powder XRD performed at room temperature using a PANalytical x-ray diffractometer (CuK_α , $\lambda_{\text{avg}} = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). Additionally, high-resolution XRD data for the $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ sample were collected at the ID22 beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (Grenoble, France) using the wavelength of 0.3546 \AA and the multi-analyzer detector setup. The sample was placed into a thin-wall borosilicate glass capillary and spun during the measurement. Sample temperature was controlled by the liquid-nitrogen cryostream.

DC magnetization (M) as a function of temperature ($1.9 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 380 \text{ K}$) and in different magnetic fields ($0 \leq H \leq 9 \text{ T}$) was measured using the VSM attachment to a Physical Property

Measurement System (PPMS, Quantum Design). An isothermal magnetization (M vs H) was recorded at $T = 2$ K in the field range -9 to 9 T. The high-field magnetization was measured at $T = 1.5$ K in pulsed magnetic field up to 60 T at the Dresden High Magnetic Field Laboratory [200, 201]. The alternating current (ac) magnetization was measured in the temperature range of $2 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 50 \text{ K}$ using the ACMS option of PPMS in different frequencies ($99 \text{ Hz} \leq \nu \leq 6999 \text{ Hz}$) and in an applied ac field of $H_{ac} = 10$ Oe. Temperature-dependent heat capacity [$C_p(T)$] was measured on a small sintered pellet over the temperature range $0.35 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 250 \text{ K}$ in different applied magnetic fields ($0 \text{ T} \leq \mu_0 H \leq 9 \text{ T}$) using the standard thermal relaxation technique in a PPMS. For measurements below 2 K (down to 0.35 K), a ^3He insert was used.

Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) experiment on the polycrystalline $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ samples was performed using a standard continuous-wave ESR setup at X-band frequency (9.4 GHz). The temperature was varied between $3 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$ with a He-flow cryostat. ESR signal can be detected by the absorbed power P of a transverse magnetic microwave field as a function of a static, external magnetic field B . To improve the signal-to-noise ratio, we used a lock-in technique by modulating the static field, which yields the derivative of the resonance signal dP/dB . The measured ESR spectra were fitted with a Lorentzian function including the influence of the counter-rotating component of the linearly polarized microwave field [258]. From the fit, we obtained the amplitude (A), the linewidth ΔB which is a measure of the spin dynamics, and the resonance field B_{res} which determines the ESR g -factor $g = h\nu/\mu_B B_{\text{res}}$.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) measurements were performed on the $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ sample using a laboratory-built phase-coherent spin-echo pulse spectrometer over a temperature range $1.6 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 300 \text{ K}$ on the ^{31}P nucleus (nuclear spin $I = 1/2$ and gyromagnetic ratio $\gamma_N/2\pi = 17.2356 \text{ MHz/T}$). The NMR data were collected at three different radio frequencies, $\nu = 56.4, 99.0, \text{ and } 126.6 \text{ MHz}$, which correspond to magnetic fields of $\mu_0 H = 3.272, 5.743, \text{ and } 7.345 \text{ T}$, respectively. The NMR spectra were obtained by sweeping the magnetic field at a fixed resonance frequency, employing a standard $\pi/2 - \tau - \pi$ pulse sequence with $\tau = 10 \mu\text{s}$.

The nuclear spin-lattice relaxation rate ($1/T_1$) was extracted by measuring the longitudinal magnetization as a function of waiting time (t) by employing the saturation pulse sequence $\pi/2 - \tau_1 - \pi/2 - \tau_2 - \pi$, at the spectral peak positions. The nuclear spin-spin relaxation rate ($1/T_2$) was determined by tracking the decay of the spin-echo intensity as a function of the delay time (τ_2) between the $\pi/2$ and π pulses.

Muon spin relaxation/rotation (μSR) measurements were carried out on the Flexible Advanced MuSR Environment (FLAME) spectrometer at the Swiss Muon Source ($S\mu\text{S}$), Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI), Villigen, Switzerland, under both zero-field (ZF) and longitudinal-field (LF) configurations. FLAME enables true ZF conditions with residual magnetic fields $\leq 5 \mu\text{T}$, actively compensated using three orthogonal vector magnets for precise field alignment and stray field cancellation. The detector system comprises compact scintillator/SiPM detectors with a timing resolution better than ~ 150 ps. The initial muon polarization was aligned along the beam direction. A pellet (10 mm diameter) of polycrystalline $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ was mounted using GE varnish on a copper backing plate and enclosed between two $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick copper foils to enhance thermal contact. Thermalization to millikelvin temperatures was ensured through rigid thermal anchoring to the mixing chamber of a KelvinoxJT dilution refrigerator, integrated with an Oxford Variox cryostat. This setup enabled measurements over a temperature range of 30 mK to 160 K and longitudinal fields up to 1.5 T. To ensure true zero-field conditions, passive field compensation was achieved via calibrated Hall probe measurements and fine-tuning with vector magnets. Particular care was taken to ensure full thermal equilibrium at each temperature set point, especially below 100 mK, by allowing adequate dwell times. The ZF and LF asymmetry spectra collected in forward and backward detector pairs were analyzed using the MUSRFIT software package [259].

Density-functional (DFT) band-structure calculations were performed in the VASP code [260, 261] using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof flavor of the exchange-correlation potential [262] and the experimental structural parameters of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ with the complete ordering of the K and Ba sites. Magnetic interactions between the Fe^{3+} ions is described by a Heisenberg spin

Table 5.1: Lattice parameters obtained from the Rietveld refinement of the powder XRD data.

Compound	$a = b = c$ (Å)	$\alpha = \beta = \gamma$	V_{cell} (Å ³)
KBaFe ₂ (PO ₄) ₃	9.885(1)	90°	966.12(1)
KPbFe ₂ (PO ₄) ₃	9.823(1)	90°	947.97(1)
KBaIn ₂ (PO ₄) ₃	10.122(1)	90°	1037.25(1)

Hamiltonian,

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{\langle ij \rangle} J_{ij} \mathbf{S}_i \mathbf{S}_j \quad (5.1)$$

where $S = 5/2$ and the summation is over bonds. The J_{ij} parameters were determined from total energies of collinear spin configurations by a mapping procedure [263,264]. To this end, the energies were calculated on the DFT+ U level using the on-site Coulomb repulsion $U_d = 7.5$ eV and Hund's coupling $J_d = 1$ eV for the Fe $3d$ shell [265]. The double-counting correction in the atomic limit was applied.

Magnetic susceptibility was obtained from classical Monte-Carlo simulations using the `spinmc` algorithm of the ALPS simulation package [266]. Finite lattices with up to $8 \times 8 \times 8$ unit cells of the KBaFe₂(PO₄)₃ structure and periodic boundary conditions were used.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 X-ray Diffraction

Rietveld refinement of the powder XRD data was carried out using the FULLPROF software package, with the initial structural parameters taken from Ref. [129]. The XRD patterns (Fig. 5.2) for all the three sample were indexed well to a cubic structure with space group $P2_13$. The refined lattice parameters are tabulated in Table 5.1. The relatively low goodness-of-fit (χ^2) parameter confirms excellent quality and phase purity of the synthesized samples.

High-resolution XRD data for the KBaFe₂(PO₄)₃ sample [see Fig. 5.3] further confirm its robust cubic symmetry. Structure refinement shows the ordering of the K and Ba atoms, albeit

Figure 5.2: Powder XRD pattern of (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, and (c) $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ measured at $T = 300$ K. The circles are experimental data points and the solid line is the Rietveld refinement fit. The Bragg peak positions are indicated by vertical lines, whereas the bottom solid line indicates the difference between the experimental and calculated intensities.

Figure 5.3: Rietveld refinement of the 80 K high-resolution XRD data for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

Table 5.2: Refined atomic positions (x, y, z), atomic displacement parameters (U_{iso} , in 10^{-2}Å^2), and site occupancies for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at 80 K. The space group is $P2_13$, and the refined lattice parameter is $a = 9.87440(1) \text{Å}$.

		x/a	y/b	z/c	U_{iso}	Occ.
K1	$4a$	0.29781(2)	0.29781	0.29781	1.10(1)	0.721(1)
Ba1	$4a$	0.29781(2)	0.29781	0.29781	1.10(1)	0.279(1)
K2	$4a$	0.06668(2)	0.06668	0.06668	0.72(1)	0.279(1)
Ba2	$4a$	0.06668(2)	0.06668	0.06668	0.72(1)	0.721(1)
Fe1	$4a$	0.58566(2)	0.58566	0.58566	0.38(1)	1.0
Fe2	$4a$	0.85242(3)	0.85242	0.85242	0.45(1)	1.0
P1	$12b$	0.62639(5)	0.46101(5)	0.27220(5)	0.27(1)	1.0
O1	$12b$	0.6543(1)	0.5001(2)	0.4192(2)	1.37(3)	1.0
O2	$12b$	0.7625(2)	0.4833(2)	0.1983(2)	1.39(3)	1.0
O3	$12b$	0.5798(2)	0.3138(2)	0.2594(1)	1.03(3)	1.0
O4	$12b$	0.5223(1)	0.5533(2)	0.1986(2)	1.21(3)	1.0

Figure 5.4: (a), (b) Temperature dependence of χ_{dc} , measured under different applied fields for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, respectively. Insets: $1/\chi$ vs T at $\mu_0 H = 0.5$ T and the solid line represents the CW fit. The solid line in (a) represents the classical Monte-Carlo simulation using the optimized exchange parameters from Table 5.3 for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ (c), (d) $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$ measured under ZFC and FC protocols in $\mu_0 H = 0.01$ T. The characteristic temperature T^* marks the onset of bifurcation between the ZFC and FC curves. (e) M vs H for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ measured at $T = 1.5$ K using pulsed magnetic fields upto 60 T. The pulsed field data are scaled with respect to the $M(H)$ data measured using PPMS at $T = 2$ K. (f) M vs H for $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at $T = 2$ K. Insets of (e) and (f): low-field M vs H data (-0.5 to 0.5 T) at $T = 2$ K showing no hysteresis.

with the residual site mixing of 28% (Table 5.2).

5.2.2 DC and AC magnetization

The dc magnetic susceptibility ($\chi_{\text{dc}} \equiv M/H$, where M is the magnetization and H is the applied field) of the powder samples of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ was measured as a function of temperature in various applied magnetic fields, as shown in Figs. 5.4 (a,b). Upon cooling, $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$ for both the compounds increases monotonically, showing no evidence of a conventional magnetic long-range order (LRO) down to 1.9 K. However, a bifurcation between zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) measurements at $\mu_0 H = 0.01$ T is observed at

a characteristic temperature T^* [~ 3.4 K for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and ~ 3.7 K for $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$] [Figs. 5.4 (c,d)], which disappears completely in magnetic fields exceeding 1 T. This ZFC-FC splitting may arise from either a spin-glass/freezing behavior or due to partial site mixing of K and Ba/Pb atoms [45].

At high temperatures, χ_{dc} follows the Curie-Weiss (CW) behaviour. The CW fit [Eq. (3.3)] to χ_{dc} of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ measured at $\mu_0 H = 0.5$ T for $T \geq 150$ K [inset of Fig. 5.4(a)] yields the parameters: $\chi_0 \simeq 2.44(1) \times 10^{-5}$ cm³/mol-Fe³⁺, $C \simeq 4.40(1)$ cm³-K/mol-Fe³⁺, and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -70(1)$ K. From the value of C , the effective magnetic moment is estimated to be $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.93(2)\mu_{\text{B}}$. This corresponds to a Landé g -factor, $g \simeq 2$ for spin $S = 5/2$, consistent with the value obtained from the ESR measurements (discussed later). Similarly, for $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, the CW fit under the same condition as that of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ [inset of Fig. 5.4(b)] yields $\chi_0 \simeq 5.84(1) \times 10^{-5}$ cm³/mol-Fe³⁺, $C \simeq 4.41(1)$ cm³-K/mol-Fe³⁺, and $\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -65(1)$ K. The corresponding $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 5.94(2)\mu_{\text{B}}$ implies $g \simeq 2$ for $S = 5/2$, in excellent agreement with the ESR value (discussed later). Further, it is observed that χ_{dc} for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at low temperatures shows the tendency towards saturation $\mu_0 H \geq 1$ T, which does not support a conventional AFM LRO near T^* .

The isothermal magnetization (M vs H) measured up to 9 T varies linearly without any indication of saturation for both the compounds [see Figs. 5.4(e, f)]. As shown in Fig. 5.4(e), we further extended the field range up to 60 T using pulsed-field for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The M vs H curve remains linear over the entire field range, indicating the presence of strong AFM exchange interactions. Although a full saturation is not clearly observed, M shows the tendency of saturation and approaches $M \simeq 5\mu_{\text{B}}$ near 60 T, consistent with the expected fully polarized moment for $S = 5/2$ with $g = 2$. This suggests that the saturation field is about $H_{\text{S}} \simeq 60$ T. Furthermore, we have also measured the magnetic isotherm carefully in the low-field regime (-0.5 T to +0.5 T) at $T = 2$ K, as shown in the insets of Figs. 5.4(e,f). The absence of any noticeable hysteresis around zero field suggest the absence of a ferromagnetic or glassy component for both the compounds.

Figure 5.5: Temperature dependence of the real component of ac susceptibility (χ'_{ac}) measured at various frequencies for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The curves are vertically offset for clarity. The vertical dashed line serves as a guide to show no shift in peak position with frequency.

To further inspect the splitting between ZFC-FC $\chi(T)$ observed at low magnetic fields around T^* , we performed ac magnetic susceptibility measurements at various frequencies. Figure 5.5 presents the temperature dependence of the real part of the ac susceptibility (χ'_{ac}) of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at various frequencies. χ'_{ac} exhibits a well-defined peak at T_f , which is very close to T^* . With increasing frequency, the peak position remained unchanged. Therefore, we conclude that the observed T^* in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ cannot be assigned to a spin-glass transition.

5.2.3 DFT

Table 5.3: Exchange couplings J_i (in K) in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, calculated in the present work using DFT, and optimized to achieve the best fit of the experimental magnetic susceptibility [Fig. 5.4(a)]. The labels of $J_1 - J_5$ follow “Nat. Commun. **15**, 7191 (2024)”.

	J_1	J_2	J_3	J_4	J_5
$d_{\text{Fe-Fe}}$ (in Å)	4.562	4.939	6.080	6.039	6.146
DFT	1.7	1.3	2.5	4.3	3.5
Optimized	1.5	0	1.6	2.7	3.9

Using DFT, we find that all five couplings of the double-trillium lattice in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$

are AFM and, therefore, highly frustrated. We further refine the $J_1 - J_5$ values by a direct comparison with the experimental $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$ [Fig. 5.4(a)]. Similar to $\text{K}_2\text{Ni}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ [29], the two dominant couplings in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ are J_4 and J_5 , but finite J_1 and J_3 are also essential to describe $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$ at low temperatures. Given the spin-5/2 nature of Fe^{3+} , the T^* is at least one order of magnitude smaller than the energy scale of the exchange couplings.

5.2.4 Heat Capacity

Figure 5.6: C_p vs T in different applied fields along with the power law fit ($C_p = \gamma T^\alpha$) in the low-temperature regime for (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The solid line represents the phonon contribution to the heat capacity (C_{ph}) using the non-magnetic analog, $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. C_{mag}/T vs T in the left y -axis and magnetic entropy ΔS_{mag} vs T in the right y -axis for (c) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (d) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

Figures 5.6(a,b) display the temperature-dependent heat capacity [$C_p(T)$] measured down to 0.35 K in various applied magnetic fields for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. As the temperature decreases, C_p systematically decreases and passes through a broad maximum, without exhibiting any λ -like anomaly, thereby ruling out the presence of a magnetic LRO. Notably, the broad maximum at around 7 K remains unaffected by applied fields up to 9 T,

reflecting the development of robust short-range AFM correlations for both the compounds, similar to other 3D SL candidates, $\text{Na}_4\text{Ir}_3\text{O}_8$ [45] and $\text{PbCuTe}_2\text{O}_6$ [267]. For 3D frustrated and SL systems, such a maximum typically appears in the range $T/\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq 0.02 - 0.15$ [267]. In the case of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, this ratio (~ 0.055) is consistent with its proximity to the SL state.

Figure 5.7: C_{mag} vs T^2 plot fitted with a straight line at low- T s for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

In magnetic insulators, the total heat capacity typically consists of two main contributions: the phonon or lattice term [$C_{\text{ph}}(T)$], dominant at high temperatures, and the magnetic contribution [$C_{\text{mag}}(T)$], which becomes significant at low temperatures depending on the strength of the magnetic interactions. To isolate C_{mag} from the total heat capacity C_{p} , we estimated the phononic background using the isostructural non-magnetic analog $\text{KBaIn}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. $C_{\text{p}}(T)$ of this non-magnetic analog was measured down to 2 K and then extrapolated down to 0.3 K assuming a purely phononic behavior, $C_{\text{ph}} = \beta T^3$, with $\beta \simeq 3.35 \text{ J/mol-K}^4$. From the value of β , the average Debye temperature is estimated to be $\theta_{\text{D}} = \left(\frac{12\pi^4 n R}{5\beta} \right)^{1/3} \simeq 22.2 \text{ K}$ ($n = 19$ is the number of atoms per formula unit) [268]. After subtracting the extrapolated C_{ph} from the total C_{p} , we obtained the magnetic heat capacity $C_{\text{mag}}(T)$.

Below 1 K, the $C_{\text{mag}}(T)$ data in zero-field were fitted using a power-law of the form $C_{\text{mag}} = \gamma T^\alpha$. For $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, it exhibits a clear quadratic behavior (see Fig. 5.7) ($\alpha \simeq 2$) while a slightly higher value of $\alpha \simeq 2.2$ is observed in the case of $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. For $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$,

the quadratic behavior yields $\gamma \simeq 0.69$ J/mol-K². Given the 3D nature of the material, such a reduced exponent excludes the possibility of a conventional 3D AFM LRO and instead indicates unconventional magnetic excitations, consistent with highly frustrated magnets that host SL-like dynamical correlations [28, 29, 247].

The magnetic entropy change, $\Delta S_{\text{mag}}(T)$, was calculated by integrating $C_{\text{mag}}(T)/T$ over temperature, i.e., $\Delta S_{\text{mag}} = \int_0^T \frac{C_{\text{mag}}(T')}{T'} dT'$. For both $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, the recovered entropy approaches close to 95 % of $R \ln 6$, as expected for $S = 5/2$ (Fe^{3+}) spins [see Figs. 5.6(c,d)].

5.2.5 Electron spin resonance

Figure 5.8: ESR spectra of (a) $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and (b) $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ at some selected temperatures and with magnifications as indicated. The black solid line depicts the fit using a Lorentzian line shape. Temperature dependence of (c) ΔB and (d) B_{res} for both $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Inset of (d): $1/\chi_{\text{ESR}}$ vs T with solid lines indicating the CW fits in the range $10 \leq T \leq 150$ K.

The electron spin resonance (ESR) intensity (χ_{ESR}) is a measure of the local static susceptibility of the probed ESR spins, i.e., the local susceptibility of the Fe^{3+} spins [269]. We

calculated $\chi_{\text{ESR}} \approx A \cdot \Delta B^2$ which approximates the integrated ESR absorption. The ESR signals for some selected temperatures for both $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ are shown in Fig. 5.8(a,b). The black solid lines depict data fitting by symmetrical Lorentzian shapes. Below $T \simeq 10$ K, the linewidth approaches the available field limit, while the amplitude and resonance field are strongly reduced. This behavior points to a slowing down of spin fluctuations at lower temperatures, which is also indicated by the temperature dependence of the ESR parameters.

The temperature dependence of the linewidth (ΔB) is shown in Fig. 5.8(c). Towards low temperatures, a continuous broadening until the lowest accessible temperature (3.7 K) is observed, which is due to the growth of AFM correlations between Fe^{3+} spins. The resonance field (B_{res}) shows a temperature dependence which also supports the critical slowing down of fluctuations below 3 K. While at high temperatures the resonance fields of both compounds are essentially determined by the Fe g -factors [see Fig. 5.8], the region below 10 K becomes gradually dominated by the build-up of magnetic molecular fields. Furthermore, χ_{ESR} was well fitted by Eq. (3.3) in the range $10 \text{ K} \leq T \leq 150 \text{ K}$ [see inset of Fig. 5.8(d)]. The obtained θ_{CW} values for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ are $\theta_{\text{CW}}^{\text{Ba}} \simeq -75 \text{ K}$ and $\theta_{\text{CW}}^{\text{Pb}} \simeq -65 \text{ K}$, respectively, which are in good agreement with the χ_{dc} analysis.

5.2.6 ^{31}P NMR

5.2.6.1 NMR Spectra and Shift

Since both $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ and $\text{KPbFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ exhibit nearly identical behaviors, the ^{31}P NMR experiments were carried out only on $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ sample. As shown in Figs. 5.9 and 5.10, the NMR spectra measured at 56.4 MHz (3.27 T) and 126.6 MHz (7.34 T) exhibit a single and nearly Gaussian lineshape at high temperatures, consistent with the unique crystallographic P-site. Upon cooling, the NMR line broadens and shifts to lower fields. Below $T \sim 10$ K, the NMR signal intensity decreases rapidly and becomes undetectable by the NMR spectrometer while approaching T^* [inset of Fig. 5.9(a)]. This wipe-out effect results from the rapid shortening of spin-spin relaxation time (T_2), pushing the spin echo below the instrumental resolution. For

Figure 5.9: Temperature dependent field-sweep ^{31}P NMR spectra measured at 126.6 MHz for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The vertical dashed line marks the Larmor field. Inset: temperature-dependent signal intensity multiplied by temperature with the T_2 corrections.

$T \lesssim 2$ K, we observed a partial recovery of the signal, though only about $\sim 3\%$ of the intensity (as compared to high temperatures) is recovered at 1.6 K. This behavior draws parallel with that observed in other highly frustrated magnets featuring unusual spin dynamics [270, 271]. The NMR line retains a Gaussian shape across T^* , inconsistent with a rectangular pattern expected for a conventional AFM ordering.

The spectrum at each temperature was fitted by a Gaussian profile and the NMR shift (K) was determined as $\mathcal{K} = [2\pi\nu/\gamma_N - H_p]/H_p$, where H_p represents the magnetic field of the peak position at each temperature. \mathcal{K} provides a direct measure of the intrinsic spin susceptibility (χ_{dc}) and can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{K}(T) = \mathcal{K}_0 + \frac{A_{\text{hf}}}{N_A} \chi_{\text{dc}}(T), \quad (5.2)$$

where \mathcal{K}_0 is the temperature-independent orbital shift, A_{hf} is the hyperfine coupling constant,

Figure 5.10: Temperature-dependent ^{31}P NMR spectra measured at 56.4 MHz. Inset: Temperature dependence of ^{31}P NMR shift (\mathcal{K}) at 56.4 MHz and 126.6 MHz overlaid with dc magnetic susceptibility (χ_{dc}) data measured at 2 T.

and N_A is Avogadro's number. The extracted NMR shift $\mathcal{K}(T)$ from the spectral peak positions (see inset of Fig. 5.10) follows $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$ very well, confirming the intrinsic origin of the NMR response. A linear \mathcal{K} - χ plot (Fig. 5.11) for $T > 30$ K yields $A_{\text{hf}} \simeq 0.80(1)$ T/ μ_B and $\mathcal{K}_0 \simeq -0.14(1)\%$. This value of A_{hf} is found to be field-independent. Additionally, the saturation of $\mathcal{K}(T)$ to a finite value at low temperatures supports the formation of a gapless state in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The temperature dependence of $1/(\mathcal{K} - \mathcal{K}_0)$ is illustrated in the inset of Fig. 5.11. The data in the temperature range of 50–250 K were fitted using the Curie-Weiss (CW) law

$$\mathcal{K}(T) = \mathcal{K}_0(T) + \frac{B}{T - \theta_{\text{CW}}^{\mathcal{K}}}. \quad (5.3)$$

The fit results in a CW temperature $\theta_{\text{CW}}^{\mathcal{K}} \simeq -82$ K, which is consistent with the value obtained from the χ_{dc} analysis.

Having established the relationship between $\mathcal{K}(T)$ and $\chi_{\text{dc}}(T)$, we now turn to the line broadening behavior at low temperatures. Below 10 K, we see a significant increase in the NMR linewidth (ΔB) for all measured frequencies [Fig. 5.12]. As presented in the inset of Fig. 5.12,

Figure 5.11: Clogston-Jaccarino plot of \mathcal{K} vs χ with T as an implicit parameter. Inset: $1/(\mathcal{K} - \mathcal{K}_0)$ vs T and the solid line is the CW fit as per Eq. (5.3).

Figure 5.12: Full width at half maximum (ΔB) of the ^{31}P NMR line as a function of temperature, measured at three different frequencies. The solid line represents the magnetization (M) vs T plot for $\mu_0 H = 7$ T. Inset: ΔB as a function of the NMR frequency.

for $T > T^*$, ΔB scales linearly with ν (or, H) as expected for the paramagnetic fluctuations. However, below T^* (i.e., at 1.6 K), the linewidth remains almost field-independent with a residual linewidth [$\Delta B(0) = 0.6(1)$ T] for $\nu \rightarrow 0$. Thus, the NMR spectral analysis reveals the existence of a finite internal field well below T^* .

5.2.6.2 Spin-lattice relaxation rate ($1/T_1$)

Figure 5.13: Longitudinal magnetization recovery curves at three different temperatures for 56.4 MHz and the solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.4).

To obtain a further detailed information about the spin dynamics, we measured the ^{31}P spin-lattice relaxation rate ($1/T_1$) using the saturation-recovery method. The longitudinal magnetization recovery curves were fitted by a single exponential function (Fig. 5.13), appropriate for an $I = 1/2$ nucleus:

$$1 - \frac{M(t)}{M(\infty)} = A \exp(-t/T_1), \quad (5.4)$$

where A is a normalization factor, and $M(t)$ and $M(\infty)$ denote the nuclear magnetization at time t and at equilibrium, respectively. Figure 5.14 presents the spin-lattice relaxation rate ($1/T_1$) measured at different frequencies. The data from both the frequencies overlap with each other. At high temperatures $1/T_1$ is nearly temperature independent, as expected due to

Figure 5.14: Temperature dependence of $1/T_1$ at different frequencies, together with the temperature dependence of $\chi_{dc}T$ measured at 2 T.

Figure 5.15: $1/T_1 T \chi$ vs T using the $1/T_1$ data at 56.4 MHz and χ_{dc} data at 2 T for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The horizontal dashed line marks the T -independent behaviour from the high- T regime.

paramagnetic fluctuations [272]. As the temperature is reduced, it shows a gradual increase, suggesting the slowing down of fluctuating moments. For $T \leq 8$ K, (well above T^*) T_1 becomes too short and could not be measured.

To further quantify the nature of spin fluctuations in the paramagnetic regime, we analyzed the temperature dependence of $1/T_1 T \chi$. In general, one can express $1/T_1$ in terms of the dynamic susceptibility as

$$\frac{1}{T_1} = \frac{2\gamma_N^2 k_B T}{N_A^2} \sum_{\vec{q}} |A(\vec{q})|^2 \frac{\chi''(\vec{q}, \omega_N)}{\omega_N}, \quad (5.5)$$

where $A(\vec{q})$ is the hyperfine form factor and $\chi''(\vec{q}, \omega_N)$ is the imaginary part of the dynamical susceptibility [273, 274]. Figure 5.15 shows the variation of $1/T_1 T \chi$ with temperature, effectively linking the temperature dependence of $\sum_{\vec{q}} |A(\vec{q})|^2 \chi''(\vec{q}, \omega_N)$ to the uniform static susceptibility $\chi'(0, 0)$. For temperatures above $|\theta_{\text{CW}}^K|$, $1/T_1 T \chi$ remains nearly constant. This behavior implies that $|A(\vec{q})|^2 \chi''(\vec{q}, \omega_N)$ scales proportionally with $\chi'(0, 0)$, reflecting uniform spin fluctuations ($\vec{q} = 0$) across the Brillouin zone [274]. On the other hand, at temperatures below $|\theta_{\text{CW}}^K|$, $1/T_1 T \chi$ increases rapidly. This indicates an enhanced contribution from $\vec{q} \neq 0$ spin fluctuations, characteristic of emerging AFM correlations. Such behavior underscores the dominance of short-range AFM correlations in the low-temperature regime.

It is important to note that, the increase in $1/T_1$ occurs over a broad temperature range rather than displaying a sharp divergence, thereby ruling out the onset of a conventional AFM LRO [275]. Instead, the data indicate the development of slow, short-range AFM spin dynamics further reflecting the unconventional nature of spin dynamics in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

5.2.6.3 Spin-spin relaxation rate ($1/T_2$)

Since T_1 becomes too short to measure reliably below ~ 8 K, we employed the spin-spin relaxation rate ($1/T_2$) to probe the low-temperature dynamics near T^* . Figure 5.16(a) shows the recovery of the transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) above and below T^* . For $T > T^*$, the

Figure 5.16: (a) Recovery curves of the transverse magnetization (M_{xy}) plotted against time (t) for temperatures below and above T^* . (b) M_{xy} measured at different temperatures below T^* . The solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.7).

recovery is well described by a single exponential

$$M(t) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{2t}{T_2}\right)^\beta\right], \quad \beta = 1, \quad (5.6)$$

consistent with a homogeneous relaxation. In contrast, for $T < T^*$ the curves deviate from Eq. (5.6) and are best captured by a two-component form

$$M_{xy} = M_0 \left[M_S \exp\left(\frac{-2\tau}{T_2^S}\right) + M_L \exp\left(\frac{-2\tau}{T_2^L}\right) \right], \quad (5.7)$$

indicating multiple relaxation channels. Here, M_S and M_L are the relative amplitudes (normalized by M_0), and T_2^S and T_2^L are the short and long components, respectively. At $T = 1.6$ K, the short component dominates with $M_S \sim 92\%$ and $T_2^S \simeq 0.0118(1)$ ms, while the long component contributes $M_L \sim 8\%$ with $T_2^L \simeq 0.08(1)$ ms. This separation of relaxation time scales indicates a broad distribution of local magnetic environments, consistent with spatially inhomogeneous or dynamic disorder. Further evidence for this inhomogeneous dynamics is evident from Fig. 5.16(b), where the nearly temperature independent $1/T_2$ behavior below T^* is highlighted.

Figure 5.17: $1/T_2$ as a function of temperature measured at various frequencies. The red solid line represents the fit discussed in the text, with $T^* = 3.5$ K.

The representative recovery curves measured at different temperatures below T^* collapse onto a common envelope, and the solid line represents a fit using Eq. (5.7), reinforcing the picture of a disordered low-temperature magnetic state.

The temperature dependence of $1/T_2$ is summarized in Fig. 5.17. It mirrors the behavior of $1/T_1$, showing a broad minimum near 20 K and a sharp upturn below 10 K. Below T^* , $1/T_2$ saturates to a large and nearly T -independent value, evidencing persistent low-temperature spin dynamics. A power-law fit in the critical region ($T^* \leq T \leq 2T^*$) using $1/T_2 \propto \epsilon^{-\beta}$ (where, $\epsilon = T/T^* - 1$) yields a critical exponent $\beta = 0.52(3)$, larger than the typical value predicted for a conventional 3D AFM order (~ 0.3) [275]. Altogether, these observations, namely (i) the absence of conventional AFM LRO, (ii) the emergence of multiple relaxation channels in M_{xy} below T^* , and (iii) the enhanced critical behavior of $1/T_2$ with an unusual value of β , imply an inhomogeneous and dynamically fluctuating ground state in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$.

5.2.7 μSR

Next, we turn our attention towards μSR measurements. μSR probes spin dynamics over a frequency range complementary to NMR. As we have mentioned earlier, typically, the relaxation

Figure 5.18: (a) ZF muon spin asymmetry $[A_{ZF}(t)]$ at different temperatures for $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. Left panel: magnified short-time behavior ($t \leq 0.6 \mu\text{s}$) and right panel: long-time tail ($t \geq 0.6 \mu\text{s}$). Solid lines are fits using Eq. (5.8). (b) Muon-spin asymmetry $A_{LF}(t)$ measured under different LFs at $T \simeq 0.1 \text{ K}$. Left panel: enlarged short-time scale; right panel: long-time tail. The dashed lines represent simulated depolarization curves using Eq. (5.9). Solid lines are the fits using Eq. (5.10). (c) Temperature dependence of the ZF muon-spin relaxation rates (λ_1 and λ_2). Inset: temperature dependence of the stretching exponent β . (d) Temperature dependence of the fractional weight α . Inset: LF dependence of the contribution ϕ from *sporadic field fluctuations*.

time detectable in an NMR spectrometer ranges from 10^1 to 10^{-8} s, while μSR can probe in the range of 10^{-5} to 10^{-11} s. Therefore, μSR is an excellent probe to detect fast fluctuations that may be undetectable by NMR. For $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, since the NMR T_1 is getting too short and going beyond the detectable limit of the NMR spectrometer, we used μSR to probe the low temperature dynamics. Further, unlike NMR, μSR can be performed in true zero-field, eliminating any external perturbation to the intrinsic ground state.

Figure 5.18(a) presents the zero-field (ZF) muon-spin asymmetry spectra, $A_{ZF}(t)$, measured on polycrystalline $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ in the T -range $30 \text{ mK} \leq T \leq 160 \text{ K}$. For $T > 10 \text{ K}$, the

asymmetry curve follows a simple exponential decay. Upon cooling below 10 K, an additional fast initial depolarization appears, becoming increasingly Gaussian-like at lower temperatures. The continuous, monotonic loss of polarization without any coherent oscillations demonstrates the absence of a static LRO [276]. Moreover, we did not observe any sign of 1/3-tail, expected for static, randomly oriented moments [277, 278]. This suggests that the spins remain dynamic rather than static and/or frozen glassy state.

To describe the relaxation below 10 K, we tested several non-oscillatory functions, including single stretched exponentials and sums of exponentials. None provided a satisfactory description over the full time and temperature range. Instead, the spectra could be consistently modeled by the empirical function,

$$A_{\text{ZF}}(t) = A_0 \left[\alpha e^{-(\lambda_1 t)^\beta} + (1 - \alpha) e^{-\lambda_2 t} \right] + A_b G_{\text{KT}}, \quad (5.8)$$

where α and $(1 - \alpha)$ quantify the relative weight fractions of the two relaxation channels experienced by the sample. Here, λ_1 and λ_2 are relaxation rates associated with the fast early-time decay ($t \leq 0.3 \mu\text{s}$) and the slower long-time component ($t \geq 0.3 \mu\text{s}$), respectively. $A_0 = 0.241(1)$ and $A_b = 0.005(1)$ are the contributions from muons stopping sites at the sample and Cu sample holder, respectively. The background relaxation is described by the static Gaussian Kubo-Toyabe function, $G_{\text{KT}} = \frac{1}{3} + \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \sigma^2 t^2 \right) \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 t^2 \right]$, with $\sigma = 0.38 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$ fixed at the typical value expected for Cu [279] [see Fig. 5.19(b)]. Figures 5.18(c) and (d) show the extracted parameters (λ_1 , β , λ_2 , and α) as a function of temperature.

At higher temperatures, the relaxation is purely exponential (rather than root-exponential, as one expect in dilute systems), consistent with a dense network of fluctuating Fe^{3+} ($S = 5/2$) moments. Using the estimated nearest-neighbor exchange coupling $J/k_B \simeq 2 \text{ K}$ (from DFT calculations) and number of nearest neighbors $z = 6$, the high-temperature fluctuation rate can be approximated as $\nu = \sqrt{z} JS/\hbar \approx 1.6 \times 10^6 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$ [280]. In this dense magnetic environment, the fluctuating field distribution at the muon site can be approximated as Gaussian, with a

Figure 5.19: Zero-field muon spin asymmetry $A_{ZF}(t)$ measured at the lowest temperature (30 mK) in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. (a) Short-time region ($t \leq 0.3 \mu\text{s}$); the solid line shows the fit using Eq. (5.8), with an exponent $\beta \simeq 3.8$. Constraining $\beta = 2$ yields a noticeably poorer agreement with the data; as shown by red dashed line. (b) Background Kubo-Toyabe contribution (A_b) arising from muons stopping in the sample holder; the solid line shows the fit using Eq. (5.8) with σ fixed at the typical value expected for copper, $\sim 0.38 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$. (c) Longitudinal field dependence of the muon-spin relaxation rate (λ') associated with the $(1 - \phi)$ contribution in Eq. (5.10); the red dashed line is shown as a guide to the eye.

width $\Delta = \gamma_\mu \sqrt{\langle (\mu_0 H_{\text{loc}} - \langle \mu_0 H_{\text{loc}} \rangle)^2 \rangle}$, where $\gamma_\mu/2\pi = 135.53 \text{ MHz/T}$. Above 40 K, λ_2 is nearly temperature independent ($\sim 0.14 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$). Using $\lambda \approx 0.14 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$ at ZF ($H_{\text{LF}} = 0$) in the Redfield formula [281], $\lambda = 2\Delta^2\nu/[\nu^2 + (\gamma_\mu\mu_0 H_{\text{LF}})^2]$ yields $\Delta \approx 335 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$. This confirms that the system remains in the fast fluctuating regime ($\nu \gg \Delta$).

As the temperature falls below $\sim 20 \text{ K}$, λ_2 increases gradually, signaling a progressive slowing down of fluctuating moments, similar to $1/T_1$. Cooling further below 10 K, an additional faster relaxation component λ_1 appears. Both λ_1 and λ_2 eventually saturate below $T^* \simeq 3.5 \text{ K}$, consistent with a dynamic ground state and reminiscent of the behavior observed in QSL candidates [29, 46]. Moreover, the fractional weight α associated with the fast component, as well as the stretching exponent β , also show a rapid increase and saturate at ~ 0.79 and to a purely phenomenological value of ~ 3.8 , respectively at low temperatures. Constraining $\beta = 2$, the fit yields poor agreement with the early-time data [see Fig. 5.19(a)]. The transformation of the asymmetry shape below T^* from exponential to Gaussian-like indicates that the spin fluctuations have slowed down significantly on approaching a regime where ν becomes comparable to Δ .

Further evidence for persistent spin dynamics comes from the longitudinal-field (LF) dependent relaxation data at $T \simeq 0.1$ K [Fig. 5.18(b)]. To evaluate these fluctuations, we analyzed the data using a composite function [46, 282]

$$A_{\text{LF}}(t) = A_0 G_{\text{DKT}}(t, \Delta, \nu, \mu_0 H_{\text{LF}}) + A_b G_{\text{KT}}(t, \Delta_b, \mu_0 H_{\text{LF}}). \quad (5.9)$$

Here, the first term describes the sample relaxation and decoupling behavior following a Dynamic Gaussian Kubo-Toyabe (DKT) function [283, 284] under applied field, while the second term captures the contribution from muons stopping in the holder, which decouples rapidly in a small field of $\mu_0 H_{\text{LF}} \simeq 0.01$ T. This model gives a reasonable fit to the zero-field data, yielding $\Delta \approx 16.1 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$ and $\nu \approx 13.9 \mu\text{s}^{-1}$, suggesting that the spins approach a quasi-static limit ($\nu \leq \Delta$) at low temperature. However, applying these parameters to simulate field dependence exposes a clear discrepancy: in a purely quasi-static scenario, a field of about ~ 0.1 T would strongly suppress the relaxation, and 0.5 T should decouple it entirely. In contrast, a field as large as 1.5 T could only partially decouple the relaxation [Fig. 5.18(b)], demonstrating that a simple quasi-static picture is inadequate and instead points to the presence of much stronger spin dynamics.

This leads us to adopt a dynamical model based on *sporadic field fluctuations*, which was introduced to explain persistent Gaussian relaxation in kagome bilayer chromates [280, 285]. In this framework, the relaxation function uses the same DKT form scaled by a factor f , namely $G_{\text{DKT}}(t, f, \Delta, f\nu, fH_{\text{LF}})$. Here, the relaxation in the presumed SL state has been explained to arise from the deconfined spinon excitations that intermittently pass near the muon site, producing transient local magnetic fields during only a fraction ft of the muon lifetime. For the remaining time interval $(1-f)t$, the spins form a nearly non-magnetic, possibly singlet background that contributes negligible relaxation.

To describe the field dependence over the entire range, we replaced the first term in Eq. (5.9)

with the expression proposed by Bono et al [285],

$$A_{\text{LF}}(t) = A_0 \left[\phi G_{\text{DKT}}^{\text{sp}}(t, f\Delta, f\nu, f\mu_0 H_{\text{LF}}) + (1 - \phi)e^{-\lambda' t} \right] + A_b G_{\text{KT}}(t, \Delta_b, \mu_0 H_{\text{LF}}). \quad (5.10)$$

The first term describes the dynamic relaxation arising from sporadic fluctuations. Here, ϕ quantifies the fraction of muons experiencing this process, while $(1 - \phi)$ accounts for a conventional exponential relaxation originating from a minority component in which the spin dynamics are slower and more continuous. In analogy with the zero-field model given by Eq. (5.8), the parameter ϕ plays the same role as α , representing the relative weight of the dominant dynamic contribution. This model provides a good fit to the data [Fig. 5.18 (b)], yielding $\nu = 560(5) \mu\text{s}^{-1}$, $\Delta = 555.5(1) \mu\text{s}^{-1} \approx \gamma_\mu \times 0.65 \text{ T}$, and $f = 0.028(1)$. Despite strong local fluctuations with rate ν , the depolarization can appear Gaussian-like because the fluctuation rate satisfies $\nu \approx \Delta$ [282, 285]. At low fields, ϕ is close to unity, making it effectively redundant as a fitting parameter in this regime. As the applied field increases, ϕ decreases [inset of Fig. 5.18(d)], indicating a gradual crossover from predominantly intermittent dynamics to more conventional Markovian fluctuations, enabling us to track how λ' varies with field [see Fig. 5.19(c)] [286]. It should be noted that the fits to the low-field data are not perfect, which may lead to some overestimation of ϕ . Nevertheless, incorporating this second component $(1 - \phi)$ emphasizes that not all regions of the sample contribute equally to the dynamic fluctuations, highlighting a degree of spatial inhomogeneity within the magnetic ground state. Analysis of the zero-field data leads to a similar conclusion: the ground state consists of a dominant dynamic phase (with $\alpha \approx 0.79$) characterized by sporadic spin fluctuations and a minor component ($1 - \alpha \approx 0.21$) exhibiting slower and more heterogeneous relaxation. Such coexisting inhomogeneous dynamics have been observed in other highly frustrated magnets [282, 285, 287]. In this scenario, the observed robust dynamic with pronounced heterogeneity in a coupled trillium lattice, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, represents a remarkable finding, demonstrating the rich landscape

of magnetic correlations in this compound.

5.3 Conclusion

Though the first magnetic study on $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ was reported nearly four decades ago, its magnetic ground state still remains elusive. Our findings pinpoint a dynamic ground state, which is in sharp contrast to an L -type ferrimagnetic transition near 4 K proposed by Battle *et al.* [129]. In $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, Fe^{3+} ions form a frustrated bipartite double-trillium lattice with strong AFM interactions. While a weak feature appears at $T^* \simeq 3.5$ K in low-field $\chi(T)$, a conventional magnetic LRO or spin freezing is ruled out down to 30 mK. Below T^* , both local probes (NMR and μSR) reveal a spatially inhomogeneous dynamic state with two relaxation channels: a dominant and fast-relaxing component ($\sim 80\%$) coexisting with a slower, yet dynamic minority component ($\sim 20\%$). Moreover, the LF μSR data are well captured by a *sporadic-fluctuation model*, drawing a parallel with the kagome bilayers, where a fluctuating RVB background coexists with slowly fluctuating spins [280, 285]. This inhomogeneity in spin dynamics appears to be a unique characteristic feature and a consequence of strong magnetic frustration due to trillium geometry in 3D. Heat capacity exhibits a broad maximum near T^* , which is field-independent, reminiscent of short-range spin correlations and contradicting a conventional magnetic LRO. A further evidence for the dynamic state is obtained from the quadratic temperature dependence of $C_{\text{mag}}(T)$ at low-temperatures.

Altogether, $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ realizes a rare high-spin, 3D frustrated magnet that evades LRO and develops a *mosaic-like* landscape of fluctuating spins with different dynamics. These findings, observed for the first time in a double trillium lattice, establish $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ as a unique material candidate and an ideal model system for exploring frustration-driven, dynamically inhomogeneous magnetism in 3D. Our findings in this chapter further call upon further experimental investigations, such as diffuse neutron scattering, chemical substitution, etc, to uncover the microscopic origin of the observed spin dynamics and to assess the potential proximity of $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ to a canonical SL phase

Chapter 6

Summary and Future Directions

Geometrically frustrated magnets provide a fertile platform for unconventional ground states that emerge from the interplay of lattice geometry, spin quantum number, dimensionality, and anisotropy. In this thesis, we investigated four distinct frustrated magnets: the TLAF $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$, the spin-orbit coupled $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$, and the double trillium lattice AFM $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The structural and magnetic properties were studied using powder x-ray diffraction, AC and DC magnetization, heat capacity, neutron diffraction, ^{31}P NMR, and μSR techniques supported by theoretical modeling and band structure calculations.

$\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ has been established as a spin-5/2 TLAF with magnetic LRO near $T_{\text{N}} \simeq 10.4$ K, with a moderate degree of frustration ($f \simeq 3.6$). The neutron powder diffraction indicates a collinear AFM ground state characterized by the propagation vector $\mathbf{k} = (1, 0, 0)$. Despite its large spin value, the ordered moment below T_{N} is significantly less ($\sim 1.5 \mu_{\text{B}}$) compared to the complete saturation of $\sim 5 \mu_{\text{B}}$, indicative of low dimensionality and magnetic frustration. Furthermore, the field-dependent magnetization of the titled compound exhibits a spin-flop transition at $\mu_0 H_{\text{SF}} \simeq 3.2$ T and fully polarized state near $\mu_0 H_{\text{sat}} \simeq 31.5$ T. This enabled us to construct an H - T phase diagram with distinct AFM, spin-flop, and polarized regimes. In addition, the neutron depolarization measurements confirm AFM domain formation

below T_N . These results highlight how anisotropy, especially an easy-plane XY-type, and frustration compete to stabilize a collinear spin state instead of a conventional 120° non-collinear order expected for a TLAF. In the future, our efforts will focus on the growth of high-quality single crystals of $\text{Na}_3\text{Fe}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and perform inelastic neutron scattering (INS) experiments to probe the low temperature spin dynamics.

The above classical scenario provides a useful reference point to understand how the quantum fluctuations reshape the ground state when low spin systems are chosen. Therefore, we focused on the Co^{2+} -based $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs. In particular, the isostructural cobaltates $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ and $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ represent $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ triangular magnets, where spin-orbit coupling, weak easy-axis anisotropy, and reduced dimensionality lead to successive magnetic transitions. In $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$, the transitions occur at $T_{N1} \simeq 1.47$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 1.22$ K, whereas in $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ they are reduced to $T_{N1} \simeq 0.88$ K and $T_{N2} \simeq 0.67$ K, reflecting the higher degree of frustration in the Ta-compound ($f \simeq 9$) compared to its Nb analog ($f \simeq 5$). High-field magnetization reveals a striking contrast between the two compounds. $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoNb}_2\text{O}_9$ stabilizes the canonical $1/3$ magnetization plateau (*uud* state) expected for TLAFs, whereas $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ enters a broad field-induced regime without plateau features before reaching the saturation field. $C_p(T)$ for Ta-analog is dominated by gapless excitations ($C_p \propto T^2$) in a broad field regime, pointing towards a field-induced quantum disordered phase. Meanwhile, the Nb-analog follows a typical $C_p \propto T^3$, indicating 3D AFM LRO. The exotic phase observed in the Ta analog and not in the Nb compound is likely attributed to the differences in superexchange pathways, where $\text{Co-O-Nb}(4p)\text{-O-Co}$ and $\text{Co-O-Ta}(4f)\text{-O-Co}$ involve different orbital overlaps. Taken together, these results highlight the extreme sensitivity of $j_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ TLAFs to subtle structural and orbital effects, with $\text{Sr}_3\text{CoTa}_2\text{O}_9$ emerging as a promising candidate for a field-induced QSL state. Future investigations, particularly INS and μSR on single crystals in magnetic fields are crucial for uncovering the microscopic nature of these excitations and establishing the full phase diagram of these spin-orbit entangled TLAFs.

The above Co^{2+} -based triangular magnets demonstrate how frustration and anisotropy con-

spire to produce quantum-disordered states in 2D. This naturally motivates the exploration of analogous phenomena in 3D frustrated magnets, where the interplay of geometry and competing interactions may lead to even more exotic ground states. $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ offers a compelling example of such behavior. $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ is a double-trillium lattice formed by Fe^{3+} ($S = 5/2$) ions, presents an unconventional ground state with strong AFM interactions indicated by a large Curie–Weiss temperature ($\theta_{\text{CW}} \simeq -70$ K). No magnetic LRO is detected down to 30 mK. The bulk measurements indicate a characteristic temperature $T^* \simeq 3.5$ K which marks the onset of anomalous low-energy spin dynamics in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$. The $C_p(T)$ data further corroborate this picture, showing a broad, field-independent maximum near 7 K and a quadratic low- T dependence ($C_{\text{mag}} \propto T^2$), indicative of unconventional low-energy excitations in 3D. Furthermore, by implementing the local probes, ^{31}P NMR and μSR reveals an inhomogeneous spin dynamics at low temperatures. Below T^* , ^{31}P NMR experiments show an abrupt, nearly field-independent broadening of the linewidth, accompanied by a suppression of NMR signal intensity and a saturation of the spin–spin relaxation rate $1/T_2$, consistent with a heterogeneous dynamical state. Complementary μSR experiments detect neither static internal fields nor spin freezing down to the lowest temperatures, instead reveal dual relaxation channels: a dominant component ($\sim 80\%$) characterized by fast spin fluctuations and a minority component ($\sim 20\%$) with slower dynamics. The longitudinal μSR data confirm that the faster dynamics correspond to a “sporadic spin fluctuation”. This type of fluctuation is reminiscent of 2D kagome bilayer systems, which establishes the presence of an inhomogeneous and dynamically fluctuating ground state in $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, unique to the trillium network. Band structure calculations reveal multiple competing AFM couplings (J_1 – J_5), with J_4 and J_5 being the dominant ones, while the others are non-negligible, ensuring strong geometric frustration throughout the lattice.

These results mark $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ as the first stoichiometric, high-spin, 3D trillium-based AFM to exhibit such inhomogeneous and persistent spin dynamics. In the future, we intend to perform diffuse neutron scattering that would probe short-range spin correlations directly and assess possible proximity to a spin-liquid regime. Furthermore, controlled chemical substitution

at the alkali or alkaline-earth sites could shed light on the role of residual structural randomness in stabilizing the inhomogeneous state.

Bibliography

- [1] A. A. Mills, *Ann. Sci.* **61**, 273 (2004).
- [2] J. C. Maxwell, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond.* 459 (1865).
- [3] L. Balents, *Nature* **464**, 199 (2010).
- [4] J. Vannimenus and G. Toulouse, *J. Phys. C* **10**, L537 (1977).
- [5] R. Moessner and A. P. Ramirez, *Phys. Today* **59**, 24 (2006).
- [6] H. T. Diep *et al.*, *Frustrated spin systems* (World scientific, 2013).
- [7] N. D. Mermin and H. Wagner, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **17**, 1133 (1966).
- [8] L. Ding, P. Manuel, S. Bachus, F. Grubler, P. Gegenwart, J. Singleton, R. D. Johnson, H. C. Walker, D. T. Adroja, A. D. Hillier, and A. A. Tsirlin, *Phys. Rev. B* **100**, 144432 (2019).
- [9] M. J. P. Gingras and P. A. McClarty, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **77**, 056501 (2014).
- [10] V. Zapf, M. Jaime, and C. D. Batista, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **86**, 563 (2014).
- [11] S. Seki, Y. Onose, and Y. Tokura, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **101**, 067204 (2008).
- [12] Y. Kohama, H. Ishikawa, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, N. Shannon, and Z. Hiroi, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **116**, 10686 (2019).

-
- [13] Y. Shirata, H. Tanaka, A. Matsuo, and K. Kindo, Phys. Rev. Lett. **108**, 057205 (2012).
- [14] Y. Shirata, H. Tanaka, T. Ono, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, and H. Nakano, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **80**, 093702 (2011).
- [15] O. Janson, I. Rousochatzakis, A. A. Tsirlin, M. Belesi, A. A. Leonov, U. K. Rößler, J. Van Den Brink, and H. Rosner, Nat. Commun. **5**, 5376 (2014).
- [16] S.-H. Do *et al.*, Nat. Phys. **13**, 1079 (2017).
- [17] S.-Y. Yang, Y. Wang, B. R. Ortiz, D. Liu, J. Gayles, E. Derunova, R. G.-Hernandez, L. Šmejkal, Y. Chen, S. S. P. Parkin, S. D. Wilson, E. S. Toberer, T. McQueen, and M. N. Ali, Science Advances **6**, eabb6003 (2020).
- [18] E. Lefrançois, G. Grissonnanche, J. Baglo, P. Lampen-Kelley, J.-Q. Yan, C. Balz, D. Mandrus, S. E. Nagler, S. Kim, Y.-J. Kim, N. Doiron-Leyraud, and L. Taillefer, Phys. Rev. X **12**, 021025 (2022).
- [19] V.-D. Nguyen, Y. Perrin, S. Le Denmat, B. Canals, and N. Rougemaille, Phys. Rev. B **96**, 014402 (2017).
- [20] M. Ye and A. V. Chubukov, Phys. Rev. B **96**, 140406 (2017).
- [21] R. Nath, A. A. Tsirlin, H. Rosner, and C. Geibel, Phys. Rev. B. **78**, 064422 (2008).
- [22] Z. Zhu, P. A. Maksimov, S. R. White, and A. L. Chernyshev, Phys. Rev. Lett. **120**, 207203 (2018).
- [23] Y. Iqbal, W.-J. Hu, R. Thomale, D. Poilblanc, and F. Becca, Phys. Rev. B **93**, 144411 (2016).
- [24] Y. Li, P. Gegenwart, and A. A. Tsirlin, J. Phys.: Condens. Matter **32**, 224004 (2020).

-
- [25] Z. Zangeneh, S. Avdoshenko, J. van den Brink, and L. Hozoi, Phys. Rev. B **100**, 174436 (2019).
- [26] A. Sera, Y. Kousaka, J. Akimitsu, M. Sera, T. Kawamata, Y. Koike, and K. Inoue, Phys. Rev. B **94**, 214408 (2016).
- [27] S. Chillal *et al.*, Nat. Commun. **11**, 2348 (2020).
- [28] K. Plumb, H. J. Changlani, A. Scheie, S. Zhang, J. Krizan, J. Rodriguez-Rivera, Y. Qiu, B. Winn, R. J. Cava, and C. L. Broholm, Nat. Phys. **15**, 54 (2019).
- [29] I. Živković *et al.*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **127**, 157204 (2021).
- [30] J. M. Kosterlitz and D. J. Thouless, J. Phys. C, Solid State Phys. **6**, 1181 (1973).
- [31] A. Auerbach, *Interacting Electrons and Quantum magnetism* (Springer-Verlag, London, 1994).
- [32] C. Domb and A. Miedema, J. Low Temp. Phys. **4**, 296 (1964).
- [33] A. Ramirez, Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci. **24**, 453 (1994).
- [34] R. G. Meisenheimer and J. D. Swalen, Phys. Rev. **123**, 831 (1961).
- [35] M. P. Shores, E. A. Nytko, B. M. Bartlett, and D. G. Nocera, J. Am. Chem. Soc. **127**, 13462 (2005).
- [36] M. R. Norman, Rev. Mod. Phys. **88**, 041002 (2016).
- [37] T.-H. Han, J. S. Helton, S. Chu, D. G. Nocera, J. A. Rodriguez-Rivera, C. Broholm, and Y. S. Lee, Nat. **492**, 406 (2012).
- [38] M. Fu, T. Imai, T.-H. Han, and Y. S. Lee, Science **350**, 655 (2015).

-
- [39] T.-H. Han, M. R. Norman, J.-J. Wen, J. A. Rodriguez-Rivera, J. S. Helton, C. Broholm, and Y. S. Lee, *Phys. Rev. B* **94**, 060409 (2016).
- [40] Z. Feng *et al.*, *Chin. Phys. Lett.* **34**, 077502 (2017).
- [41] B. Fåk, E. Kermarrec, L. Messio, B. Bernu, C. Lhuillier, F. Bert, P. Mendels, B. Koteswararao, F. Bouquet, J. Ollivier, A. D. Hillier, A. Amato, R. H. Colman, and A. S. Wills, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 037208 (2012).
- [42] D. Boldrin, B. Fåk, M. Enderle, S. Bieri, J. Ollivier, S. Rols, P. Manuel, and A. S. Wills, *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 220408 (2015).
- [43] R. Chisnell, J. S. Helton, D. E. Freedman, D. K. Singh, R. I. Bewley, D. G. Nocera, and Y. S. Lee, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **115**, 147201 (2015).
- [44] R. Chisnell, J. S. Helton, D. E. Freedman, D. K. Singh, F. Demmel, C. Stock, D. G. Nocera, and Y. S. Lee, *Phys. Rev. B* **93**, 214403 (2016).
- [45] Y. Okamoto, M. Nohara, H. Aruga-Katori, and H. Takagi, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **99**, 137207 (2007).
- [46] P. Khuntia, F. Bert, P. Mendels, B. Koteswararao, A. V. Mahajan, M. Baenitz, F. C. Chou, C. Baines, A. Amato, and Y. Furukawa, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116**, 107203 (2016).
- [47] J. S. Gardner, M. J. P. Gingras, and J. E. Greedan, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **82**, 53 (2010).
- [48] S. T. Bramwell and M. J. Gingras, *Science* **294**, 1495 (2001).
- [49] H. Shinaoka, Y. Tomita, and Y. Motome, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **107**, 047204 (2011).
- [50] J. S. Gardner, S. R. Dunsiger, B. D. Gaulin, M. J. P. Gingras, J. E. Greedan, R. F. Kiefl, M. D. Lumsden, W. A. MacFarlane, N. P. Raju, J. E. Sonier, I. Swainson, and Z. Tun, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **82**, 1012 (1999).

- [51] M. F. Collins and O. A. Petrenko, *Can. J. Phys.* **75**, 605 (1997).
- [52] P. Anderson, *Mater. Res. Bull.* **8**, 153 (1973).
- [53] A. V. Chubukov and T. Jolicoeur, *Phys. Rev. B* **46**, 11137 (1992).
- [54] T. Jolicoeur and J. C. Le Guillou, *Phys. Rev. B* **40**, 2727 (1989).
- [55] A. V. Chubukov, S. Sachdev, and T. Senthil, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **6**, 8891 (1994).
- [56] L. Capriotti, A. E. Trumper, and S. Sorella, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **82**, 3899 (1999).
- [57] B. Bernu, P. Lecheminant, C. Lhuillier, and L. Pierre, *Phys. Rev. B* **50**, 10048 (1994).
- [58] A. L. Chernyshev and M. E. Zhitomirsky, *Phys. Rev. B* **79**, 144416 (2009).
- [59] R. R. P. Singh and D. A. Huse, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **68**, 1766 (1992).
- [60] P. H. Y. Li, R. F. Bishop, and C. E. Campbell, *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 014426 (2015).
- [61] H. Kawamura and S. Miyashita, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn* **53**, 4138 (1984).
- [62] D. Yamamoto, T. Sakurai, R. Okuto, S. Okubo, H. Ohta, H. Tanaka, and Y. Uwatoko, *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 4263 (2021).
- [63] K. Ranjith, R. Nath, M. Majumder, D. Kasinathan, M. Skoulatos, L. Keller, Y. Skourski, M. Baenitz, and A. Tsirlin, *Phys. Rev. B.* **94**, 014415 (2016).
- [64] T. Jolicoeur, E. Dagotto, E. Gagliano, and S. Bacci, *Phys. Rev. B* **42**, 4800 (1990).
- [65] Z. Zhu and S. R. White, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 041105 (2015).
- [66] S. Hu, W. Zhu, S. Eggert, and Y.-C. He, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **123**, 207203 (2019).
- [67] Y.-M. Lu, *Phys. Rev. B* **93**, 165113 (2016).
- [68] J. Sheng *et al.*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **119**, e2211193119 (2022).

-
- [69] Y.-D. Li, Y. Shen, Y. Li, J. Zhao, and G. Chen, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 125105 (2018).
- [70] C. A. Gallegos, S. Jiang, S. R. White, and A. L. Chernyshev, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **134**, 196702 (2025).
- [71] D. Heidarian, S. Sorella, and F. Becca, *Phys. Rev. B* **80**, 012404 (2009).
- [72] M. Q. Weng, D. N. Sheng, Z. Y. Weng, and R. J. Bursill, *Phys. Rev. B* **74**, 012407 (2006).
- [73] S. Yunoki and S. Sorella, *Phys. Rev. B* **74**, 014408 (2006).
- [74] Z. Zhu, P. A. Maksimov, S. R. White, and A. L. Chernyshev, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **119**, 157201 (2017).
- [75] Y. Shimizu, K. Miyagawa, K. Kanoda, M. Maesato, and G. Saito, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **91**, 107001 (2003).
- [76] T. Radu, H. Wilhelm, V. Yushankhai, D. Kovrizhin, R. Coldea, Z. Tylczynski, T. Lühmann, and F. Steglich, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **95**, 127202 (2005).
- [77] R. Coldea, D. A. Tennant, and Z. Tylczynski, *Phys. Rev. B* **68**, 134424 (2003).
- [78] R. Coldea, D. A. Tennant, A. M. Tselik, and Z. Tylczynski, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **86**, 1335 (2001).
- [79] S. Miyahara, K. Ogino, and N. Furukawa, *Physica B* **378**, 587 (2006).
- [80] T. Ono, H. Tanaka, H. Aruga Katori, F. Ishikawa, H. Mitamura, and T. Goto, *Phys. Rev. B* **67**, 104431 (2003).
- [81] T. Ono, H. Tanaka, O. Kolomiets, H. Mitamura, T. Goto, K. Nakajima, A. Oosawa, Y. Koike, K. Kakurai, J. Klenke, P. Smeibidle, and M. Meißner, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter.* **16**, S773 (2004).

-
- [82] W. J. L. Buyers, R. M. Morra, R. L. Armstrong, M. J. Hogan, P. Gerlach, Hirakawa, and K., Phys. Rev. Lett. **56**, 371 (1986).
- [83] Y. Oohara, H. Kadowaki, and K. Iio, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **60**, 393 (1991).
- [84] S. Maegawa, T. Kohmoto, T. Goto, and N. Fujiwara, Phys. Rev. B **44**, 12617 (1991).
- [85] H. Kadowaki, T. Inami, Y. Ajiro, K. Nakajima, and Y. Endoh, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **60**, 1708 (1991).
- [86] R. Ishii, S. Tanaka, K. Onuma, Y. Nambu, M. Tokunaga, T. Sakakibara, N. Kawashima, Y. Maeno, C. Broholm, D. P. Gautreaux, J. Y. Chan, and S. Nakatsuji, EPL. **94**, 17001 (2011).
- [87] M. Lee, J. Hwang, E. S. Choi, J. Ma, C. R. Dela Cruz, M. Zhu, X. Ke, Z. L. Dun, and H. D. Zhou, Phys. Rev. B **89**, 104420 (2014).
- [88] K. M. Ranjith, K. Brinda, U. Arjun, N. G. Hegde, and R. Nath, J. Phys.: Condens. Matter **29**, 115804 (2017).
- [89] M. Lee, E. S. Choi, X. Huang, J. Ma, C. R. Dela Cruz, M. Matsuda, W. Tian, Z. L. Dun, S. Dong, and H. D. Zhou, Phys. Rev. B **90**, 224402 (2014).
- [90] M. Liu, H. Zhang, X. Huang, C. Ma, S. Dong, and J.-M. Liu, Inorg. Chem. **55**, 2709 (2016).
- [91] B. D. Gaulin, T. E. Mason, M. F. Collins, and J. Z. Larese, Phys. Rev. Lett. **62**, 1380 (1989).
- [92] A. Hauser, U. Falk, P. Fischer, and H. U. Güdel, J. Solid State Chem. **56**, 343 (1985).
- [93] L. Heller, M. F. Collins, Y. S. Yang, and B. Collier, Phys. Rev. B **49**, 1104 (1994).
- [94] S. Miyashita and H. Kawamura, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **54**, 3385 (1985).

-
- [95] P.-E. Melchy and M. E. Zhitomirsky, Phys. Rev. B **80**, 064411 (2009).
- [96] R. H. Clark and W. G. Moulton, Phys. Rev. B **5**, 788 (1972).
- [97] H. Kadowaki, K. Ubukoshi, and K. Hirakawa, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **56**, 751 (1987).
- [98] Y. Ajiro, T. Inami, and H. Kadowaki, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn. **59**, 4142 (1990).
- [99] A. Harrison, M. F. Collins, J. Abu-Dayyeh, and C. V. Stager, Phys. Rev. B **43**, 679 (1991).
- [100] Z. Lu, L. Ge, G. Wang, M. Russina, G. Günther, C. R. dela Cruz, R. Sinclair, H. D. Zhou, and J. Ma, Phys. Rev. B **98**, 094412 (2018).
- [101] R. Rawl, M. Lee, E. S. Choi, G. Li, K. W. Chen, R. Baumbach, C. R. dela Cruz, J. Ma, and H. D. Zhou, Phys. Rev. B **95**, 174438 (2017).
- [102] D. Yamamoto, G. Marmorini, and I. Danshita, J. Phys. Soc. Jpn **85**, 024706 (2016).
- [103] D. Yamamoto, G. Marmorini, and I. Danshita, Phys. Rev. Lett. **114**, 027201 (2015).
- [104] L. Seabra, T. Momoi, P. Sindzingre, and N. Shannon, Phys. Rev. B **84**, 214418 (2011).
- [105] O. A. Starykh, Rep. Prog. Phys. **78**, 052502 (2015).
- [106] C. Griset, S. Head, J. Alicea, and O. A. Starykh, Phys. Rev. B **84**, 245108 (2011).
- [107] H. D. Zhou, E. S. Choi, G. Li, L. Balicas, C. R. Wiebe, Y. Qiu, J. R. D. Copley, and J. S. Gardner, Phys. Rev. Lett. **106**, 147204 (2011).
- [108] G. Koutroulakis, T. Zhou, Y. Kamiya, J. D. Thompson, H. D. Zhou, C. D. Batista, and S. E. Brown, Phys. Rev. B **91**, 024410 (2015).
- [109] L. E. Svistov, A. I. Smirnov, L. A. Prozorova, O. A. Petrenko, L. N. Demianets, and A. Y. Shapiro, Phys. Rev. B **67**, 094434 (2003).

-
- [110] Y. A. Sakhratov, O. Prokhnenko, A. Y. Shapiro, H. D. Zhou, L. E. Svistov, A. P. Reyes, and O. A. Petrenko, *Phys. Rev. B* **105**, 014431 (2022).
- [111] T. Nakajima, N. Terada, S. Mitsuda, and R. Bewley, *Phys. Rev. B* **88**, 134414 (2013).
- [112] N. Biniskos, F. dos Santos, M. Stekiel, K. Schmalzl, E. Ressouche, D. Sviták, A. Labh, M. Vališka, N. Marzari, and P. Čermák, arXiv preprint arXiv:2508.21021 (2025).
- [113] M. Saito, M. Watanabe, N. Kurita, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, M. Avdeev, H. O. Jeschke, and H. Tanaka, *Phys. Rev. B* **100**, 064417 (2019).
- [114] Y. Kojima, M. Watanabe, N. Kurita, H. Tanaka, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, and M. Avdeev, *Phys. Rev. B* **98**, 174406 (2018).
- [115] S. Lal, S. J. Sebastian, S. S. Islam, M. P. Saravanan, M. Uhlarz, Y. Skourski, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **108**, 014429 (2023).
- [116] S. Mühlbauer, B. Binz, F. Jonietz, C. Pfleiderer, A. Rosch, A. Neubauer, R. Georgii, and P. Böni, *Science* **323**, 915 (2009).
- [117] X. Z. Yu, Y. Onose, N. Kanazawa, J. H. Park, J. H. Han, Y. Matsui, N. Nagaosa, and Y. Tokura, *Nature* **465**, 901 (2010).
- [118] N. Kanazawa and et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **106**, 156603 (2011).
- [119] J. M. Hopkinson and H.-Y. Kee, *Phys. Rev. B* **74**, 224441 (2006).
- [120] S. Seki, X. Z. Yu, S. Ishiwata, and Y. Tokura, *Science* **336**, 198 (2012).
- [121] V. Kalmeyer and R. B. Laughlin, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **59**, 2095 (1987).
- [122] S. V. Isakov, J. M. Hopkinson, H.-Y. Kee, and Y. B. Kim, *Phys. Rev. B* **78**, 014404 (2008).
- [123] D. Lozano-Gómez, Y. Iqbal, and M. Vojta, *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 10162 (2024).

-
- [124] C. L. Henley, *Annu. Rev. Condens. Matter Phys.* **1**, 179 (2010).
- [125] T. E. Redpath and J. M. Hopkinson, *Phys. Rev. B* **82**, 014410 (2010).
- [126] A. Fancelli, R. Flores-Calderón, O. Benton, B. Lake, R. Moessner, and J. Reuther, *Phys. Rev. B* **111**, 134413 (2025).
- [127] J. M. Bulled, J. A. M. Paddison, A. Wildes, E. Lhotel, S. J. Cassidy, B. Pato-Doldán, L. C. Gómez-Aguirre, P. J. Saines, and A. L. Goodwin, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **128**, 177201 (2022).
- [128] T. Hikita, H. Sekiguchi, and T. Ikeda, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **43**, 1327 (1977).
- [129] P. D. Battle, A. K. Cheetham, W. T. Harrison, and G. J. Long, *J. Solid State Chem.* **62**, 16 (1986).
- [130] M. Kakihana, K. Nishimura, Y. Ashitomi, T. Yara, D. Aoki, and et al., *J. Electron. Mater.* **46**, 3572 (2017).
- [131] I. Živković, J. Hopkinson, H.-Y. Kee, and et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127**, 157204 (2021).
- [132] M. G. Gonzalez, V. Nocolak, A. Sharma, V. Favre, J.-R. Soh, and et al., *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 7191 (2024).
- [133] K. Boya, K. Nam, K. Kargeti, A. Jain, R. Kumar, and et al., *APL Mater.* **10**, 101103 (2022).
- [134] J. Khatua, S. Lee, G. Ban, M. Uhlarz, and et al., *Phys. Rev. B* **109**, 184432 (2024).
- [135] R. Kolay, Q.-P. Ding, Y. Furukawa, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **110**, 224405 (2024).
- [136] J. Khatua, S. Krishnamoorthi, C. Koo, G. Ban, and et al., *Phys. Rev. B* **112**, 064430 (2025).

- [137] G. Castilla, S. Chakravarty, and V. J. Emery, Phys. Rev. Lett. **75**, 1823 (1995).
- [138] W. Lorenz *et al.*, Europhys. Lett. **88**, 37002 (2009).
- [139] H. Kikuchi, Y. Fujii, M. Chiba, S. Mitsudo, T. Idehara, T. Tonegawa, K. Okamoto, T. Sakai, T. Kuwai, and H. Ohta, Phys. Rev. Lett. **94**, 227201 (2005).
- [140] M. Fujihala *et al.*, Sci. Rep. **7**, 16785 (2017).
- [141] N. Shannon, B. Schmidt, K. Penc, and P. Thalmeier, Eur. Phys. J. B **38**, 599 (2004).
- [142] S. Furukawa, M. Sato, and S. Onoda, Phys. Rev. Lett. **105**, 257205 (2010).
- [143] A. Kitaev, Ann. Phys. **321**, 2 (2006).
- [144] S. Trebst and C. Hickey, Phys. Rep. **950**, 1 (2022).
- [145] G. Jackeli and G. Khaliullin, Phys. Rev. Lett. **102**, 017205 (2009).
- [146] B. Lian, X.-Q. Sun, A. Vaezi, X.-L. Qi, and S.-C. Zhang, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. **115**, 10938 (2018).
- [147] Y. Singh and P. Gegenwart, Phys. Rev. B **82**, 064412 (2010).
- [148] S. Hwan Chun *et al.*, Nat. Phys. **11**, 462 (2015).
- [149] Y. Singh, S. Manni, J. Reuther, T. Berlijn, R. Thomale, W. Ku, S. Trebst, and P. Gegenwart, Phys. Rev. Lett. **108**, 127203 (2012).
- [150] T. Takayama, A. Kato, R. Dinnebier, J. Nuss, H. Kono, L. S. I. Veiga, G. Fabbris, D. Haskel, and H. Takagi, Phys. Rev. Lett. **114**, 077202 (2015).
- [151] A. Banerjee *et al.*, Nat. Mater. **15**, 733 (2016).
- [152] S.-H. Baek, S.-H. Do, K.-Y. Choi, Y. S. Kwon, A. U. B. Wolter, S. Nishimoto, J. van den Brink, and B. Büchner, Phys. Rev. Lett. **119**, 037201 (2017).

-
- [153] G. Lin *et al.*, Nat. Commun. **12**, 5559 (2021).
- [154] M. Becker, M. Hermanns, B. Bauer, M. Garst, and S. Trebst, Phys. Rev. B **91**, 155135 (2015).
- [155] I. Rousochatzakis, U. K. Rössler, J. van den Brink, and M. Daghofer, Phys. Rev. B **93**, 104417 (2016).
- [156] T. Dey, A. V. Mahajan, P. Khuntia, M. Baenitz, B. Koteswararao, and F. C. Chou, Phys. Rev. B **86**, 140405 (2012).
- [157] T. Sakamoto, Y. Doi, and Y. Hinatsu, J. Solid State Chem. **179**, 2595 (2006).
- [158] C. Wellm, W. Roscher, J. Zeisner, A. Alfonsov, R. Zhong, R. J. Cava, A. Savoyant, R. Hayn, J. van den Brink, B. Büchner, O. Janson, and V. Kataev, Phys. Rev. B **104**, L100420 (2021).
- [159] H. Liu, J. Chaloupka, and G. Khaliullin, Phys. Rev. Lett. **125**, 047201 (2020).
- [160] T. Susuki, N. Kurita, T. Tanaka, H. Nojiri, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, and H. Tanaka, Phys. Rev. Lett. **110**, 267201 (2013).
- [161] Y. Li, G. Chen, W. Tong, L. Pi, J. Liu, Z. Yang, X. Wang, and Q. Zhang, Phys. Rev. Lett. **115**, 167203 (2015).
- [162] M. M. Bordelon, X. Wang, D. M. Pajerowski, A. Banerjee, M. Sherwin, C. M. Brown, M. S. Eldeeb, T. Petersen, L. Hozoi, U. K. Rößler, M. Mourigal, and S. D. Wilson, Phys. Rev. B **104**, 094421 (2021).
- [163] K. Somesh, S. S. Islam, S. Mohanty, G. Simutis, Z. Guguchia, C. Wang, J. Sichelschmidt, M. Baenitz, and R. Nath, Absence of magnetic order and emergence of unconventional fluctuations in $J_{\text{eff}} = 1/2$ triangular lattice antiferromagnet YbBO_3 .

- [164] H. D. Zhou, C. Xu, A. M. Hallas, H. J. Silverstein, C. R. Wiebe, I. Umegaki, J. Q. Yan, T. P. Murphy, J.-H. Park, Y. Qiu, J. R. D. Copley, J. S. Gardner, and Y. Takano, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 267206 (2012).
- [165] L. Kamiya, Y. Ge, T. Hong, D. L. Qiu, Y. Quintero-Castro, Z. Lu, H. B. Cao, E. S. Matsuda, M. Choi, C. D. Batista, M. Mourigal, H. D. Zhou, and J. Ma, *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 2666 (2018).
- [166] N. Li, Q. Huang, X. Yue, W. Chu, Q. Chen, E. Choi, X. Zhao, H. Zhou, and X. Sun, *Nat. Commun.* **11**, 4216 (2020).
- [167] R. Zhong, S. Guo, L. T. Nguyen, and R. J. Cava, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 224430 (2020).
- [168] R. Rawl, L. Ge, H. Agrawal, Y. Kamiya, C. R. Dela Cruz, N. P. Butch, X. F. Sun, M. Lee, E. S. Choi, J. Oitmaa, C. D. Batista, M. Mourigal, H. D. Zhou, and J. Ma, *Phys. Rev. B* **95**, 060412 (2017).
- [169] I. P. Muthuselvam, R. Sankar, A. V. Ushakov, G. N. Rao, S. V. Streltsov, and F. C. Chou, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 174430 (2014).
- [170] H. Liu and G. Khaliullin, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 014407 (2018).
- [171] R. Sano, Y. Kato, and Y. Motome, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 014408 (2018).
- [172] R. Zhong, T. Gao, N. P. Ong, and R. J. Cava, *Sci. Adv.* **6**, 6953 (2020).
- [173] J. Chadwick, *Nature* **129**, 312 (1932).
- [174] J. Rodríguez-Carvajal, *Physica B* **192**, 55 (1993).
- [175] A. Zieba and S. Foner, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **53**, 1344 (1982).
- [176] A. Morello, W. G. J. Angenent, G. Frossati, and L. J. de Jongh, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* **76**, 023902 (2005).

-
- [177] R. Bachmann, J. DiSalvo, F. J., T. H. Geballe, R. L. Greene, R. E. Howard, C. N. King, H. C. Kirsch, K. N. Lee, R. E. Schwall, H. Thomas, and R. B. Zubeck, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **43**, 205 (1972).
- [178] G. R. Stewart, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **54**, 1 (1983).
- [179] A. Abragam, *Principles of Nuclear Magnetism* (Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1961).
- [180] N. J. Curro, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **72**, 026502 (2009).
- [181] J. J. Sakurai and E. D. Commins, *Modern Quantum Mechanics* (AMERICAN ASSOCIATION OF PHYSICS TEACHERS, Newyork, 1995).
- [182] C. P. Slichter, *Principle of Nuclear Magnetic Resonance*, 3rd ed. (Springer, New York, 1992).
- [183] A. M. Clogston, V. Jaccarino, and Y. Yafet, *Phys. Rev.* **134**, A650 (1964).
- [184] R. Kubo, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **29**, 255 (1966).
- [185] E. L. Hahn, *Phys. Rev.* **80**, 580 (1950).
- [186] S. J. Sebastian, S. S. Islam, A. Jain, S. M. Yusuf, M. Uhlarz, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **105**, 104425 (2022).
- [187] S. J. Sebastian, K. Somesh, M. Nandi, N. Ahmed, P. Bag, M. Baenitz, B. Koo, J. Sichelschmidt, A. A. Tsirlin, Y. Furukawa, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **103**, 064413 (2021).
- [188] N. E. Amuneke, D. E. Gheorghe, B. Lorenz, and A. Möller, *Inorg. Chem.* **50**, 2207 (2011).
- [189] N. E. Amuneke, J. Tapp, C. R. de la Cruz, and A. Möller, *Chem. Mater.* **26**, 5930 (2014).
- [190] A. Möller, N. E. Amuneke, P. Daniel, B. Lorenz, C. R. de la Cruz, M. Gooch, and P. C. W. Chu, *Phys. Rev. B* **85**, 214422 (2012).

-
- [191] G. Nakayama, S. Hara, H. Sato, Y. Narumi, and H. Nojiri, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **25**, 116003 (2013).
- [192] A. Reuß, V. Ksenofontov, J. Tapp, D. Wulferding, P. Lemmens, M. Panthöfer, and A. Möller, *Inorg. Chem.* **57**, 6300 (2018).
- [193] L. D. Sanjeeva, V. O. Garlea, M. A. McGuire, C. D. McMillen, and J. W. Kolis, *Inorg. Chem.* **58**, 2813 (2019).
- [194] S. Lee, R. Klauer, J. Menten, W. Lee, S. Yoon, H. Luetkens, P. Lemmens, A. Möller, and K.-Y. Choi, *Phys. Rev. B* **101**, 224420 (2020).
- [195] A. A. Tsirlin, A. Möller, B. Lorenz, Y. Skourski, and H. Rosner, *Phys. Rev. B* **85**, 014401 (2012).
- [196] S. Lee, C. H. Lee, A. Berlie, A. D. Hillier, D. T. Adroja, R. Zhong, R. J. Cava, Z. H. Jang, and K.-Y. Choi, *Phys. Rev. B* **103**, 024413 (2021).
- [197] J. Tapp, C. R. dela Cruz, M. Bratsch, N. E. Amuneke, L. Postulka, B. Wolf, M. Lang, H. O. Jeschke, R. Valentí, P. Lemmens, and A. Möller, *Phys. Rev. B* **96**, 064404 (2017).
- [198] V. Morozov, B. Lazoryak, A. Malakho, K. Pokholok, S. Polyakov, and T. Terekhina, *J. Solid State Chem.* **160**, 377 (2001).
- [199] M. Belkhiria, S. Laaribi, A. Ben Hadj Amara, and M. Ben Amara, *Ann. Chim.: Sci. Mater.* **23**, 117 (1998).
- [200] Y. Skourski, M. D. Kuzmin, K. P. Skokov, A. V. Andreev, and J. Wosnitza, *Phys. Rev. B* **83**, 214420 (2011).
- [201] A. A. Tsirlin, B. Schmidt, Y. Skourski, R. Nath, C. Geibel, and H. Rosner, *Phys. Rev. B* **80**, 132407 (2009).

-
- [202] J. Rodríguez-Carvajal, *Physica B: Condensed Matter* **192**, 55 (1993).
- [203] S. Todo and K. Kato, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **87**, 047203 (2001).
- [204] A. Albuquerque *et al.*, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater* **310**, 1187 (2007).
- [205] S. S. Islam, K. M. Ranjith, M. Baenitz, Y. Skourski, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 174432 (2018).
- [206] P. W. Selwood, *Magnetochemistry* (Read Books Ltd, ADDRESS, 2013).
- [207] Mendelsohn, Biggs, and Mann, *Phys. Rev. A* **2**, 1130 (1970).
- [208] C. Delmas, G. L. Flem, C. Fouassier, and P. Hagenmuller, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **39**, 55 (1978).
- [209] H.-J. Schmidt, A. Lohmann, and J. Richter, *Phys. Rev. B* **84**, 104443 (2011).
- [210] R. Dingle, M. E. Lines, and S. L. Holt, *Phys. Rev.* **187**, 643 (1969).
- [211] H. Kawamura and S. Miyashita, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **54**, 4530 (1985).
- [212] E. S. R. Gopal, *Specific heats at low temperatures* (Springer Science & Business Media, ADDRESS, 2012).
- [213] R. K. Fitzgerald and F. H. Verhoek, *J. Chem. Educ* **37**, 545 (1960).
- [214] P. Bag, N. Ahmed, V. Singh, M. Sahoo, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **103**, 134410 (2021).
- [215] K. Somesh, Y. Furukawa, G. Simutis, F. Bert, M. Prinz-Zwick, N. Büttgen, A. Zorko, A. A. Tsirlin, P. Mendels, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **104**, 104422 (2021).
- [216] V. K. Anand, L. Opherden, J. Xu, D. T. Adroja, A. D. Hillier, P. K. Biswas, T. Herrmannsdörfer, M. Uhlarz, J. Hornung, J. Wosnitza, E. Canévet, and B. Lake, *Phys. Rev. B* **97**, 094402 (2018).

- [217] S. S. Islam, V. Singh, K. Somesh, P. K. Mukharjee, A. Jain, S. M. Yusuf, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 134433 (2020).
- [218] E. Bertaut, *Magnetism* (GT Rado and H. Shul, eds.) **3**, 149 (1963).
- [219] P. Saeau, Y. Zhao, P. Piyawongwatthana, T. J. Sato, F. C. Chou, M. Avdeev, G. Gitgeatpong, and K. Matan, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 134407 (2020).
- [220] L. J. D. Jongh and A. R. Miedema, *Adv. Phys.* **50**, 947 (2001).
- [221] K. M. Ranjith, R. Nath, M. Skoulatos, L. Keller, D. Kasinathan, Y. Skourski, and A. A. Tsirlin, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 094426 (2015).
- [222] K. M. Ranjith, M. Majumder, M. Baenitz, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 024422 (2015).
- [223] A. V. Chubukov and D. I. Golosov, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **3**, 69 (1991).
- [224] A. I. Smirnov, H. Yashiro, S. Kimura, M. Hagiwara, Y. Narumi, K. Kindo, A. Kikkawa, K. Katsumata, A. Y. Shapiro, and L. N. Demianets, *Phys. Rev. B* **75**, 134412 (2007).
- [225] J. Hwang, E. S. Choi, F. Ye, C. R. Dela Cruz, Y. Xin, H. D. Zhou, and P. Schlottmann, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **109**, 257205 (2012).
- [226] O. A. Petrenko, G. Balakrishnan, M. R. Lees, D. McK. Paul, and A. Hoser, *Phys. Rev. B* **62**, 8983 (2000).
- [227] N. Ahmed, A. A. Tsirlin, and R. Nath, *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 214413 (2015).
- [228] Y. C. Arango, E. Vavilova, M. Abdel-Hafiez, O. Janson, A. A. Tsirlin, H. Rosner, S.-L. Drechsler, M. Weil, G. Nénert, R. Klingeler, O. Volkova, A. Vasiliev, V. Kataev, and B. Büchner, *Phys. Rev. B* **84**, 134430 (2011).

-
- [229] M. Lee, E. Choi, J. Ma, R. Sinclair, C. D. Cruz, and H. Zhou, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **28**, 476004 (2016).
- [230] V. Ting, Y. Liu, R. Withers, and L. Norén, *J. Solid State Chem.* **177**, 2295 (2004).
- [231] D. T. Liu, F. J. Burnell, L. D. C. Jaubert, and J. T. Chalker, *Phys. Rev. B* **94**, 224413 (2016).
- [232] Y. Haraguchi, T. Ohnoda, A. Matsuo, K. Kindo, and H. A. Katori, *Phys. Rev. B* **106**, 214421 (2022).
- [233] P. Pietrzyk, M. Srebro, M. Radoń, Z. Sojka, and A. Michalak, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **115**, 2316 (2011).
- [234] K. Yokota, N. Kurita, and H. Tanaka, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 014403 (2014).
- [235] M. V. Gvozdikova, P.-E. Melchy, and M. E. Zhitomirsky, *J. Condens. Matter Phys.* **23**, 164209 (2011).
- [236] D. Yamamoto, C. Suzuki, G. Marmorini, S. Okazaki, and N. Furukawa, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125**, 057204 (2020).
- [237] E. Grivei, V. Bayot, L. Piraux, and J.-P. Issi, *Phys. Rev. B* **51**, 1301 (1995).
- [238] K. An, T. Sakakibara, R. Settai, Y. Onuki, M. Hiragi, M. Ichioka, and K. Machida, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **104**, 037002 (2010).
- [239] F. Matsubara, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **51**, 2424 (1982).
- [240] G. Quirion, M. Lapointe-Major, M. Poirier, J. A. Quilliam, Z. L. Dun, and H. D. Zhou, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 014414 (2015).
- [241] M. E. Lines, *Phys. Rev.* **131**, 546 (1963).

-
- [242] H. Shiba, Y. Ueda, K. Okunishi, S. Kimura, and K. Kindo, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **72**, 2326 (2003).
- [243] R. Nath, K. M. Ranjith, B. Roy, D. C. Johnston, Y. Furukawa, and A. A. Tsirlin, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 024431 (2014).
- [244] Y. Ran, M. Hermele, P. A. Lee, and X.-G. Wen, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **98**, 117205 (2007).
- [245] M. Hermele, Y. Ran, P. A. Lee, and X.-G. Wen, *Phys. Rev. B* **77**, 224413 (2008).
- [246] S. Kundu, A. Shahee, A. Chakraborty, K. M. Ranjith, B. Koo, J. Sichelschmidt, M. T. F. Telling, P. K. Biswas, M. Baenitz, I. Dasgupta, S. Pujari, and A. V. Mahajan, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **125**, 267202 (2020).
- [247] S. Nakatsuji, Y. Nambu, H. Tonomura, O. Sakai, S. Jonas, C. Broholm, H. Tsunetsugu, Y. Qiu, and Y. Maeno, *Science* **309**, 1697 (2005).
- [248] J. S. Helton, K. Matan, M. P. Shores, E. A. Nytko, B. M. Bartlett, Y. Yoshida, Y. Takano, A. Suslov, Y. Qiu, J.-H. Chung, D. G. Nocera, and Y. S. Lee, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **98**, 107204 (2007).
- [249] L. Clark, J. C. Orain, F. Bert, M. A. De Vries, F. H. Aidoudi, R. E. Morris, P. Lightfoot, J. S. Lord, M. T. F. Telling, P. Bonville, J. P. Attfield, P. Mendels, and A. Harrison, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **110**, 207208 (2013).
- [250] J. G. Cheng, G. Li, L. Balicas, J. S. Zhou, J. B. Goodenough, C. Xu, and H. D. Zhou, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **107**, 197204 (2011).
- [251] O. Mustonen, S. Vasala, E. Sadrollahi, K. P. Schmidt, C. Baines, H. C. Walker, I. Terasaki, F. J. Litterst, E. Baggio-Saitovitch, and M. Karppinen, *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 1085 (2018).
- [252] H. Takagi, T. Takayama, G. Jackeli, G. Khaliullin, and S. E. Nagler, *Nat. Rev. Phys* **1**, 280 (2019).

-
- [253] R. Zhong, M. Chung, T. Kong, L. T. Nguyen, S. Lei, and R. J. Cava, Phys. Rev. B **98**, 220407 (2018).
- [254] P. A. Maksimov, Z. Zhu, S. R. White, and A. L. Chernyshev, Phys. Rev. X **9**, 021017 (2019).
- [255] M. Ulaga, J. Kokalj, A. Wietek, A. Zorko, and P. Prelovšek, (2023).
- [256] M. Watanabe, N. Kurita, H. Tanaka, W. Ueno, K. Matsui, T. Goto, and M. Hagihala, Phys. Rev. B **105**, 054414 (2022).
- [257] S. J. Sebastian, S. S. Islam, R. Kolay, S. Mohanty, Q. P. Ding, Y. Skourski, J. Sichelschmidt, M. Baenitz, J. A. Krieger, T. J. Hicken, H. Luetkens, A. A. Tsirlin, Y. Furukawa, and R. Nath, Inhomogeneous dynamic state in the double trillium lattice antiferromagnet $\text{KBaFe}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$, 2025.
- [258] D. Rauch, M. Kraken, F. J. Litterst, S. Süllow, H. Luetkens, M. Brando, T. Förster, J. Sichelschmidt, A. Neubauer, C. Pfleiderer, W. J. Duncan, and F. M. Grosche, Phys. Rev. B **91**, 174404 (2015).
- [259] A. Suter and B. Wojek, Phys. Procedia **30**, 69 (2012), 12th International Conference on Muon Spin Rotation, Relaxation and Resonance ($\mu\text{SR}2011$).
- [260] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, Computational Materials Science **6**, 15 (1996).
- [261] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, Phys. Rev. B **54**, 11169 (1996).
- [262] J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, and M. Ernzerhof, Phys. Rev. Lett. **77**, 3865 (1996).
- [263] H. J. Xiang, E. J. Kan, S.-H. Wei, M.-H. Whangbo, and X. G. Gong, Phys. Rev. B **84**, 224429 (2011).
- [264] A. A. Tsirlin, Phys. Rev. B **89**, 014405 (2014).

-
- [265] A. A. Tsirlin, I. Rousochatzakis, D. Filimonov, D. Batuk, M. Frontzek, and A. M. Abakumov, *Phys. Rev. B* **96**, 094420 (2017).
- [266] A. F. Albuquerque *et al.*, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* **310**, 1187 (2007).
- [267] B. Koteswararao, R. Kumar, P. Khuntia, S. Bhowal, S. K. Panda, M. R. Rahman, A. V. Mahajan, I. Dasgupta, M. Baenitz, K. Kim, and F. C. Chou, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 035141 (2014).
- [268] C. Kittel, *Introduction to solid state physics* (J. Wiley, Hoboken, NJ, c2005), 500317.
- [269] A. Abragam and B. Bleaney, *Electron paramagnetic resonance of transition ions* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, ADDRESS, 2012).
- [270] H. Takeya, K. Ishida, K. Kitagawa, Y. Ihara, K. Onuma, Y. Maeno, Y. Nambu, S. Nakatsuji, D. E. MacLaughlin, A. Koda, and R. Kadono, *Phys. Rev. B* **77**, 054429 (2008).
- [271] A. Olariu, P. Mendels, F. Bert, B. G. Ueland, P. Schiffer, R. F. Berger, and R. J. Cava, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **97**, 167203 (2006).
- [272] T. Moriya, *Prog. Theor. Exp. Phys.* **16**, 23 (1956).
- [273] T. Moriya, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn* **18**, 516 (1963).
- [274] R. Nath, Y. Furukawa, F. Borsa, E. E. Kaul, M. Baenitz, C. Geibel, and D. C. Johnston, *Phys. Rev. B* **80**, 214430 (2009).
- [275] D. V. Ambika, Q.-P. Ding, S. J. Sebastian, R. Nath, and Y. Furukawa, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* **35**, 015803 (2022).
- [276] A. Amato and E. Morenzoni, *Introduction to Muon Spin Spectroscopy: Applications to Solid State and Material Sciences* (Springer, New York, 2024).

-
- [277] Y. J. Uemura, T. Yamazaki, D. R. Harshman, M. Senba, and E. J. Ansaldo, *Phys. Rev. B* **31**, 546 (1985).
- [278] A. Keren, G. Bazalitsky, I. Campbell, and J. S. Lord, *Phys. Rev. B* **64**, 054403 (2001).
- [279] R. Kadono, J. Imazato, T. Matsuzaki, K. Nishiyama, K. Nagamine, T. Yamazaki, D. Richter, and J.-M. Welter, *Phys. Rev. B* **39**, 23 (1989).
- [280] Y. J. Uemura, A. Keren, K. Kojima, L. P. Le, G. M. Luke, W. D. Wu, Y. Ajiro, T. Asano, Y. Kuriyama, M. Mekata, H. Kikuchi, and K. Kakurai, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **73**, 3306 (1994).
- [281] A. G. Redfield, in *Advances in Magnetic Resonance*, edited by J. S. Waugh (Academic Press, New York, 1965), Vol. 1, pp. 1–32.
- [282] H. Cho, R. Nirmala, J. Jeong, P. J. Baker, H. Takeda, N. Mera, S. J. Blundell, M. Takigawa, D. T. Adroja, and J.-G. Park, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 014439 (2020).
- [283] R. S. Hayano, Y. J. Uemura, J. Imazato, N. Nishida, T. Yamazaki, and R. Kubo, *Phys. Rev. B* **20**, 850 (1979).
- [284] A. Keren, *Phys. Rev. B* **50**, 10039 (1994).
- [285] D. Bono, P. Mendels, G. Collin, N. Blanchard, F. Bert, A. Amato, C. Baines, and A. D. Hillier, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **93**, 187201 (2004).
- [286] See the Supplementary Material at [URL will be inserted by publisher] for more details about material synthesis, x-ray diffraction, AC and DC magnetization, heat capacity, NMR, and μ SR data analysis, as well as DFT calculations. This document also includes Refs. [[45](#), [129](#), [132](#), [258–266](#), [269](#), [274](#)]. (unpublished).
- [287] S. K. Dey, K. Ishida, H. Okabe, M. Hiraishi, A. Koda, T. Honda, J. Yamaura, H. Kageyama, and R. Kadono, *Phys. Rev. B* **107**, 024407 (2023).